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ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

FORENSIC ज्ञान '23

It is indeed our proud privilege to be the hosts for the 2nd International Conference on "Recent Developments in Forensic Science" to be held on 10 and 11 October 2022 at VGU, Jaipur. The Conference has been designed for professionals engaged in various fields of criminal investigation, research & academics. The aim of the conference is to provide an opportunity to bring together the scientific community involved in the various aspects of criminal investigation, as well as to share and discuss the various advances in this field. This two-days international conference will have invited lectures, oral and poster presentations by the participants representing various forensic science institutions & organizations. We take this opportunity that is worth in every aspect endorsing the knowledge and to tune skills to keep us updated in the area of forensic science. It will be our endeavour to make this academic feast a learning experience for one and all. We look forward to your enthusiastic participation to make this a productive and an enjoyable event.

ABOUT THE JOURNAL

ANIL AGRAWAL'S INTERNET JOURNAL OF FORENSIC MEDICINE AND TOXICOLOGY

Anil Aggrawal's Internet Journal of Forensic Medicine and Toxicology is a peer-reviewed electronic journal, available in both CD (ISSN: 0972-8066) and online (ISSN: 0972-8074) formats, dedicated to advancing the field of forensic medicine and toxicology. With a commitment to rigorous peer review, the journal covers a broad spectrum of topics, including forensic pathology, anthropology, toxicology, and genetics. The NLM Unique ID, 100960452, underscores its distinction. Led by an experienced editorial team, the journal attracts global contributions, making it a valuable resource for professionals, researchers, and academics involved in forensic sciences. Its dual-format publication ensures widespread accessibility, catering to diverse preferences within the forensic community.

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FORENSIC ज्ञान '23

PART I ABSTRACT BOOK

3rd International Conference on
Recent development in Forensic Science

FORENSIC ज्ञान '23

The Evolving Technology of DNA Fingerprinting in Criminal Investigation

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ABSTRACT

DNA fingerprinting, a ground-breaking forensic and genetic identification technique, has traversed a remarkable journey since its inception. This abstract offers a concise overview of the past, present, and promising future of DNA fingerprinting. In the late 20th century, Sir Alec Jeffreys pioneered the concept of DNA fingerprinting, revolutionizing the fields of forensics, genetics, and paternity testing. The discovery of highly polymorphic regions in the human genome, known as short tandem repeats (STRs), paved the way for the development of this technique. The past was marked by the manual, labor-intensive process of gel electrophoresis to visualize DNA profiles. In the present era, DNA fingerprinting has evolved significantly. With the advent of polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and capillary electrophoresis, the process has become more efficient, accurate, and rapid. This advancement has led to widespread adoption in criminal investigations, immigration cases, and ancestry tracing. Moreover, the integration of DNA databases and the refinement of analysis software have improved matching and identification capabilities. The future of DNA fingerprinting holds exciting possibilities. The advent of next-generation sequencing (NGS) technologies promises higher resolution, allowing for even more precise identification and differentiation of individuals. Additionally, the emergence of epigenetic and metagenomic fingerprinting opens doors to applications beyond human genetics, including

Keywords: DNA

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CyberGuardians 2.0: Charting the AI Frontier in Cybersecurity

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ABSTRACT

In the face of escalating cyber threats, cybersecurity has become an imperative challenge in our modern world. As cyberattacks grow in sophistication and reach, there is an urgent need for innovative defense mechanisms. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force with the potential to revolutionize cybersecurity. However, comprehending the intricacies of this technology is essential to harness its full potential. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, the proliferation of sophisticated cyber threats

necessitates innovative solutions to safeguard critical information assets. This research paper delves into the paradigm shift brought about by artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in the realm of cybersecurity, presenting an in-depth exploration of the advancements that constitute CyberGuardians 2.0. Through a comprehensive analysis of cutting-edge AI techniques, including deep learning, adversarial machine learning, and explainable AI, this study illuminates the transformative impact of AI-driven cybersecurity strategies. This research paper delves into the future of AI in cybersecurity, emphasizing the development of AI-powered solutions to counter cyber threats. CyberGuardians 2.0 represents the future of cybersecurity, offering a robust defense strategy against the most advanced cyber threats. By providing a comprehensive overview of the future of AI in cybersecurity and proposing this innovative vision, this research paper stands as a significant contribution to the cybersecurity domain.

Keywords: Machine learning, CyberGuardians 2.0, Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, Cyber threats, Deep learning

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Relation Between Psychopathy And Serial Killer

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ABSTRACT

Psychopathy is a personality disorder characterized by traits such as callousness, superficial charm, and a lack of empathy. Research has consistently shown a significant correlation between psychopathy and involvement in criminal activities. Individuals with psychopathic traits may be more inclined to engage in criminal activities due to their impulsivity, risk-taking behaviour, and disregard for social norms. The correlation between psychopathy and serial murder has been the subject of extensive study, as these individuals often exhibit a chilling blend of charm and ruthlessness, enabling them to prey on victims repeatedly. Understanding the interplay between psychopathy and the development of serial killers sheds light on the dark intricacies of human behaviour and remains a critical area of investigation in criminology and psychology. Ethical dilemmas surrounding the treatment and sentencing of psychopathic offenders further underscore the importance of continued research and interdisciplinary collaboration to address the multifaceted issue of psychopathy in criminal behaviour. It is essential to note that not all psychopaths become serial killers, and not all serial killers have psychopathic traits, but there is a significant overlap between psychopathy and criminal behaviour.

Keywords – Psychopathy, Serial Murder, Criminology, Human Behaviour, Ethical dilemma.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Handprint Dimensions For Sex Classification: The ABC Model Of Forensic Science

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ABSTRACT

Forensic science plays a crucial role in providing investigators with valuable evidence in criminal investigations. One area of focus within this field is the analysis of handprints, which can provide valuable information about the individual who left the print. The ABC model, also known as the anatomical, biological, and cultural model, is a widely used framework in forensic science for analyzing various aspects of human anatomy. When it comes to determining sex based on handprints, this model provides a comprehensive approach that considers anatomical differences, biological factors, and cultural influences. The ABC model of forensic science provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing handprint dimensions for sex classifications. By considering anatomical, biological, and cultural factors, forensic experts can make informed determinations about the sex of an individual based on handprints. The findings can serve as crucial evidence in criminal investigations, helping to narrow down potential suspects and aid in the pursuit of justice. The review explores the key aspects of the ABC model in relation to handprint analysis for sex classifications. By further understanding the complexities involved in this field, we can enhance the accuracy and reliability of forensic science applications and contribute to the advancement of criminal investigations.

Keywords: Forensic Science, ABC Model, Handprint Analysis, Sex Determination

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

The Role Of Forensic Genealogy In Solving Age-Old Cases

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ABSTRACT

"The Role of Forensic Genealogy in Solving Age-Old Cases" explores the significant impact of forensic genealogy in solving long-standing criminal cases. Our aim is to showcase the power of using DNA technology and genealogical research in identifying perpetrators and victims of crimes that have remained unsolved for years. It highlights the use of advanced tools, such as DNA databases and genetic genealogy techniques, to create family trees and identify potential suspects or victims. The challenges and ethical considerations involved in using forensic genealogy, as well as its potential to bring closure to families and justice for victims, are also discussed. Forensic genealogy combines traditional genealogical research with DNA analysis to identify individuals involved in criminal investigations or

historical mysteries. Forensic Genealogy has become a popular tool in criminal investigations since it first emerged in 2018. FG is a novel investigatory tool that has been applied to hundreds of unresolved cold cases in the United States to generate investigative leads and identify unknown individuals. Consumer DNA testing and the public's increased curiosity about their own DNA and genetic ancestry, have greatly contributed to the availability of human genetic data. Genetic genealogy has been a field of study/interest for many years as both amateur and professional genetic genealogists use consumer DNA data to explore genetic connections in family trees. FG encompasses this knowledge by applying advanced sequencing technologies to forensic DNA evidence samples and by performing genetic genealogy methods and genealogical research, to produce possible identities of unknown perpetrators of violent crimes and unidentified human remains. This combination of forensic genetics, genetic genealogy, and genealogical research has formed a new subdiscipline within the forensic sciences.

Keywords: Forensic Genealogy, Consumer DNA testing, genealogy

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Application of RM-Y Short Tandem Repeats (STRs) in DNA Fingerprinting

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ABSTRACT

DNA fingerprinting is a powerful forensic and genetic identification technique that relies on the analysis of specific genetic markers known as Short Tandem Repeats (STRs). While conventional STRs are located on autosomal chromosomes and the X chromosome, the RM-Y STRs, found exclusively on the Y chromosome, offer a unique avenue for genetic profiling in male individuals. This abstract explores the significance and applications of RM-Y STRs in DNA fingerprinting. RM-Y STRs exhibit several distinct advantages, such as their haploidy, which allows for unambiguous interpretation in male individuals. Additionally, these markers are highly polymorphic, making them suitable for distinguishing closely related male individuals. Furthermore, RM-Y STRs have a low mutation rate, ensuring the stability of profiles over generations. The applications of RM-Y STRs in forensic science include the identification of male suspects, the reconstruction of male lineage in familial cases, and the resolution of complex cases where autosomal STRs provide inconclusive results. RM-Y STRs also find utility in population genetics, anthropology, and evolutionary studies, shedding light on the male-specific genetic history of human populations. In conclusion, RM-Y STRs constitute a valuable addition to the DNA fingerprinting toolkit, offering a specialized tool for male individual identification and lineage tracing. Their unique properties and applications make them an indispensable asset in forensic investigations and genetic research, contributing to the broader

understanding of human genetics and evolution.

Keywords: RM-Y, STR, DNA, Male, Individuals

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Significance of Section 65 of IEA, 1872 in Digital Evidence

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ABSTRACT

Section 65 of the Indian Evidence Act of 1872 should be a key point of discussion. Today, every case is decided in part by the use of digital evidence. Oral and documented evidence are the two types available. Again, there are two categories of documentary evidence: primary evidence and secondary evidence. The Indian Evidence Act, 1872 addresses documented evidence in Sections 61 to 90A. The method outlined in Sections 61 to 90A of the Indian Evidence Act governs the admission of any documents offered as evidence in both civil and criminal proceedings. The Indian Evidence Act, 1872 Sections 65A and 65B should be followed while presenting electronic evidence. A certificate from the devices & owner or authorized user is required for electronic evidence to be admitted into evidence. Additionally, the party submitting the secondary evidence must have a legitimate reason for doing so and make an effort to present the primary evidence first. Additionally, the party must state why it filed secondary evidence after considering all of the alternatives listed in Section 65 of the Indian Evidence Act. The Court has the power to accept the same as supplemental evidence.

Keywords: digital evidence, Indian Evidence Act, primary, secondary

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Digital Detectives 2.0: Enhancing Forensic Analysis with AI and ML

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ABSTRACT

This comprehensive review paper delves into the transformative integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) in the realm of forensic pathology, a critical facet of forensic science. Historically reliant on manual examination, the advent of AI and ML technologies has revolutionized forensic practice, ushering in automated tools for analysis, interpretation, and decision-making based on intricate

patterns and data. The significance of this integration lies in its potential to markedly enhance the accuracy, speed, and objectivity of forensic assessments, offering a promising solution to longstanding challenges in the field. The research critically analyzes the applications, benefits, ethical considerations, limitations, and future prospects of AI and ML in forensic pathology, emphasizing the collaborative dynamic between human experts and AI systems. A mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative analyses, is employed, drawing from academic papers, case studies, and pertinent databases. Content analysis techniques are applied to extract meaningful insights. Various applications of AI and ML in forensic pathology are elucidated, including automated pattern recognition, digital image analysis, predictive modelling, and time of death estimation. These technologies hold immense potential for advancing the field, offering precise identification of abnormalities, cause of death determination, and accurate time of death estimation. The integration of AI and ML presents a range of advantages, notably improved accuracy and objectivity, enhanced efficiency and speed, and the capability to handle large volumes of data. By mitigating human error and bias, AI systems offer more reliable forensic assessments, expedite analysis processes, and address backlog issues in forensic labs. Ethical and legal considerations are scrutinized, with a focus on mitigating biases in AI algorithms, safeguarding data privacy and security, and navigating the admissibility of AI-generated evidence in court. This review provides a comprehensive understanding of the implications of AI and ML in forensic pathology, offering valuable insights for practitioners, researchers, and policymakers alike.

Key words: forensic pathology ,artificial intelligence (AI) ,machine learning(ML), Interpretation, analysis

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Unconscious Bias vs. Conscious Beliefs: Attitudes In Contrast

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ABSTRACT

There is a conceptual distinction that some theories have put forth between judgments that are the outcome of introspection and are referred to as explicit attitudes and judgments that may exist outside of conscious knowledge or conscious control and are referred to as implicit attitudes. By recognizing that the human mind is more than the sum of its conscious operations, this conceptual distinction acknowledges this. Explicit attitudes are those that we are aware of and prepared to self-report, in contrast to implicit attitudes, which are automatic and not immediately conscious accessible. Well look into the psychological processes that underlie these attitudes, with a particular emphasis on how socialization, culture, and personal experiences help people

develop explicit attitudes as well as how automatic mechanisms, stereotypes, and heuristics help people develop implicit attitudes. Any potential differences in these degrees of attitudes will also be discussed. Well go over implicit attitude assessment techniques like the Implicit Association Test (IAT) as well as the moral dilemmas that come with revealing underlying prejudices. A more sophisticated understanding of human behavior and the development of strategies to lessen the impact of unconscious biases in a variety of societal contexts are both expected to benefit from increased knowledge of these various attitudes. I go over implicit attitude assessment techniques like the Implicit Association Test (IAT) as well as the moral dilemmas that come with revealing underlying prejudices. A more sophisticated understanding of human behavior and the development of strategies to lessen the impact of unconscious biases in a variety of societal contexts are both expected to benefit from increased knowledge of these various attitudes.

Keywords – explicit attitudes, implicit attitudes, unconscious bias, heuristics, psychological processes.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Neuroimaging In Lie Detection: Unveiling The Truth In The Brain

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ABSTRACT

Lie detection has long been a challenge with traditional methods as it shows limitations in accuracy, dependability, and application in various domains, such as law enforcement and social contacts. The beginning of neuroimaging techniques, such as Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Electroencephalography (EEG), has offered a promising path for exploring the neural connections with deception. This study provides an overview of the role of neuroimaging in lie detection. Neuroimaging allows us to examine changes in brain activity connected with deception, offering potential understandings of the cognitive processes involved in this process. Research studies show that these techniques have uncovered specific brain regions and patterns of activation linked to deception. However, neuroimaging in the practical lie detection application faces many challenges and controversies. The limitations of these techniques, such as their sensitivity to the situation and the need for further validation, should be acknowledged. Questions of privacy and potential misuse also require careful consideration. Despite these challenges, neuroimaging in lie detection is promising as a tool for enhancing our understanding of the complex relationship between the brain and deception. Future research may find other improved procedures and ethical rules for its responsible use, potentially developing the field of lie detection.

Keywords: Deception, Neuroimaging, Cognitive Process, Instrumentation.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

The Consistency of Handwriting Analysis: An Examination of Its Reliability When Self Disguised

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ABSTRACT

Handwriting analysis is the study and analysis of handwriting patterns to determine a person's personality. Some experts argue handwriting analysis remains consistent even when a person intentionally disguises their writing. This examines the reliability of handwriting analysis when confronted with disguised handwriting. context, perplexity, burstiness, and the expertise of the graphologist are crucial factors. Skilled professionals undergo extensive training and possess a deep understanding of the complexities involved in analyzing handwriting. Experts can identify subtle patterns, such as pressure, letter shapes, and spacing, which remain consistent even when a person disguises their writing. Their ability to differentiate between intentional modifications and inherent traits enhances the reliability of their analysis. While the consistency and reliability of handwriting analysis when confronted with disguised writing may be subject to debate, it remains an intriguing field of study. Despite intentional alterations, certain underlying patterns and characteristics often persist, offering valuable insights into a person's true self. By considering these aspects, handwriting analysis can provide meaningful and reliable results, even when confronted with intentionally disguised writing. Handwriting analysis, when conducted can unravel hidden truths and shed light on the unique individual behind the pen.

Keywords: Graphology, Disguised Writing, Handwriting analysis.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

A Review on Use of Diatom Identification to Determine the Cause and Manner of Death

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ABSTRACT

Diatoms have been widely used in forensic sciences as trace evidence collected from clothing or shoes because they are difficult to move or destroy at a crime scene. In forensic practice, it can be challenging to tell whether a body in the water was dumped there after passing away or drowned. Despite being a time-consuming and difficult task, diatom testing is currently a crucial supporting tool for identifying drowning deaths and drowning sites. This article offers a novel approach for the potential use of deep learning in diatom testing as well as reviews the evolution of diatom testing over the years. Although diatom testing is crucial in drowning instances, more effective diatom testing techniques must be developed. This article analyzes the evolution of diatom testing

over the years and explores a novel approach for the future use of deep learning in diatom testing. Diatom species are distinguished by forensic pathologists based on visual inspection of their morphologies and patterns, which are well-preserved even after chemical digestion.

Keywords: Forensic sciences, forensic pathology, diatoms, drowning, deep learning.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Forensic Biology and DNA Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Forensic biology and DNA analysis play a crucial role in criminal investigations by providing scientific evidence that can link suspects to crime scenes or victims. This abstract aims to provide an overview of forensic biology and DNA analysis, highlighting their significance and impact in the field of criminal justice. Forensic biology involves the application of biological principles and techniques to analyze evidence collected from crime scenes. This can include the examination of bodily fluids, such as blood, saliva, semen, or hair, as well as other biological materials like tissues or bones. The goal of forensic biologists is to identify and analyze these samples to extract valuable information that can aid in solving crimes. DNA analysis is a fundamental component of forensic biology. DNA, or deoxyribonucleic acid, is a molecule that carries genetic information unique to each individual. Through DNA analysis, forensic scientists can compare DNA profiles obtained from crime scene evidence with those of potential suspects or victims. This comparison allows for the identification or exclusion of individuals based on their genetic profiles. The process of DNA analysis involves several steps. First, DNA is extracted from the collected samples, which can be challenging depending on the quality and quantity of the biological material. Once extracted, the DNA is amplified through a process called polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which produces millions of copies of specific DNA regions for analysis. The amplified DNA is then subjected to various techniques, such as restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), short tandem repeat (STR) analysis, or single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) analysis, to generate a DNA profile. Forensic biologists compare DNA profiles by examining specific regions of the DNA known as genetic markers. These markers are highly variable among individuals, making them useful for identification purposes. By comparing the patterns of genetic markers between crime scene samples and potential suspects, forensic scientists can determine if there is a match or exclusion. The significance of forensic biology and DNA analysis in criminal investigations cannot be overstated. DNA evidence has proven to be a powerful tool in identifying perpetrators, exonerating the innocent, and solved cases.

Keywords - Genetic makers, polymorphism, Forensics.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Investigating the Role of Insects in Myiasis among Humans

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ABSTRACT

Forensic entomology is the use of insects and their arthropod relatives that are necrophagous in nature meaning they feed on decaying remains and can be helpful to aid the legal investigations. This study investigates myiasis, a condition caused by the infestation of fly larvae on living tissue, which is commonly found in decaying matter. The study focuses on examining changes in the feeding preference of flies from dead animals to live tissue in domestic animals & Humans. Forensic entomologists can provide invaluable aid in death cases where human remains are colonized by insects and in overall investigation. Some forensically important families are Calliphoridae, sarcophagidae, and muscidae. Studying myiasis can help us identify potential health risks and public health concerns associated with this condition, particularly in areas where flies are in close contact with humans such as dumping grounds, grave yards, mortuaries in hospital etc. From a forensic perspective, the presence of these species could help in estimating the time of death of a deceased individual, as the lifecycle and development of these species are closely associated with the decomposition process. Moreover, their presence can help in the detection of foul play or any other criminal activity associated with the death of the individual. The presence of these species may indicate the occurrence of recent or ongoing deaths in the area. This can be a useful indicator for forensic investigators and law enforcement officials who may need to investigate and gather evidence related to these deaths. From a medical perspective, the presence of these species raises concerns for public health, as they are known to transmit various diseases and infections to humans.

Key words - myiasis, dead bodies, live tissue, time of death, maggot, forensic investigations, criminal activities, calliphoridae, sarcophagidae, muscidae, public health.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Are We Losing The Evidentiary Value of Fingerprint Evidence in the Court of Law ?

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ABSTRACT

Fingerprints have been used as a significant piece of evidence in the court of law from way back to prove or disprove the facts of the case.

The field is emerging day by day and thus fingerprint remains one of the most accurate and reliable forensic evidence in the court of law. Even though it is frequently challenged in the court of law for its reliability and validity. There is no question about the value of this piece of scientific evidence, but the procedural errors play a pivotal role in the authenticity of this crucial evidence. Here comes the role of the expert who is involved in the process, is lacking. It is evident from the various landmark judgements that the question of the fingerprint evidence is actually raised on the procedural errors that has been made by the scientific community. And it is found that on one pretext or the other, the evidence is not appreciated in the criminal cases and is not given due evidential importance. The reasons being chain of custody, faulty handling, preservation, packing, forwarding and many such. This paper is an attempt to highlight unrevealed facts with the help of landmark judgements delivered by the honourable supreme court of India, and also to highlight the importance of fingerprint evidence in the investigation and adjudication of justice focusing upon cases where the evidence has been looked down upon for multiple procedural reasons. Author has also made an effort to recommend certain ways to reduce the errors of scientific community during the process.

Keyword: Fingerprint, Criminal justice system, Expert evidence, Admissibility, evidentiary value

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Identification of Victims In Mass Disasters

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ABSTRACT

Accidental Phosphine Inhalation is a silent killer that has claimed many lives. This gas is colorless, odorless, and highly toxic. It is commonly found in pesticides and fumigants used in agriculture and stored grain facilities. Accidental inhalation can cause severe respiratory distress, leading to death. This poster will provide an overview of accidental phosphine inhalation and its effects. Phosphine is commonly used as a fumigant to control pests in stored grain facilities and in agriculture. It is also produced naturally in the decomposition of organic matter. Exposure to phosphine can occur through inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact. Symptoms of exposure include headache, dizziness, nausea, vomiting, and respiratory distress. The toxicity of Phosphine is highly toxic and can cause severe respiratory distress. It works by inhibiting the production of ATP in cells, leading to cell death. The Toxic effects of phosphine are due to its ability to bind to proteins and disrupt cellular metabolism. Exposure To high levels of phosphine can lead to pulmonary edema, cardiac arrest, and death. Accidental phosphine inhalation is a serious public health concern. It is important to be aware of the sources of phosphine and the symptoms of exposure. Early recognition and treatment are critical for a successful outcome. Prevention of exposure through proper protective equipment, ventilation, and education is key to reducing the risk of accidental phosphine inhalation.

Keywords: Phosphine, Toxic, Inhalation.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Extraction of DNA from Dandruff

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ABSTRACT

Forensic analysis plays a critical role in criminal investigations, and obtaining DNA from biological samples is a crucial step in this Process. Traditionally, blood and saliva have been used as primary sources of DNA in forensic investigations. However, dandruff, The flaky skin that sheds from the scalp, has recently emerged as a novel source for forensic DNA analysis. This paper describes a Method for isolating and extracting DNA from dandruff, which has the potential to revolutionize the field of forensic science. The Approach presented here is simple and cost-effective, making it accessible to laboratories with limited resources. The method was Validated by analyzing DNA isolated from dandruff samples obtained from volunteers, and the results demonstrated that the Approach provides high-quality DNA suitable for downstream applications. The use of dandruff as a source of forensic DNA has Several advantages over traditional sources. Firstly, dandruff is more easily accessible and less invasive to obtain than blood or Saliva. Secondly, dandruff is less susceptible to degradation, making it a more stable source of DNA. Finally, dandruff contains a Higher concentration of human DNA than other biological samples, increasing the likelihood of obtaining a complete DNA profile Overall, the results of this study suggest that dandruff could represent a valuable source of forensic DNA and have a significant. Impact on the field of forensic science. The approach described here provides a simple and cost-effective method for laboratories. To obtain high-quality DNA from dandruff samples, potentially improving the accuracy and efficiency of forensic investigations. DNA could be extracted form dandruff because of a particular case in which we were involved, a study was carried out to determine whether or not DNA could be extracted form dandruff, and if the two most widely used extraction techniques (Chelex and organic) would be applicable. Results show that sufficient quantities of DNA (more than 30 to 40ng) can be obtained from as little as 1.0 to 1.5mg of dandruff. Both methods yield DNA, although the organic procedure seems to yield more (72.5ng Chelex vs. 183.3 ng organic).

Keywords: Forensic science, dandruff, DNA typing, polymerase chain reaction, HUMTH01, HUMvWA

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Fingerprint Biometrics in Forensic Science

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ABSTRACT

Modern forensic science heavily relies on fingerprint biometrics since they provide a reliable and tried-and-true way of identifying a

specific person. The importance and uses of fingerprint biometrics in forensic investigations are highlighted in this abstract. Each person's fingerprints are distinct and unique, with distinctive ridge counts, minute points, and complex ridge patterns. Latent fingerprints collected at crime scenes are matched by forensic professionals using these distinctive qualities to recognize people in databases. This method of identification using fingerprints acts as a crucial component in resolving crimes and connecting suspects, victims, and crime scenes. Modern fingerprint analysis techniques like automated fingerprint recognition algorithms and identification systems (AFIS) have greatly accelerated and increased the precision of latent print matching. Furthermore, the creation of non-intrusive techniques for gathering latent biometrics allows a person to be identified and authenticated based on recognizable, verifiable, unique, and specific data. The aim is to capture an item of biometric data from this person. It can be a photo of their face, a record of their voice, or an image of their fingerprint.

Keywords: Forensic science, biometric, fingerprint

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

The Ethics of Forensic Genealogy: Legal and Social Implications

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ABSTRACT

This poster presentation delves into the captivating realm of forensic genealogy, a cutting-edge field at the intersection of genetics, law, and society. By employing genetic genealogy databases and techniques to solve cold cases and identify unknown individuals, forensic genealogy has become a powerful tool in the hands of law enforcement. However, this newfound power raises intricate ethical questions regarding privacy, consent, and the potential for unintended consequences. Through a comprehensive exploration of legal and social implications, this presentation aims to stimulate dialogue on the ethical boundaries that govern the utilization of genetic information in the pursuit of justice. Join us as we navigate this complex terrain and contemplate the delicate balance between advancing forensic science and safeguarding individual liberties.

Keywords: forensic genealogy, law enforcement, consent, safeguarding

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Aging of Bitemarks: A Forensic Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This review will explore the potential of porcine skin as an in-vivo model for understanding the ageing process of human bite marks in forensic odontology. Human bite marks, often crucial in criminal investigations, undergo dynamic changes over time due to various factors, including environmental conditions and biological responses. This research aims to bridge the knowledge gap by investigating the similarities and dissimilarities between human and porcine skin, shedding light on the ageing mechanisms of bite marks. Porcine skin shares structural and compositional similarities with human skin, making it a promising candidate for modelling bite mark ageing. This study involves the careful examination of bite marks inflicted on porcine skin, subjecting them to controlled environmental conditions and monitoring the progression of changes over time. Factors such as tissue degradation, wound healing, microbial activity, and environmental influences are closely observed. By establishing porcine skin as a viable in-vivo model, forensic experts can gain valuable insights into the ageing patterns of human bite marks. This research not only contributes to enhancing our understanding of the underlying processes but also bolsters the reliability of forensic evidence presented in criminal cases. Ultimately, such advancements hold the potential to improve the accuracy and fairness of the criminal justice system.

Keywords: Porcine skin, Promising

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Microexpression In Detection of Deception

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ABSTRACT

Microexpression is a momentary, involuntary, facial expressions that people unconsciously display when they are hiding an emotion. They are quick and intense expressions of concealed emotion. They are considered as reliable indicators of emotions, as they are difficult to control or suppress. Microexpressions were first introduced by Paul Ekman in the 1960s, and have since been studied in the field of psychology. When someone is lying, they may experience a flash of emotions that they are trying to hide, such as fear, disgust, or contempt. The emotions are visible in the form of microexpression. Microexpression detection has been shown to be an effective way to detect deception in a variety of settings, including law enforcement, security, and business. Microexpressions are of particular interest to researchers and practitioners in a variety of fields, including forensic psychology as it helps in criminal investigation.

Key words: Microexpression, Deception, Detection, Practitioner

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Ecological Insights into the Diversity and Distribution of Forensic Insect Species Associated with Mortuary of Civil Hospital, Nashik

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ABSTRACT

This research paper investigates the diversity and distribution of forensic insect species commonly found in mortuary environment of Civil Hospital, Nashik. The study identifies six key species: *Chrysomya albiceps*, *Chrysomya megacephala*, *Chrysomya saffrana*, *Musca domestica*, *Sarcophaga ruficornis*, *Chrysomya bezziana*. These species exhibit varying natural habitats, feeding preferences, and modes of dispersal. The presence of these species in mortuaries is primarily attributed to their attraction to decaying organic matter (viscera) a prevalent resource in such environments. Additionally, species like *C. bezziana* may be attracted to decaying matter and thus they can be found on dead bodies during the present study. The specific combination of species at a mortuary can also be influenced by environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and the timing of death and body discovery. *C. megacephala* in particular is highlighted as a prominent early colonizer of vicinity of mortuary due to its affinity for various decomposing organic materials. These findings provide valuable insight into the ecological dynamics of forensic insect species occur in mortuary environments contributing to the field of forensic entomology, enhancing our understanding of decomposition ecology and aiding in the estimation of post-mortem intervals (PMI) in forensic investigations.

Keywords: Forensic entomology, mortuary, forensic insect diversity, post-mortem interval (PMI)

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

The Ever-Changing Trends in Legal High - Xylazine's Emergence in Drug Abuse

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ABSTRACT

Drug abuse is a common problem and an increasing threat. And designer drugs are the modern solution to this problem. For every drug restricted there exists another to provide similar or even better effects. This popular trend is due to these drugs being on the very fine line which differentiates between legal and illegal. The study explores the extent to which designer drugs have improved and continue to do so. It also examines the up-and-coming drugs such as HHC, xylazine, fentanyl, etc, primarily the use of xylazine with fentanyl to increase the drug's effect. These are commonly known as

tranq-dope and also responsible for numerous overdose cases, many even resulting in death. The study outlines the mechanism of action of xylazine which is a non-opioid veterinarian drug not for human usage but because of its CNS depression characteristics has become a substitute to already existing drugs. It also highlights the current scenario related to this particular drug from a national and global point of view and future possibilities of increase in its usage. It includes a thorough review of literature and empirical data with supporting information pertaining to its high trade and distribution. It also brings into the equation the challenges faced both in treatment and rehabilitation.

Keywords :- Designer drugs, Drug abuse, Xylazine, tranq- dope, mechanism of action

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Body Fluid Identification in Forensics: Current Practices and Future Endeavor

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ABSTRACT

Identification and origin of body fluids found at a crime scene can prove to be prime insights while linking victim, suspect, and crime scene. Since decades numerous techniques and methods have been introduced and employed to identify body fluids which include chemical tests, immunological tests, protein catalytic activity tests, spectroscopic methods and microscopy. These conventional identification methods are generally presumptive as well as destructive and stagnant in nature. Also, one method can be carried out for only one fluid at a time. Due to such limitations of conventional methods, technological advances have led the way to the use of new molecular genetics based approach using RNA and DNA markers. Various RNA markers and tDMRs (tissue-specific differentially methylated regions) have been identified which are forensically significant and are specific to different body fluids. This review provides an insight into the current and conventional knowledge as well as recent developments in the field of body fluid identification. The field of forensic science needs to be assisted by advancing molecular techniques to evolve current body fluid detection techniques for fulfilling the requirements of the criminal justice system in a better way.

Keywords: Body fluid identification, RNA, DNA Methylation, tDMRs, miRNA, spectroscopy.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

The Role Of Forensic Accounting In White Collar Crime Investigations

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ABSTRACT

Considering the complex financial issues that frequently underlie these crimes, forensic accounting is a crucial tool in the field of white-collar crime investigations. White-collar crimes usually entail embezzlement, corporate fraud, insider trading, and money laundering and are characterized by deceit, financial manipulation, and non-violent techniques. The qualified experts tasked with separating the financial web of such offenses are forensic accountants. The primary aim of forensic accounting in white-collar crime is to uncover financial irregularities by providing financial expertise in the identification of financial misconduct. They collect, analyze, and preserve financial records, documents, and data that can be used as evidence in legal proceedings. Forensic accountants follow the money trail and trace the flow of funds to determine how the crime was committed, where the money went, and who benefited from it and quantify the losses accordingly. To track the movements of illegal funds, these professionals carefully examine financial records, transactions, and supporting paperwork. They use cutting-edge auditing methods, data analysis, and forensic tools to find anomalies, fraud, and hidden assets that could otherwise go undetected. In order to demonstrate a clear narrative of wrongdoing, they play the role of financial detectives by reconstructing financial histories and time frames. Not only are forensic accountants skilled investigators, but they also make excellent witnesses in court. They offer their conclusions with authority and clarity, translating sophisticated financial terminology into terms that judges and juries can understand. This testimony can make or break a case because it establishes a strong connection between the perpetrators of financial crimes and the wrongdoers themselves. Furthermore, the influence of forensic accounting goes beyond specific cases. These experts are relied upon by organizations to improve internal controls and risk management procedures, strengthening their barriers against potential financial crimes. By doing this, forensic accountants contribute significantly to protecting the integrity of financial systems and ensuring that justice is done in the constantly changing world of white-collar crime.

Keywords: White-collar crime, Forensic accountants, Fraud.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

The Nexus Between Drug Abuse and Criminal Behavior: A Review

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ABSTRACT

This review explores the intricate relationship between drug abuse and criminal behavior. Drug abuse often impels individuals to commit crimes through various mechanisms. Pharmacologically, substances can impair judgment and lower inhibitions, leading to impulsive criminal acts. Socioeconomic factors associated with drug abuse, such as poverty and unemployment, can drive individuals to criminality as a means of sustaining their addiction. Moreover, drug-related activities, including trafficking and distribution, contribute to criminal enterprises. Specific crimes, such as property offenses and violence, are closely linked to substance abuse. This relationship forms a cycle, where addiction fosters criminality and vice versa. The criminal justice system plays a pivotal role in responding to drug-related crimes, offering opportunities for rehabilitation and diversion. This review underscores the importance of holistic approaches that address both substance abuse's root causes and its accompanying criminality. Understanding these dynamics is vital for policymakers, healthcare professionals, and law enforcement to develop effective strategies to mitigate the societal impact of drug abuse. This paper's synthesis of existing literature provides valuable insights into this complex issue and advocates for a comprehensive, integrated approach to tackle drug abuse and its consequences.

keywords: criminal behavior, drugs, CNS, drug-related activities, rehabilitation, law enforcement.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Blood Spatter Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Blood spatter analysis (BPA) is an integral part of crime scene investigation. For violent crimes involving gunshots, standard practice in police departments worldwide have some physical limitations. For instance, the effect of gravity and air drag on trajectories of blood droplets are neglected using current reconstruction methods, which results in a well-known overestimation of the height of the source of blood. As a consequence, more sophisticated models for blood spatter trajectory reconstruction are being developed, two of which are highlighted in the present work. They allow the prediction of bloodstain patterns produced from backward spattered blood droplets from blunt and sharp bullets. Our recent models attribute the splashing of blood to the Rayleigh–Taylor instability which arises when blood is accelerated towards lighter air. This physically based description comes with the powerful predictive capability to correlate features of bloodstain patterns with the specific bullet and gun that produced them, as well as with the body position. The results of the numerical models were compared with four experiments simulating blood spatter deposition on a vertical wall through the number of stains produced, average stain area, and

average impact angle at the surface, and the agreement found is fairly good. Moreover, further insight is obtained by probing and explaining the influence of observable parameters on the resulting spatter pattern, with the goal of aiding BPA experts evaluating a crime scene. The goal of BPA is to provide answers to questions arising from the scene of a violent crime such as what caused these patterns. Determination of the region of origin of the blood spatter is expected from the BPA community however, current techniques lack a fundamental basis in fluid mechanics. Namely, the method of strings, or the trigonometric method, which has been in use since as early as the 1950s and is implemented in widely distributed software neglects physical realities such as gravity and air drag.

Keywords: Bloodstain analysis, BPA, Crime scene investigation.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

EDXRF and ATR-FTIR Based Elemental Profiling & Characterization of Commonly Used Smokeless Tobacco Products in Gujarat State

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ABSTRACT

The use of smokeless tobacco (ST) is common globally, with high prevalence rates in India. Among the 275 million tobacco users in India, almost 60% (164 million) use ST products; whereas, an additional 15% (42 million) use both ST and combustible tobacco products (American Cancer Society, 2015). In addition to tobacco, several South Asia ST products (gutkha, some zarda and khaini products) also contain areca nut. Also, a popular hand-made preparation called Pan (betel quid) often contains ST products, such as zarda and quiname mixed with alkaline agents and areca nut (US HHS, 2014). Few chewing tobaccos and zarda had the lowest levels of un-protonated nicotine (0.10–0.52% and 0.15–0.21%, respectively), whereas Gul, Gudhaku, and Khaini had the highest levels, ranging from 95.33 to 99.12%. In the present study, we made use of two sophisticated instruments EDXRF and ATR-FTIR and have found radioactive elements Sr, Si, Ca, S, Rh, K, Ti, V, Mn, Fe, Cu, Zn, Rb, Zr, P, Ar, Ba, Br, Y, Cl in several brands of ST like Musagul, Parag Pan masala, Vimal, R.D etc. Such radioactive elements and some other compounds are already established to be grave dangers for the human body. ST's health concerns and addiction dangers are worsened by the high proportion of bioavailable nicotine coupled with flavours. The findings of this study have important implications for the regulation and use of ST in countries where use of ST is prevalent.

Keywords: - Smokeless tobacco, Nicotine, Radioactive elements, Instrumentation, EDXRF, ATR-FTIR.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Forensic Investigation of Bullet Holes for Determining the Distance from Glass Fragments

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ABSTRACT

Fragments of glass are substantial physical evidence found in different scenes in an investigation. In cases where firearms are involved, glass fractures may provide valuable information related to what happened and help investigate the crime scene. Glass can be fractured intentionally or unintentionally at the crime scenes. Analysis of glass fracture pattern often provides much significant information like causes of fracture, the direction of a bullet hitting the target, impact on fracture pattern from distance and direction, etc. Holes occurred in the glass at the crime scenes have much importance and many attempts are taken to investigate the properties of these glass holes to find the type, speed, and angle of the projectile which probably produced the hole. These bullet holes in glass can exhibit certain features and fractures for high-velocity projectiles including bullets. The objective of this research was to determine the distance of a shooter from the bullet hole on glass used in automobiles. Bullet holes were prepared and different parameters of glass fractures like bullet hole diameter, cone fractures radius, cone fractures diameter, radial, and concentric fracture count were considered from both front and the backside of the glass. Bullet hole distance help in determine the distance of weapon from glass some time it play evidential role in investigation. The determination of distance was related to the factors and parameters used in this research and also to some other environmental factors. If factors or parameters are changed then resulting observations and results will also change accordingly. These findings can be supportive of forensic criminal investigations along with new related detective parameters for researchers. Bullet holes investigation to determine these factors with the help of fracture analysis can be helpful to construct rational judgment by interpreting the evidence, for forensic investigations.

keywords: substantial physical evidence, concentric, parameter, Radial fracture.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

The Effectiveness of Different Drug Treatment Program for Offenders

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ABSTRACT

This abstract will provide an overview of the effectiveness of various drug treatment programs for offenders. Research has shown that drug addiction is a significant factor contributing to criminal behavior. Therefore, implementing effective treatment programs for offenders with substance abuse issues is crucial in reducing recidivism and

promoting rehabilitation. This review examines a range of drug treatment programs, including residential rehabilitation centers, outpatient programs, and medication-assisted treatments. It analyzes the impact of these programs on reducing drug-related offenses, improving the well-being of participants, and preventing relapse. Furthermore, this abstract will explore the importance of tailoring treatment programs to the specific needs of offenders, taking into account factors such as the type of substance abuse, the severity of addiction, and the presence of co-occurring mental health disorders. The findings suggest that comprehensive, evidence-based drug treatment programs that offer a combination of counseling, therapy, and medication support tend to be more effective in reducing recidivism among offenders. However, successful outcomes also depend on factors such as program duration, participant engagement, and post-release support. In conclusion, this abstract underscores the significance of implementing effective drug treatment programs for offenders to address the root causes of criminal behavior, reduce reoffending rates, and contribute to their successful reintegration into society. Further research and evaluation of these programs are necessary to refine and improve their effectiveness.

Keywords: Rehabilitation, Recidivism, Drug treatment programs, Offenders

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

The Impact of Erotic Media on Sexual Behaviour.

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ABSTRACT

The impact of erotic media on sexual behaviour is a complex and debated topic. Erotic media, including pornography and explicit content in various forms, has become increasingly accessible due to the internet and modern technology. While some argue that consuming erotic media can have both positive and negative effects on sexual behaviour, it is essential to recognize that individual responses vary widely. On one hand, proponents suggest that erotic media can serve as a source of sexual education and exploration. It may help individuals better understand their desires, and preferences, and even improve their sexual self-confidence. Additionally, it can be a tool for couples to enhance their intimacy by introducing new ideas or fantasies into their relationship. However, there are concerns regarding the potential negative impacts of excessive consumption of erotic media. Some studies suggest that it might lead to unrealistic expectations, desensitization to real-life sexual encounters, and addiction-like behaviours. Overconsumption can also contribute to relationship problems and intimacy issues. Ultimately, the impact of erotic media on sexual behaviour depends on various factors, including individual susceptibility, frequency of consumption, and the nature of the content. It is crucial for individuals to maintain a balanced approach, use it as a tool for exploration and education rather than a substitute for real intimacy, and be aware of its potential consequences on their sexual behaviour and relationships. In conclusion, the influence of erotic media on sexual behaviour is a complex matter with both positive and negative aspects.

Recognizing its potential benefits and pitfalls, individuals should approach it thoughtfully, ensuring that it augments rather than hinders their sexual experiences and relationships.

Keywords: erotic media, sexual behaviour, pornography, unrealistic expectations, addiction.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Role of Muscle Fiber During Estimation of Time Since Death

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ABSTRACT

The Time since Death is Important for Forensic Pathologist to Estimate Postmortem Interval to give Report and Present it in the Court of Law. The Time since Death is Estimated as after some Interval of Time the Body Undergoes different changes and starts to show different signs like Pallor Mortis, Algor Mortis, Livor Mortis. Primary flaccidity, rigor mortis, and secondary flaccidity muscle changes occurs after livor mortis. Physiology is disturbed as muscle Fiber that is Actin and Myosin shorten in length because no resynthesis. Muscle lost the property of Flaccidity during rigor mortis. This action is acidic in nature it leads to lactic acid formation. H Zone Distance Increases during secondary flaccidity. All this muscle fiber changes occurs at different time Interval after Death, so time since death can be estimated. After this body starts Decomposing and becomes skeletonized. According to our study, we have observed that calculation of time since death is varying with different factors. So there is a further need to evolve this study more particularly we have to study blood lactic acid concentration during muscle fiber changes for comparing and making a standard so that time since death can be calculated more appropriately.

Keywords:- Primary flaccidity, Rigor Mortis, Secondary flaccidity, Actin-myosin

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Break the Chains : END Human Trafficking

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ABSTRACT

According to Indian Penal Code (IPC) Section 370, Human trafficking is an abhorrent and prevalent crime that violates fundamental human rights and takes advantage of the weak. It is a serious and widespread crime that infringes on fundamental human rights and uses people for forced labor, sexual exploitation, or organ harvesting,

among other uses. Millions of individuals are affected by this issue, which is global in scope and disproportionately affects women and children. Initiatives or policies taken by the Indian government for women and children, trafficking is the Immoral Traffic Prevention Act 1956 (ITPA) for the prevention of trafficking of commercial Sexual Exploitation. This could involve making bogus job offers, improved opportunity guarantees, or kidnapping. The varied character of anti-human trafficking initiatives is described in this abstract, which emphasizes the necessity of a thorough strategy for effectively combating this horrible crime. Human abuse, and coercion. In 2007, Indian government launched a scheme 'UJJWALA' for the prohibition of trafficking. Prevention tactics emphasize public awareness, community education, and tackling underlying issues including poverty and education disparities. To break up criminal networks, intervention entails taking legal action, identifying victims, and prosecuting traffickers. The main goals of rehabilitation programs are to help survivors physically and psychologically, merge them into society, and teach them in skills that will enable them to live independently in the future. Collaboration between governments, non-governmental organizations, law enforcement, and international organizations is essential in the battle against human trafficking.

Keywords:- Trafficking, Organ harvesting, Kidnapping, NGO, Victim.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Asphyxial Drowning

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ABSTRACT

In literal words, drowning can be defined as suffering 'death by submersion in water or any liquid because of being unable to breathe'. Drowning denotes a confined concept where death is suffered due to submersion in water or any other liquid. That's why when an autopsy is done, one has to pay attention to make out the differences that are caused due to drowning and those that are otherwise. It is also said that the deaths that are caused due to drowning are considered 'asphyxial deaths'. Asphyxial death refers to the situation where the respiratory passage is occupied by the fluid, i.e., water or any other fluid, due to submersion and inhalation of the fluid. Drowning deaths are considered when the nostrils and mouth are occluded by water or any other liquid. In many cases, the medium of drowning is water, but in some cases, the medium is any fluid other than water, such as in a vat of beer. When a person falls into the water who cannot swim, he/she immediately tends to sink to the depth proportionate to the momentum accrued during the fall, weight and specific gravity of the body and to some extent, the nature of clothing. The person at this stage may die either from the concussion following the head injuries due to the fall from the height or due to heart failure or from sudden cardiac arrest. There are two types of drowning- Wet drowning and Dry drowning. Death in fresh water takes 4-5 minutes, whereas in sea water, it takes 8-12 minutes. Diagnosis of death drowning can be established from the following observations: (i) external signs of drowning, (ii) internal signs of drowning, (iii) biochemical signs of drowning.

Key words: water or fluid, submerging, falling, suffocation, death.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Anthracycline Drugs in Cancer: from Mechanism to Resistance and Toxicity

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ABSTRACT

Due to its capacity to identify and eliminate cancer cells, anthracycline antibiotics are crucial in the treatment of cancer. This activity of anthracyclines is due to their capability to inhibit topoisomerase II from anthracycline interactions among two adjacent DNA bases and generate hydroxyl free radicals related to antitumor consequences and toxicity in healthy tissues leads to cellular death and most cancers mobile acceleration. Anthracyclines in their early stages are effective against many different forms of cancer and are a key component of many combination regimens. However, its efficacy may be inhibited by the development of its immunosuppressive effects, including P-glycoprotein-mediated antagonism, particularly in the heart, gonadal tissues and blood. The toxicity of anthracyclines is also well documented, with cardiac toxicity being a major concern. Myocardial tissue is particularly susceptible to free radical damage. Anthracycline can lead to both systolic and diastolic dysfunctions in the heart. In addition, anthracycline damages gonadal tissue and also increases haematological toxicity, affecting both fertility and well-being. Anthracycline has great implications in forensic science in cases of sudden cardiac events or health complications that cannot be explained and leads to death, especially in individuals with a history of anthracycline therapy. A forensic expert also investigates whether past drug exposure played a role in the antagonistic results. Additionally, anthracycline can be used as a poison in cases of homicide or intentional injury. Knowing their presence in post-mortem samples and observing their distribution in different organs can provide crucial evidence and insight into traumatic death situations.

Keywords- Anthracycline, drug, cancer, resistance, toxicity.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Advancement of Age Estimation Using Human Skeleton Helps in Forensic Science

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ABSTRACT

The Anthropometry is a progression of organized estimating strategies that express quantitatively the elements of the human body and

skeleton. Anthropometry is many times seen as a traditional and maybe the fundamental device of biological anthropology, however it has a long practice of purpose in measurable sciences and it is tracking down expanded use in clinical sciences particularly in the discipline of forensic medicine. It is exceptionally evenhanded and dependable in the possession of prepared anthropometrics. The importance and significance of osmometry, cephalometry, craniometry and osteometry in the distinguishing proof of human remaining parts have been depicted and another term of measurable anthropometry is coined. While age assessment of unidentified cadavers and skeletons for recognizable proof purposes has a long custom in criminological sciences, age assessment of living people has shaped a somewhat ongoing area of scientific exploration which is turning out to be progressively significant. The global interdisciplinary Review Gathering on Measurable Age Diagnostics (AGFAD) gave proposals for age assessment of living people with the end goal of criminal, common, shelter and advanced age benefits methods as well concerning deciding the sex and period of skeletons. Progresses enlisted in late examination incorporate the subjects of taphonomy influence, new physical areas of interest, histology, populace variety, the dental mash chamber, innovation, numerical methodologies, biochemical examination and strategies explicitly focusing on the living. This article surveys the authentic improvement old enough assessment techniques and thinks about probable future bearings.

Keywords: AGFAD, Osmometry, Cephalometry, Craniometry, Anthropometrics

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Integration of Drone Technology in Crime Scene Reconnaissance

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the integration of drone technology has revolutionized various sectors, and law enforcement is no exception. Drones, or Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), have rapidly gained prominence in crime scene reconnaissance due to their ability to provide a unique aerial perspective. This perspective offers law enforcement agencies valuable insights, enabling them to conduct more efficient and effective investigations. By capturing high-resolution images, conducting 3D modelling, and enhancing situational awareness, drones have the potential to significantly enhance the process of evidence collection, scene documentation, and overall crime scene management. The primary aim of this article is to comprehensively explore the integration of drone technology in crime scene reconnaissance. We will delve into the diverse applications of drones in criminal investigations, highlighting their advantages and potential drawbacks. Through an examination of real-world case studies, we seek to provide a holistic understanding of how law enforcement agencies are leveraging drone technology to improve their investigative processes. Additionally, we will address the ethical, legal, and operational challenges that accompany this integration,

emphasizing the need for responsible and transparent use of drones in the pursuit of justice. The integration of drone technology into crime scene reconnaissance represents a pivotal advancement in modern law enforcement. Drones offer unparalleled capabilities for evidence collection, scene documentation, and situational awareness, facilitating more efficient and effective investigations. However, the adoption of drone technology also presents ethical, legal, and operational challenges that demand careful consideration. As law enforcement agencies continue to embrace these aerial tools, striking a balance between their benefits and potential risks is paramount. By addressing these challenges and fostering responsible drone usage, we can enhance the pursuit of justice while upholding the principles of privacy and legality in the ever-evolving landscape of criminal investigations.

Keywords: Forensic drones, Privacy concerns, Crime scene investigation.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Forensic Psychology and Criminology Police Psychology : Organizational Behaviour and Human Resource Management in Policing

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ABSTRACT

Policing is a task that involves protecting society and serving the community. The research paper delves into the connection between police psychology behaviour and human resource management in the context of modern policing. The goal is to understand how these areas impact the effectiveness, efficiency and ethical conduct of law enforcement agencies. One important aspect is police psychology, which focuses on the health, well being and performance of officers. The paper will explore how stress, trauma and emotional resilience affect their decision making process, behaviour towards others and interactions with the public. Additionally it will discuss strategies to improve officers psychological fitness in order to address these challenges effectively. The study of how organisations function in the field of policing involves an examination of the workings of law enforcement agencies. Also carefully analyse leadership styles, communication patterns and the overall culture, within these organisations to understand the impact on officer performance, job satisfaction and the effectiveness of the agency as a whole. The main focus is on creating a work environment and fostering a culture that values accountability within police organisations. This paper highlights the interconnected relationship between police psychology behaviour and human resource management in addressing the current challenges faced by law enforcement. It delves into the issues of establishing trust with the public, managing community relations and adapting to changing societal and technological landscapes. The paper proposes an approach that combines these three areas as a way to improve the effectiveness of policing, promote behaviour and

enhance community relations.

Keywords: Resource management, Modern policing, Psychological fitness, Leadership styles.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Exploring the Correlation Between Internet Addiction and Deviant Behaviour

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ABSTRACT

This comprehensive review paper investigates the intricate relationship between internet addiction and various forms of deviant behaviour in today's digital age. It examines existing research and empirical evidence to explore the extent to which internet addiction may contribute to or be influenced by deviant behaviour such as cyberbullying, online fraud, and social dysfunction. By shedding light on this complex interplay, the study provides critical insights into the implications of internet addiction for individual and collective behaviour. The findings not only highlight the potential repercussions for mental health and social well-being but also underscore the need for proactive interventions and strategies to address the challenges posed by excessive internet use. This paper contributes to a deeper understanding of the evolving dynamics between technology and deviance in contemporary society, with relevance for policymakers, educators, and mental health professionals.

Keywords: Deviant Behaviour, Internet Addiction, Cyberbullying, Mental Health.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Domino India Cyber Attack: Massive Data Breach Exposes 1.8 Billion Orders.

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ABSTRACT

In a startling development, Domino India, one of the country's leading pizza delivery chains, has fallen victim to a severe cyber attack resulting in the compromise of personal data from a staggering 1.8 billion customer orders and 10 lakh credit cards that were used to purchase on the company's application. The breach, which has sent shockwaves through the Indian tech and cyber security landscape, has exposed sensitive customer information, including names, addresses, phone numbers, and email addresses. This breach serves as a stark reminder of the growing threats posed by cybercriminals and the urgent need for

robust cyber security measures across industries. The fallout from this breach is expected to have far-reaching consequences for both Domino's India and its customers, raising questions about the security practices of organizations handling sensitive personal data. This abstract offers a glimpse into the scale and impact of the Domino's India cyber attack, underscoring the importance of proactive cyber security measures and data protection strategies in an increasingly digital world.

Keywords – cyber attack, cyber security landscape, shockwaves, proactive cyber security.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Cold Cases and Forensic Advances: How Modern Technology is Changing Investigations

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ABSTRACT

Modern technology has had a significant influence on forensic science and cold case investigations, revolutionizing how law enforcement agencies approach and resolve these age-old mysteries. In contemporary cold case investigations, finding a balance between employing technology to forward the cause of justice and preserving individual rights is still difficult. The possibility of resolving old mysteries and giving victims and their families closure, however, continues to rise as a result of using these tools and strategies. Various technologies such as Forensic genetic genealogy, DNA analysis, National Missing and Unidentified Persons System (NamUs) for investigation of cold cases. These advancements in forensic technology have significantly increased the chances of solving cold cases that were previously left unresolved.

Keywords: Modern technology, cold case, investigations.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Fluid Dynamics of Bloodstain Pattern Analysis

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ABSTRACT

A crucial area of forensic science called bloodstain pattern analysis is useful for reconstructing crime scenes and understanding the circumstances surrounding violent incidents. This explores the complex connection between fluid dynamics and the development of bloodstain patterns. It reveals the secrets hidden patterns by examining the profound influence of fluid behaviour on the form of

size, and distribution of bloodstains. Understanding bloodstain patterns can be done through a special lens called fluid dynamics, a field of physics that studies the motion of fluids. Fundamental concepts are first explained, including viscosity, the characteristics of Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids, and how fluids react to impact. Understanding the mechanisms that cause bloodstains to form is based on these principles. The influence of impact angle and velocity on bloodstain patterns is one of the key ideas explored. Analysts can pinpoint the angle and point of origin of blood spatter by using fluid dynamics principles, making it easier to reconstruct the sequence of events that resulted in bloodshed. We highlight the useful applications of fluid dynamics in forensic investigations, drawing on real-world case studies and controlled experiments. These cases serve as an example of how fluid dynamics can help investigators crack cases by corroborating or disputing witness accounts, reconstructing the course of events, and locating potential offenders. In conclusion, this highlights the profound influence of fluid dynamics on the discipline of forensic science, illustrating how a thorough comprehension of fluid behaviour is essential for revealing the mysteries concealed in bloodstain patterns and advancing the cause of justice.

Keywords- Bloodstain, Analysis, Fluid, Newtonian, Investigation.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Age Estimation of Archeological Evidences Using DNA Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Molecular genetics is an underrated branch of Forensic science, which has an indefensible use of molecular genetical structures like DNA and RNA. Even though massive irreplaceable factors like identification of individuals, parenting cases etc... have been revealed by DNA analysis which gave this technique a dominant chessman in the foundation of Forensic science. However, as the modern technology grew, the aspects of molecular genetics in Forensic science also latrogenically changed to a doorway of thousands. Age estimation is an indivisible indicator of identification of humans which is exceedingly advantageous. For a few decades, age estimation is done using the technique called carbon dating. As the era have changed, the databases should be updated. Therefore, here we are igniting a new technique of age estimation by molecular genetical constituents like DNA, mainly on archeological evidences. DNA methylation and Telomere length examination are Stonehenge and Callanish of age estimation by DNA analysis in Forensic science. DNA methylation is a process of addition of methyl group to DNA and whereas the Telomere length examination uses the scaling of telomere which is then compared to a metric system called flow-fish, which was developed by Peter Leinsdorf in 2006. Overall, we conclude that these two methods are very cost effective and gives high range of accuracy, which makes these approaches felicitous for age estimation.

Keywords:- molecular genetics, DNA, Carbon Dating

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Exploring the Use of DNA Methylation Patterns in Monozygotic Twins for Forensic Identification

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ABSTRACT

Monozygotic (MZ) twins, who share identical genetic profiles, pose unique challenges in forensic identification. Traditional DNA fingerprinting methods struggle to differentiate MZ twins. However, DNA methylation, an epigenetic modification involving methyl groups added to cytosine residues, offers a promising solution. Despite their genetic sameness, MZ twins exhibit distinct methylation patterns. This epigenetic variability allows for their differentiation, enhancing forensic analysis capabilities. Additionally, the influence of environmental factors on methylation patterns underscores the importance of considering both genetics and the environment in forensic investigations involving MZ twins. Methods such as bisulfide sequencing and DNA methylation microarrays provide reliable, sensitive, and specific means of distinguishing MZ twins. Nevertheless, addressing legal and ethical concerns, standardization, and legal admissibility remains essential for the successful integration of DNA methylation into forensic practice. Continued research and collaboration between scientists, geneticists, and legal experts are imperative to unlock DNA methylation's potential in resolving identity in challenging MZ twin cases, ultimately advancing forensic science.

Keywords: DNA fingerprinting, Monozygotic twins, DNA methylation, Epigenetic modification.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Robotic Tactile Sensing Via Biomimetic Fingerprint

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ABSTRACT

Tactile sensors have advanced significantly since the early 1970s, there are still no options that are commonly used. Haptic sensing makes use of a number of technologies, including magnetic, optical, piezoelectric, and piezoresistive. The majority of sensors, however, are not mechanically reliable for many applications and struggle to handle curved or sizable surfaces. We present a 3D-printed fingerprint pattern to improve the body-borne vibration signal for dynamic tactile feedback in an effort to solve this issue. The 3D-

printed fingerprint designs were created and put through testing for a robot hand the size of the RH8D adult. Applications including dexterous robotic grasping, intelligent prosthetics, and surgical robots are made possible by tactile sensing, which is a key technological advancement. The basic purpose of tactile sensors is to simulate mechanoreceptors. The location, shape, and strength of touches can be determined using tactile sensors, among other things. The force and many contact locations can be calculated using the instantaneous pressure or force. On the other hand, dynamic tactile sensations are better able to deduce details regarding texture as well as rolling or slipping. A practical solution to some of tactile sensing's problems is vibrotactile sensing. The method has been put to the test in a number of applications, including tactile sensing, prosthetic texture perception, and social touch classification.

Keywords: Tactile sensor, Haptic sensor, Prosthetics, Piezoelectric, 3D Fingerprint

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Retrospective Study of Pattern of Head Injury in Victims of Fatal Road Traffic Accident in Rewari Region of Haryana

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ABSTRACT

The study of pattern of head injury in victim of fatal road traffic accident in Rewari region of Haryana. the study identify, head injury is caused by mechanical forces that results in damage to the scalp, skull and brain. There are three types of head injury: subdural hemorrhage, subarachnoid hemorrhage and epidural hemorrhage. Most common head injury is subdural hemorrhages and sub arachnoid hemorrhages. Depending on weather the dura mater was torn, the type of brain injury might either be open or closed. In situation of road traffic accident, many types of head injury such as scalp abrasions, contusion, lacerations, incised wound and there are many more fractures. As per WHO around 1.2 million individuals worldwide pass away in traffic accident each year. since the skull is the most susceptible area of the body, head injuries are the leading cause of death in road traffic accidents.

Keywords: Hemorrhage, Subarachnoid hemorrhage, epidural hemorrhage, contusion, lacerations, incised wound, fractures.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Effectiveness of MFCC Feature Extraction in Classifying and Identifying Disguised Voices: A Study Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

The field of law enforcement as well as the field of forensic physics has long been concerned with speaker recognition, and over the years, speaker recognition systems have evolved with technological advancements. However, the deliberate disguise of voices has posed a significant challenge to the effectiveness of these systems. To address this issue, various algorithms have been continuously developed. This research contributes to the ongoing efforts to enhance speaker recognition systems, offering valuable insights into their performance and potential improvements, ultimately bolstering their effectiveness in law enforcement applications. This paper focuses on classifying disguised voices using MFCC (Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients) feature extraction, employing machine learning algorithms like Random Forest and Decision Tree for classification and detection of original and disguised voices. The study also explores the impact of noise on speaker recognition. The dataset comprised 31 speakers and 217 speech samples including original and various types of disguised voices. The results revealed that voice disguise has a notable effect on classifier performance. Random Forest classifier achieved the best result, accurately classifying both original and disguised voices with better accuracy. To enhance the accuracy rates of the classifiers, future work may involve the incorporation of additional parameters and the expansion of the training dataset. These measures hold promise for improving the performance of speaker recognition systems, especially when faced with disguised voices in law enforcement applications.

Keywords: Forensic Physics, Forensic voice analysis, Voice disguise, MFCC, Random Forest, Decision Tree, Speaker recognition.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Crime Scene Investigation And Best Practicals

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ABSTRACT

Crime Scene Investigation (CSI) is a crucial aspect of criminal investigations, serving as the foundation for evidence collection and interpretation. This comprehensive review paper examines the evolution, advancements, and best practices in CSI methodologies and techniques. This paper explores how the technological advancements have revolutionized evidence collection, preservation, and analysis, ultimately enhancing investigative outcomes. The discussion emphasizes the importance of standardized practices and protocols in CSI to ensure consistent, reliable, and unbiased results. Training and education play a vital role in enhancing the skills and knowledge of investigators, fostering the implementation of best practices in the field. Additionally, interdisciplinary collaboration among law enforcement

agencies, forensic experts, and other stakeholders is crucial in optimizing the investigative process and ensuring a multidimensional approach to complex crime scenes. Moreover, the paper highlights the significance of evidence preservation and chain of custody, emphasizing the critical role they play in maintaining the integrity and admissibility of evidence in court. By synthesizing current trends and practices, this review offers valuable insights into the advancements in CSI and provides a roadmap for the continued improvement of investigative processes. Ultimately, this review aims to contribute to the ongoing enhancement of CSI methodologies, advancing the field and facilitating the pursuit of justice in a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

keywords: Crime scene Investigation, Collection, Evidence, Chain of Custody, Justice, Preservation, Forensic Experts.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Estimation Of Stature From Fingers Length Among The Population Of Karnataka State

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ABSTRACT

Identification of a corpse is the primary step in any crime scene investigation. DNA, fingerprints, any birthmarks or certain medical conditions aid in this process of identification. But not all dead bodies discovered in a crime scene have an intact face/ skull or fingers or sometimes they are skeletonized making it difficult / impossible to extract DNA out of them. During these scenarios, crime investigators resort to anthropometric parameters, wherein the length of certain bones of the human remains can help identify a person's stature and thereby identify the person or at least help in narrowing down the list. The present study focuses on the usage of length of both left and right fingers [thumb, index, middle, ring and little fingers] for a person's stature estimation in a population [Karnataka state] and also to find a particular finger which is more suitable for stature estimation among both males and females. 200 samples from individuals belonging to 18-30years of age was collected using vernier caliper and anthropometric rod along with their informed consents. These samples were subjected to statistical analysis using a software- IBM SPSS Software Version 26. The length of each of the 10 fingers of a subject was compared with their stature in order to find a correlation which can aid in formulating a formula which can in turn aid in stature estimation from fingers.

Keywords: Stature estimation, fingers, Karnataka, vernier caliper, anthropometric rod, IBM SPSS software.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Psychological Autopsy of Suicide

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ABSTRACT

Suicide is a grave public health issue, demanding a fine understanding and innovative strategies for prevention of all other methods, psychological autopsy is the detailed study of the web of emotions, thoughts, and surroundings leading to someone's death. This in-depth study enables in explaining the aspects of psychological autopsy, its importance, how it's done and means of mental health research and help. A psychological autopsy is a research to understand the factors that may have contributed to a person committing suicide. It involves a systematic procedure of questioning the family members, relatives, and friends of the deceased and studying the available healthcare and psychiatric records, forensic examinations, and other documents. This helps in gaining awareness of the complex nature of suicide and its triggers. One of the central theories in suicide psychology is the Interpersonal-Psychological Theory of Suicidal Behavior (IPT). This theory posits that the convergence of three main factors - perceived burdensomeness, thwarted belongingness, and the acquired capability for self-harm - is necessary for suicidal behavior to occur. Perceived burdensomeness refers to the belief that one is a burden to others, while thwarted belongingness pertains to feelings of social disconnection. The acquired capability for self-harm suggests that individuals must develop a tolerance to physical pain and fear of death to enact lethal self-harm. In conclusion, psychological autopsy is an invaluable tool that has the ability to unravel the enigmatic threads of human despair, caused by a large number of factors, and provides society the knowledge required to combat this persistent public health crises. This will help to forge a future where suicide rates are reduced and mental healthcare services are enhanced leading to a more compassionate and proper understanding of human psyche.

Keywords: Psychological autopsy, mental health, suicide, forensic examination, suicidal behavior, death, self-harm.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Disguised Handwriting: Unaccustomed Hand

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ABSTRACT

A writer generally writes using their accustomed hand (i.e., dominant hand which is usually right hand), however they may disguise their handwriting using the unaccustomed hand (i.e., non-dominant hand which is left hand) to hide their identity. Writing with the unaccustomed hand is a frequent method of disguise. In this type of disguise, the writer does not have a strong hold on the writing instrument which may cause

sudden loss of the instrument which in turn causes a change in its pictorial appearance and because of this change the writer believes that they have successfully disguised their handwriting. Writing with unaccustomed hand also causes changes in direction of writing, crossbars to letters, pen trailing, missing terminal strokes, and other characteristics. However, after a detailed study on Canadian population and University students who knew to read and write English well, it was found that even after the pictorial differences there are certain unconscious features that are rarely disguised which could either form the basis to link the writing with a particular person or indicate its probability for further investigation. The analysis and investigation of these unconscious features left by the writer can be carried out by a trained forensic document examiner and then they could give justifiable facts and circumstance about a case.

Keywords: Unaccustomed, Accustomed, Disguise, Handwriting

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Decomposition Dynamics of Human Bodies in Aquatic Environments: A Case Study in the Mediterranean Sea

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the intricate processes of human body decomposition in aquatic environments is paramount for forensic science. This abstract explores the decomposition dynamics in the Mediterranean Sea, presenting findings from a case study involving the discovery and recovery of a submerged body at a depth of 30 meters. The investigation focuses on environmental factors, decomposition stages, forensic analyses, and collaborative efforts to unravel the mysteries concealed beneath the waves. The study considered unique environmental factors of the Mediterranean Sea, including temperature variations, oxygen levels, and the presence of endemic marine species. Decomposition stages were systematically documented, emphasizing the progression through Fresh, Bloat, Active Decay, Advanced Decay, Skeletonization, and Final Dispersal. Forensic experts applied specialized aquatic decomposition scores tailored to the Mediterranean Sea's conditions. The systematic evaluation of soft tissue and bone changes facilitated the estimation of the postmortem Submersion Interval (PMSI). Despite advanced decomposition, DNA analysis played a crucial role in identifying the victim, supported by collaboration with marine biologists to understand local marine fauna behavior and scavenger interactions.

Keywords: Decomposition dynamics, aquatic environments, Mediterranean Sea, forensic science, postmortem Submersion Interval, interdisciplinary collaboration, DNA analysis, marine fauna behavior.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Comparison of Organic Powder with Current Trends in Revival of Destroyed Fingerprints on Porous Surface

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ABSTRACT

In the discipline of forensics, fingerprint research is crucial. A fingerprint serves as a person's identity due to its distinction and individuality. Numerous techniques have been developed by experts to find latent fingerprints at crime scenes. However, fingerprints are not always recoverable since they may be unintentionally or on purpose erased by a variety of causes, including the culprit. Organic powder made using biochar technique was used for development of fingerprints on white paper after treatment with tap water, soapy water and sanitizer. The results obtained were then compared to current powders which have been employed in the same process. Organic powder was found to be effective on soapy water and sanitizer in comparison to black powder. The efficacy flow of powder is Neem Nano- Biochar > Organic Powder > Black Powder. Therefore, latent prints can be created from these surfaces if any paper is retrieved in this manner from a crime scene. Future capabilities may include testing the same compounds that caused negative effects on the print on surfaces with varied textures, porous and non-porous materials, and the impact of the environment on these.

Keywords: Fingerprint, Recovery, Organic Powder, Efficacy.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Advancing Justice and Discovery: A Comprehensive Examination of DNA

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ABSTRACT

DNA databases represent a pivotal intersection of science, technology, and law that has revolutionized various fields, from criminal justice to medical research. A DNA database, also known as a DNA databank or genetic database, is a collection of genetic information from individuals stored for various purposes, primarily related to law enforcement, scientific research, and medical applications. The Purpose of Abstract is Forensic investigation, Parentage Testing and Medical Research. Criminal DNA Database, Voluntary DNA Database, Population Genetics Database The advent of DNA databases has ushered in a new era of investigative precision and scientific discovery. These databases, repositories of genetic profiles derived from individuals' DNA, have grown exponentially in both size and significance. This

abstract explores the multifaceted landscape of DNA databases, addressing their key attributes and societal implications. They facilitate the discovery of genetic markers associated with various diseases, enabling advancements in personalized medicine, drug development, and our understanding of genetic factors influencing health. Ethical and Legal Considerations As the power and scope of DNA databases grow, so do the ethical and legal dilemmas. This abstract explores critical concerns, such as privacy, consent, and the potential misuse of genetic information. It also highlights the legal regulations and safeguards in place to govern their use. Future Prospects The future of DNA databases promises further innovations, with emerging technologies like Next-Generation Sequencing and advancements in population genetics. These developments will expand the databases' potential in diverse fields, including ancestry tracing, conservation biology, and disaster victim identification. Conclusion DNA databases stand as powerful tools with far-reaching implications. Their impact spans from solving crimes and advancing medicine to raising profound ethical questions. This abstract invites a comprehensive exploration of DNA databases, recognizing their invaluable contributions to science and society.

Keywords : DNA database , Law enforcement , Technology, Forensic investigation, Parentage testing , DNA profiling .

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Datura Stramonium as a Potential Sedative Agent

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ABSTRACT

Forensic toxicology is the analysis of biological samples for the presence of toxins, including drugs. India has a great wealth of naturally occurring plant drugs which have a great potential pharmacological activity. Datura is one of the widely well-known folklore medicinal herbs. It is a plant with both poisonous and medicinal properties and has been proven to have great properties in the medical world. Datura stramonium commonly called as Jimson weed, has contributed various pharmacological in the scientific field of Indian history of medicine like analgesic and anti-asthmatic activities. The current paper presents an exclusive review work on the ethnomedical, phytochemical and pharmacological properties of this plant.

Keywords: Datura stramonium, Jimsonweed, Ethnomedical, traditional uses, Pharmacology

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Xylazine Intoxication in Humans and its Importance as an Emerging Adulterant in Abused drugs

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ABSTRACT

Xylazine is sold as a veterinary medicine and used as a sedative, analgesic, and muscle relaxant; it is not a prohibited substance. It may result in bradycardia, hypotension, depression of the central nervous system, respiratory depression, and even death in people. 43 reports of xylazine intoxication in humans have been published, of which 21 (49%) had non-fatal outcomes and 22 (51%) had fatal outcomes. The majority of non-fatal instances necessitated medical attention. In recent years, xylazine has become a common adulterant in recreational narcotics including heroin and speedball (a combination of cocaine and heroin). 43 cases that were recorded involved using xylazine as an adulterant in drugs of abuse. Chronic use has been linked to physical degeneration and skin ulceration, according to reports. The pharmacologic effects of xylazine and heroin on humans have been compared in the literature. These related pharmaceutical outcomes could have synergistic harmful outcomes in people. Therefore, the use of xylazine as an adulterant may result in an increase in drug user fatalities. Humans have found xylazine to be dangerous on its own and significantly more so when mixed with other addictive substances.

Keywords: Xylazine, Adulterant, Drugs

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

A Cause Study on the Impact of Multiple Personality Disorder On Criminal Behaviour

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ABSTRACT

Multiple personality disorder is a mental disorder characterized by maintenance of at least two distinct and relatively enduring personality states. This review plays a significant role in criminal psychology. It is different to study the behaviour of person having multiple personality disorder which cause trouble recalling his or her own personal information. This review paper explore the relationship between the disorder and it's potential impact on criminal actions . The aim of this study is to provide insight into the complexities of the multiple periods disorder and how it may intersect with criminal behaviour. This review on multiple personality disorder in criminal behaviour conclusion emphasizes the cases were individual with disorder, is important to handle with caution by doing proper investigation and researches.

keywords: Multiple personality disorder, criminal psychology, researches, criminal behaviour, personality.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Forensic Biology and DNA Analysis of Bodily Fluids

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ABSTRACT

Forensic biology involves the application of biological principles and techniques to analyze evidence collected from crime scenes. This can include the examination of bodily fluids. The goal of forensic biologists is to identify and analyze these samples to extract valuable information that can aid in solving crimes. DNA analysis is a fundamental component of forensic biology. DNA, or deoxyribonucleic acid, is a molecule that carries genetic information unique to each individual. Through DNA analysis, forensic scientists can compare DNA profiles obtained from crime scene evidence with those of potential suspects or victims. This comparison allows for the identification or exclusion of individuals based on their genetic profiles. The process of DNA analysis involves several steps. First, DNA extracted from the collected samples, which can be challenging depending on the quality and quantity of the biological material. Once extracted, the DNA is amplified through a process called polymerase chain reaction (PCR), which produces millions of copies of specific DNA regions for analysis. Amplified DNA subjected to various techniques, such as restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), short tandem repeat (STR) analysis, or single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) analysis, generate a DNA profile. Forensic biologists compare DNA profiles by examining specific regions of the DNA known as genetic markers. These markers are highly variable among individuals, making them useful for identification purposes. The significance of forensic biology and DNA analysis in criminal investigations cannot be overstated. DNA evidence has proven to be a powerful tool in identifying perpetrators, exonerating the innocent, and solved cases.

keywords: Deoxyribonucleic acid, Genetic markers, polymorphism, quantification, polymerase chain reaction

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Intersection of Drowning and Diatoms: A Review of Postmortem and Antemortem Perspectives

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ABSTRACT

Drowning is the process of experiencing respiratory impairment from submersion. Drowning cases are presenting a significant challenge in forensic investigations and clinical medicine. It is difficult to differentiate between whether the death caused was postmortem or antemortem in nature. The examination of diatoms in postmortem and antemortem contexts has been a valuable tool in drowning-related cases. This

review explores the intersection of drowning and diatoms, offering insights into the utilization of diatom analysis to distinguish between antemortem and postmortem submersion, and to aid in the determination of the cause and manner of death. It provides an overview of the collection and analysis methods for diatoms for further forensic investigation, highlighting the proper chain-of-custody and the potential sources of contamination. Moreover, it also explores the variations in the species of diatom in various water bodies which can also be implicated in establishing geographic associations in forensic investigations. This study also includes different analysis techniques used to differentiate between the postmortem and antemortem drowning deaths. It also highlights the challenges and limitations of this approach, including the interpretation of results in the absence of standardized protocols and the potential for false positives or negatives results while postmortem examination of viscera and other samples.

Keywords: Drowning, Diatoms, Forensic investigation, Viscera, long bones.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Recent Developments in Firearm and Bullet Examination

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ABSTRACT

This work summarizes recent developments in the methods used for chemical analysis in investigations of firearm-related events over the past ten years, from 2016 to 2021. The paper covers various aspects of forensic firearm examination, including the examination of gunshot and gunpowder residues on suspects and their clothing, detection of firearm imprints on suspects; and hands, identification of bullet entry holes, estimation of shooting distances, and the linking of weapons and ammunition to gunshot entries. One notable shift in recent years is the move towards more objective methods in firearm examination. Traditionally, this field has relied on examiners; and judgments, but there is a growing demand for greater objectivity. To address this, new approaches involve acquiring surface topographies in 2D or 3D and using computer-based comparison algorithms to compare features in cartridge cases and bullets. The resulting comparison scores can provide quantitative measures of evidence strength, such as likelihood ratios, categorical conclusions, or estimated error rates when applying the method. Furthermore, the study highlights research areas that include firearm examination, technical examination, shooting incident reconstruction, and wound ballistics. Notably, efforts have been focused on understanding the validity and reliability of firearm examiners; source judgments and how they can be influenced by bias. Additionally, considerable work has been dedicated to developing computer-based methods for comparing striation and impression patterns, aligning with the recommendations of authoritative reports such as the President Council of Advisors on Science and Technology (PCAST) and the National Academy of Sciences (NAS) on strengthening forensic science in criminal courts. In summary, this work

provides a comprehensive overview of the advancements in scientific methods and discussions related to firearm examination and related fields in the past decade, with an emphasis on objectivity and reliability in forensic investigations.

Keywords: investigation, firearms, gunpowder, bullets, examination.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic DNA Phenotyping: A Future Perspective of Crime Investigations

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ABSTRACT

Predicting the appearance traits or extremely visible characteristics (EVC) of unknown biological samples found at crime scenes is known as Forensic DNA Typing. Forensic DNA Typing plays a significant role in crime investigations through the biological evidence of that unknown person. Conventionally, Forensic DNA typing was used, which was based on human identification using short tandem repeats (STRs), where unknown STR profile was matched with known/reference STR profiles. But this technique fails in the cases where references STRs were not known. Therefore, the FDP technique was introduced for providing important leads in the investigations. EVCs are human phenotyping traits that can be predicted using a specific set of DNA markers. DNA markers provide accurate information about the possible suspect. EVCs are considered the most promising components to distinguish between individuals. Forensic DNA typing is the probability-based technique as FDP is related to the common traits that are shared by different potential groups. Therefore, it only increases the chances of suspect confirmation according to the probable outcome after the test. Several issues are faced by FDP like genotyping issues, ethical issues, legal issues, and morphological issues. This paper focuses on the heritability of the EVCs and their associated markers, the accuracy rate of FDP, and issues majorly faced by this technique.

Keywords: DNA Phenotyping, EVCs, probability, STR markers, traits

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Imaging Wound Ballistics - With An Advantage of AI Technology : A Review

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ABSTRACT

To study the standard imaging technique used for the documentation of

gun-shot related injuries i.e., a two-dimensional photographic image created by visible light, which are defines as electromagnetic radiation within the portion of the electromagnetic spectrum that can perceived by photons, snake photons etc. visible light lies between UV and IR. The latter is commonly used for the detection and visualization of gun-shot residues, where the temporary region in a bullet part is what we are more concerned about in the research. The main aim was to bridge interdisciplinary cooperation between forensic ballistics and deep-learning engineers, emphasizing activating clinical forensic run-through instrumentation with advanced artificial intelligence techniques with interest in its implementation in their efforts to advance the wound imaging further. This paper includes a workflow of analysis of imaging of gun-shot wounds concerning the formed temporary region and its effects through the track of ballistic photons and on a special light using the AI technology as one of the parts of instrumentation in order to achieve the expected results. In conclusion, the application of AI with wound imaging, leading to an unprecedented improvement of forensic analysis and in the project test.

Keywords: Wound imaging, Ultra violet radiation, Infrared radiation, Gun-shot residues, Ballistic photons, Artificial intelligence.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Familial DNA Searching : An Emerging Forensic Tool

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ABSTRACT

In the past few years, there have been such significant developments in the field of forensic science that current investigative methods are hardly comparable to those from not so long ago. Nowadays, DNA is one of the most recent advancements in forensic DNA technology and one of the instruments that a forensic scientist might use. Familial DNA searching is the technique of deliberately searching a DNA database for a match at only a small subset of the typed loci in an effort to find unidentified relatives in an effort to provide fresh leads for investigation. A familial search will permit matching subsets of alleles for any given marker as the basis for comparison, unlike a search for a direct match. The creation of CODIS (COMBINED DNA INDEX SYSTEM), an FBI-funded computer database that houses provided by municipal, state, and federal crime laboratories in the USA. The number of shared genetic characteristics (i.e., alleles) and the rareness of those shared alleles in human populations form the basis of this search. Offenders, arrestees, convicted offenders, and/or other people from whom samples have been lawfully obtained may be classified in various ways in database profiles. According, any initial identification of possible kinship between an individual and a target perpetrator's DNA profile is based sole upon the presence of shared genetic markers that do not code for any known biological trait other than gender. The FORENSIC SCIENCE Service. Ltd (FSS) designed two types algorithm to, identify any DNA profile within the NDNAD (i.e. DNA Database) that could be

related to the target DNA profile as a parent or child. Secondly, to identify those individuals more likely to be related as siblings to the true perpetrator by ranking the DNA profiles held in the NDNAD by the no. of alleles shared with the target DNA profile. Familial DNA search protocol for their DNA databases should first determine whether such use of the database is addressed by existing statutory, regulatory, judicial or other controlling authority. For instance, familial DNA searching is in line with the goals stated in the federal DNA identification act.

Keywords: DNA searching, Criminal DNA identification, Inherited alleles, Genetic Markers, legal proceedings.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

To Compare Consequences of Environmental Factors Related to DNA Yield From Forensic Blood Sample

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ABSTRACT

The study of the effect of environmental factors on DNA yield is important in understanding the factors that affect the DNA extracted from various biological samples. The purpose of this study was to investigate the impact of several environmental factors, including temperature, soil, water, PH and exposure to UV Radiation, on the quantity and quality of DNA obtained from forensic blood samples. These factors can affect the stability of DNA and the efficiency of DNA extraction. This can result in variability in DNA yield, which can impact downstream applications such as PCR, sequencing, etc. According to the study, environmental factors like temperature significantly affect the amount of DNA that can be extracted from forensic blood samples. It was discovered that lower temperatures increased DNA yield whereas higher temperatures decreased it. The research also discovered that the DNA extracted from forensic blood samples is significantly impacted by sunshine exposure. In this research, we look at the numerous environmental variables that might affect DNA yield and quality as well as DNA extraction techniques that can be used to maximize DNA production under various environmental circumstances. The accuracy of DNA-based analysis in numerous scientific disciplines can be increased by better understanding how environmental conditions affect DNA yield. These results demonstrate the significance of handling and storing forensic blood samples properly to obtain the highest yield and DNA purity for forensic analysis. This knowledge will be helpful to forensic scientists as they work to collect accurate and trustworthy DNA evidence for criminal investigations.

Keywords: environmental factors, DNA yield, DNA extraction, forensic investigation, blood sample.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

DNA Markers Backbone of DNA Profiling

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ABSTRACT

Earlier it was difficult to solve such cases identification and linking of potential suspect or, mixed DNA identification, integrated paternity cases, body fluid analysis, identification of tissue remains, and detection of species origin, but with the emergence of this technology. At present time, forensic investigation is aided by DNA profiling. DNA profiling or DNA typing is basically a technique of a series of tests and methodology that is used to inspect or identify the genetic information in an individual's cell. In Forensics DNA profiling is simply a correlation of the gene information of an individual and the biological evidence collected from the scene of a crime Like blood in all states, hair, semen in case of rape or sexual assault, saliva, and bones, etc or any profile stored in the database. However, 99.9% sequence of DNA is the same only 0.1% sequence varies from person to person but to make a profile of that 0.1% is really a cumbersome process, and to make that process easier we use that is why we use DNA polymorphism. In DNA profiling, DNA markers are used to identify individuals with the help of unique DNA patterns present in them. DNA markers are used as the identification of linked genes on chromosome, further chromosome abnormalities and gene mutation can be identified in the organism's genome and DNA sequence, gene associated with genetic disorders are also identified, DNA markers also plays a crucial role in wildlife forensic to identify the species and their families and help to find newly found organisms. At least 20 markers are required to make any report admissible in court of law. The most used markers are short tandem repeats (STRs), species specific primers, SNPs (single nucleotide polymorphism) which works based on PCR and NGS methods in the extreme investigations. Rather than forensic DNA profiling DNA markers are used for disease identification, biotechnology, pharmaceutical and agriculture.

Keywords : DNA profiling, DNA marker, STR, convenience.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Contactless Fingerprint Biometrics in the Modern Age

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ABSTRACT

Contactless fingerprint biometrics has witnessed remarkable progress in recent years, revolutionizing the field of biometric identification and authentication. It is a rapidly evolving technology with many potential forensic science applications. Compared to conventional contact-based fingerprint biometrics, it has a variety of perks, such as better convenience and usability, improved cleanliness and sanitation, decreased danger of cross-contamination, and increased security and tamper resistance. The introduction of 3D contactless fingerprint

scanners, the implementation of AI-powered contactless identification of fingerprints, and the incorporation of contactless scanners for fingerprints into wearable technology are some of the most recent advances in contactless fingerprint biometrics. The most recent trends and advancements in contactless fingerprint biometrics are thoroughly examined in this article. Additionally, we explore over potential applications for secure authentication, mobile devices, and access administration, emphasizing the expanding significance of contactless fingerprint technology across a range of sectors. The evaluation discusses issues pertaining to security and privacy as well as future research directions.

Keywords: Contactless fingerprint, Biometric Trends, Secure Authentication, 3D Fingerprint Readers.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Nanotechnology: An Applied and Robust Approach for Forensic Investigation

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ABSTRACT

Nanotechnology, the manipulation of matter at the atomic and molecular level, and the formation of new materials with unusually diverse and unique properties is rapid an expanding field of research with enormous potential in several areas, from health production and physical science. For forensics, this promising revolutionizes the applicability of microfluidic systems in the post-polymerase chain reaction (PCR) quantification, DNA extraction medium, fingerprint imaging using nano-powder. In general, forensic nano-technology is changing dimensions tools for small chip-based platforms and shortening analysis methods conducted Nanoparticles, with their unique properties, have revolutionized forensic analysis. They enable enhanced detection and characterization of trace evidence, such as Gunshot Residue (GSR), fingerprints, and biological materials. Nanoscale imaging techniques, including Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM), provide unprecedented resolution for visualizing evidence. Nano-sensors designed for specific chemical markers enable rapid and sensitive detection of illicit drugs, explosives, and hazardous substances. Miniaturized analytical devices, incorporating nanoscale components, empower on-site testing and real-time monitoring of crime scenes. Forensic document examination benefits from nanotechnology through the precise identification of ink composition and document alterations. Nanoscale materials, such as nanofibers and nanocomposites, enhance the collection and preservation of trace evidence from crime scenes. Moreover, nanotechnology aids in deciphering the age of ink entries, potentially critical in dating historical documents or verifying the authenticity of questioned writings. As nanotechnology continues to evolve, its interdisciplinary nature fosters collaboration among chemists, physicists, materials scientists, and forensic experts. Together, they push the boundaries of forensic science, addressing challenges in evidence analysis, crime prevention,

and justice.

keywords: Nanotechnology in Forensics, GSR analysis, Ink and Writing analysis, Nanochips, CrimeScene ,investigations.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Estimation of Stature From Foot and Hand Measurements in a Rare Tribe of Kerala State

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ABSTRACT

Formulation of biological profile is one of the modern roles of forensic anthropologist and forensic podiatrist. The study can be very useful in formulation of biological profile of individuals with their palm length and finger length measurements. This can help in forensic investigation and also to narrow down the suspects. Besides, stature and sex determination are important parameters in identification mutilated dead bodies. This study can be helpful in the areas of mass disasters, assault, natural calamities. The method is useful because in such cases the people are dismembered and become unrecognizable. The main aim of study is to find the relationship between stature and anthropometric parameters which are the measurements taken from palm and foot. Samples in the research were collected from 100 participants (50 males and 50 females) of south Indian origin, Kannavam Colony, from Kerala, Kannur district who range in 20 to 30 years. Foot length, foot breadth, palm length and length of fingers were obtained from both feet and both palms using anthropometric standards only. Foot, finger length measurements and breadth measurements were recorded and analyzed from the collected measurements. Data was analyzed using SPSS Statistic software 16.0 software. Results were obtained from Mann-Whitney test and Karl Pearson's correlation. The study concluded with a definite correlation between stature and foot length and regression equations has been established.

Keywords: Anthropology, stature, anthropometric standards, correlation, SPSS software.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Hanging: Determination of Manner of Death at Crime Scene

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ABSTRACT

Hanging is an unnatural death induced by suspension of a person from an anchor point by a ligature tied around the neck and jumping from a

height. Hanging can be done in a closed area such as a house, drawing room, bedroom, bathroom, etc., or in an open area such as a dense forest, distant location, etc. The forensic investigation primarily related to reconstruction of crime scene and differentiation of ante mortem and post mortem hanging. Hanging is usually suicidal in nature but there may be a possibility that after killing the victim, the body is suspended from a fan, tree etc. In the case of suspected murder, the cause of death is other than ante mortem hanging and may have struggle marks and other injuries. It is the utmost duty of the investigating officer and the forensic expert to look out all the probabilities. The investigation of the hanging case should be scientifically related and the approaches used for investigating the hanging cases are different for open and close places. Some important points are noted during the investigation in case of both open and close places such as the height from ground to anchor point, height of victim, length between anchor point and knot on the neck, height of item used for hanging, type of material used during hanging, distance between heel and floor, etc. Photography of the crime scene should be done including the ligature marks on the body. The photograph of suicide note should be taken if found. The examination of hanging material and the point of suspension should be done. The ligature marks on the neck and injuries on the body should be well examined. Commonly cases of hanging are suicidal and cases of homicidal and accidental hanging are rare.

Keywords- Hanging, Investigation, Ligature Mark, Anchor Point, Suicidal hanging, Homicidal hanging, accidental hanging

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Unearthing the Truth: Exploring the Intersection of Archaeology and Forensic Science in Crime Investigations

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ABSTRACT

Forensic archaeology, is a fascinating combination of archaeology and forensic science, and is crucial in uncovering the mysteries hidden beneath the surface. This poster dives into the interesting realm of forensic archaeology, where ancient tactics collide with current investigation approaches. Forensic archaeologists excavate crime scenes with great care, discovering buried evidence, human bones, and artifacts. They help to recreate events, identify victims, and gather critical evidence for criminal investigations by carefully documenting and evaluating their findings. Forensic archaeology uses ground penetrating radar, aerial surveys, and advanced imaging technology to map and examine crime scenes, drawing inspiration from past traditions. This multidisciplinary method enables investigators to perceive and comprehend the spatial context of the evidence, so assisting in the reconstruction of events and the identification of probable suspects. Furthermore, the abstract delves into the significance of forensic archaeology outside of its immediate relevance to criminal investigations. It highlights its importance in historical and

archaeological research, catastrophe victim identification, human rights investigations, and mass grave excavations, underlining the fields broader societal ramifications. In conclusion, forensic archaeology is critical to solving historical puzzles and bringing justice to the present. By utilizing a careful and interdisciplinary approach, forensic archaeologists assist to the settlement of criminal cases, the protection of human rights, and the development of historical knowledge, eventually fostering a more just and informed society.

Keywords: Forensic Archaeology, Human bone, Artifacts, Imaging technology, Areal survey, Human rights, Mass grave.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic Wildlife: The Tide of Tiger Poaching in India

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ABSTRACT

Poaching and illegal trafficking pose significant threats to endangered felids, particularly tigers. Despite India having stringent laws and strict enforcement, poaching remains rampant, with skin, claws, bones, and teeth being in high demand. The study analyzed tiger seizure cases from 2001-2021, identifying the most preferred body parts and trade routes for export. The intensity of seizures was high in Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu, and Assam, with the Western Ghats region being a previously unnoticed hotspot. The study emphasizes the need for DNA body A methods and precise enforcement of rules to combat poaching and trafficking effectively. We assert that current approaches are incapable of resolving the issue and that a more precise and effective forensic procedure capable of resolving the issue at the minute local level is critical for precisely tracing trade channels.

Keywords- Poaching, Illegal trafficking, Endangered felids, Stringent laws, DNA body methods.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Isolation and Extraction of DNA from Dandruff

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ABSTRACT

Forensic analysis plays important role in criminal investigation. In forensic generally isolated DNA from saliva, blood, urine etc. But dandruff is more easily accessible and less invasive to obtain than blood or saliva. Dandruff is less susceptible to degradation making it more stable source of DNA. Dandruff is a common scalp condition in which small pieces of dry skin flake off of the scalp Dandruff is generally presented in criminal cases, and it contains some nucleated cells which

make it possible to extract DNA for forensic uses Dandruff is produced as a pathological desquamation of the skin and histologically consists of orthokeratotic clumps with minute parakeratotic foci. It is presumed that some nucleated cells could be found in dandruff therefore in some cases sufficient dandruff could be obtained, DNA for the Polymerase chain reaction might be obtained for DNA analysis. While Extracting DNA from Dandruff using chelex-100. the amount of DNA quantized range from 72.5 ng this data support that dandruff can be reliable source of biological material in some case work scenarios. The overall results of this study described a method for isolating and Extracting DNA from dandruff , which has the potential to revolutionize in the field of forensic science.

Keywords:- forensic analysis, dandruff, isolation and extraction.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

The Prevalence of Dental Anomalies of Imphal West Region of Manipur

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ABSTRACT

Dental professionals commonly notice abnormalities in the dentitions development. The aim of this cross-sectional study is to find out the prevalence of dental anomalies that are commonly found in the Imphal west region of Manipur and that could be used for criminal profiling in which the dental evidence is compared and analysed by forensic odontologists. An retrospective study of 3000 radiographs and OPG of the patients studied with proper treatment planning and advice were given to the patient and treatment was done with the patient's consent. Sterilised surgical instruments were used. The patients ages ranged between 12 and 40 years, both male and female and about 45% of the patients commonly have horizontal 3rd molar impaction other include congenitally missing teeth, supernumerary teeth, microdontia, dilaceration macrodontia. Among others patients who were 445 (45%) had at least one dental abnormality. The horizontal 3rd molar impaction and congenitally missing teeth are mostly seen in the patients supernumerary teeth 2.6%, Microdontia 0.56% Dilaceration 0.86% Macrodonia 0.56% other anomalies were found at lower prevalence horizontal 3rd molar impaction were the most common aberration in the Imphal west region of Manipur followed by supernumerary teeth Macrodonia, dilaceration and macrodonia were the least common anomalies. Even though these anomalies may not be common in general, early detection is crucial for patient care and treatment planning.

Keywords : Dental anomalies, Forensic odontology.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Organophosphate Insecticide Poisoning

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ABSTRACT

To serve as a small reminder of the risk to public health associated with organophosphate insecticides. Organophosphate (OP) compound are a group of pesticides. Pesticides are classified according to pet organisms to which they are designed as insecticides, weedicides, rodenticides, fungicides etc. It has been approximately one in seven of all global suicides is due to pesticides poisoning. Most useful classification based on chemical composition as organochlorine, organo-phosphorous, carbamates and pyrethrin as insecticides because they used in generally agriculture to kill the insects. Pesticides poisoning occurs in three ways occupational accident, domestic accident and suicide due to intentional ingestion. Op poisoning occurs due to wide availability of highly toxic pesticides. According to the sources in 2016 found that OP poisoning is widespread in southern and central India.

Keywords:- Carbamates, Insecticidal poisoning, Organo-phosphorus

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Borderline Personality Disorder And It's Correlation To Violence And Suicidal Aspects In Forensic Psychology

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ABSTRACT

Borderline personality disorder is a mental disorder associated with high rates of severe functionality disorder, suicide rates, high rates of concurrent mental disorders. Subjects with this disorder also exhibit comorbid anti-social personality disorder. Due to substantial treatment use, subjects with borderline personality disorder are more violent and require more attention. This study examined the relationship between features of borderline personality disorder with respect to violence, self-harm and suicidal tendencies. The authors theorized the vague characteristic of borderline personality disorder with probable impetuous behaviour with co-relation to childhood trauma that would be linked with violence and suicidal behaviour. Statistics show that 73% of the subjects engage in violence, evidences also show higher risks of subjects being involved in domestic violence. The cause of this disorder though not prominent, yet adverse life events, such as physical and sexual abuse, childhood trauma, genetic factors contribute to the development of this disorder. Treatment involved in this disorder though do not directly affect it but reduce depression, anxiety and impulsive aggression. Clinical signs of this disorder include, dysregulation of emotions, impulsive nature, aggression, repeated self-injury and chronic suicidal tendencies. The studies show

violence as a serious and prevalent issue among subjects with BPD. More extensive study and research is required for the grasp and supervision of this clinical condition responsible for many psychological behaviours.

Keywords: Border Personality Disorder, self-harm, suicidal tendencies.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Presence of Dental Anomalies in Down Syndrome Patients

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ABSTRACT

A hereditary disorder in which the affected person carries a second copy of the chromosome 21, is also known as trisomy 21. The cranial, facial, and oral characteristics of down syndrome include papillary hypertrophy, brachycephaly, a condition in which the skull is abnormally large, a short maxilla, an ogival sensation of taste, and a tongue with crevices. Dental abnormalities are any variations from the typical structure or development of teeth. These abnormalities may arise alone or as a component of a more severe genetic abnormality, and they can affect the number, size, form, position, and structure of teeth. The purpose of the study was to evaluate different types of dental anomalies amongst the patients of Down's Syndrome in Brazilian and Mongolian population, with reference to the study carried out by different scientists at different aspects of time, involving number of subjects. The presence of the different anomalies was measured and recoded using panoramic radiographs and casts obtained during the examination in both primary and permanent dentition. In conclusion Down Syndrome patients showcased a high incidence of dental anomalies and in some cases more than one anomalies.

Keywords: Dental Anomalies, Down Syndrome, Panoramic Radiographs

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Sputum DNA Analysis And Forensic Science - A Theoretical Approach

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ABSTRACT

Sputum may refer to phlegm or mucus. Sputum is matter expectorated from the respiratory system (& especially lungs). It is composed of mucus but may contain pus, blood, fibrin or microorganisms (such as bacteria in diseased states) in medicine, sputum samples are usually used for microbiological investigation of

respiratory infections and cytological investigation of respiratory system. Processing sputum is difficult as it is very thick. There are many different ways to process sputum depending on what aspects of the sputum is to be studied. The person suffering with the diseases like mycobacterium tuberculosis, cystic fibrosis sputum sample are analysed in this. Also sought to find the based method to take sputum from a cystic fibrosis patient and extract DNA so that we could detect both bacteria and bacteriophage DNA. To optimize the DNA extraction from sputum for both the detection and quantification of it phage and P. aeruginosa, here different methods of sputum dissociation are used that is Chemical dissociation and mechanical dissociation. And also testing both dithiothreitol (DTT) and Enzymatic treatment of sputum samples and identifying the most suitable DNA extraction technique for the microbiota analysis for sputum. Sputum is evidence in forensic investigations, and its relevance and usefulness depend on the specific circumstances of the case. The extraction of DNA from sputum is a valuable technique in forensic science that plays a significant role in solving crimes, identifying suspects, and connecting individuals to criminal activities.

Keywords: Sputum, DNA, Forensic Investigation, Mucus, Cystic Fibrosis, Mycobacterium tuberculosis.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Potato Poisoning

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ABSTRACT

An assortment of cultivated and ornamental plant species in the Solanaceae family naturally produce a class of nitrogen-containing substances known as glycoalkaloids. Although glycoalkaloids prevent the growth of cancer cells in the body, they are extremely hazardous when taken in large doses. In cases of acute toxicity, glycoalkaloids can cause death in humans or animals by disrupting cell membranes, attaching to membrane sterols, and inhibiting acetylcholinesterase. These effects include intestinal pain, vomiting, fever, diarrhea, and neurological disorders. The glycoalkaloid found in potatoes is reviewed here. Potatoes are a popular, important, and reasonably priced vegetable. People consume potatoes in large quantity because they are widely available and are grown in almost every season. Because glycoalkaloids are concentrated in the potato peel, extended exposure to light will encourage the synthesis of glycoalkaloids near the potato tubers surface. After 24 hours of intake, glycoalkaloid is still present in the body and accumulates in several organs, including the liver. Therefore, regularly consuming potatoes or potato derivatives is extremely hazardous to human health.

Keywords: Glycoalkaloids, toxicity, human health

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Evaluating the Performance and Emissions of Gasoline and Diesel Fuel

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ABSTRACT

Gasoline and diesel fuel are two of the most important petroleum products, used in gasoline and diesel engines, respectively. The octane rating of gasoline is a measure of its resistance to knocking, while the cetane rating of diesel fuel is a measure of its ignition delay. This review used to determine the octane rating of gasoline and the cetane rating of diesel fuel. The study will also discuss the factors that affect the octane rating and cetane rating of these fuels, and the implications of these ratings for engine performance and emissions. The octane rating of gasoline is determined using two different methods: the Research Octane Number (RON) and the Motor Octane Number (MON). The RON is measured in a test engine that runs under relatively mild conditions, while the MON is measured in a test engine that runs under more severe conditions. The Anti-Knock Index (AKI) is the average of the RON and MON. The cetane rating of diesel fuel is determined using a single test engine that runs under conditions similar to those in a real diesel engine. The cetane rating is measured by comparing the ignition delay of the test fuel to the ignition delay of two reference fuels, cetane and alpha-methylnaphthalene.

Keywords: - Motor Octane Number, Anti-Knock Index, Research Octane Number

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Heavy Metal Poisoning of Children Through Various Route of Administration : A Critical Review

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ABSTRACT

Baby food poisoning caused by heavy metals happens when infants or babies ingest baby food that is contaminated with toxic heavy metals such as lead, arsenic, mercury, cadmium, and others. Heavy metals are considered as miserable factor in milk and other food products due to the industrialization of countries and have an influence on their existence. Dietary sources include products manufactured with rice and vegetables that have been exposed to heavy metals like arsenic. The toxicity of heavy metals in infants is the result of exposure to long-term and low-level contamination in our environment, including the air we breathe, water, food, and so on. Heavy metal exposure in infants is a concern because of their developing bodies and immature detoxification systems. Heavy metals disrupt critical cellular functions by binding to enzymes and proteins, interfering with normal biochemical processes, and generating oxidative stress. This interference can lead

to a range of health problems in children, including developmental delays, cognitive impairment, behavioural issues, and damage to vital organs like the brain, liver, and kidneys.

Keywords: Heavy Metal, Lead, Arsenic, Detoxification, Biochemical.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Meta Data Extraction Of Document From Instant Messaging Applications Using Freewares

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ABSTRACT

With a focus on the use of freeware tools, this review paper investigates the complex environment of metadata extraction from documents within instant messaging apps. Platforms for instant messaging have proliferated in modern communication, producing enormous amounts of data that contain priceless information. These documents metadata extraction has become a critical topic of research, posing difficulties and opportunities for both academia and business. The study starts out by giving a general overview of the value of metadata for comprehending user behaviors, communication patterns, and information flow within instant messaging ecosystems. In light of the drawbacks and moral quandaries connected with proprietary solutions, it emphasizes the growing demand for effective and available methods to extract metadata. On the basis of their features, compatibility with various instant messaging systems, and user accessibility, a thorough evaluation of the available freeware solutions for metadata extraction is offered. The analysis takes into account the diversity of document formats shared as well as the constantly evolving nature of instant messaging platforms by comparing popular freeware solutions and their comparative merits. The paper also explores the technical side of metadata extraction, talking about issues like encryption, different data formats, and changing application programming interfaces (APIs). It investigates how freeware tools overcome these obstacles and modify their architectures to accommodate instant messaging program updates. The study continues by discussing possible future advances in freeware tools for metadata extraction, highlighting the necessity for improved cross-platform compatibility, increased efficiency, and advancements in managing encrypted communications.

Keywords : Programming, metadata, Encryption, Freeware

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Blowflies: Detecting Chemical Weapons and Other pollutants

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ABSTRACT

Forensic investigation also deals with cases involving chemical weapons. Chemical weapons are often devastating and are frequently classified as WMDs (weapons of mass destruction). Chemical weapons are still unlawfully employed in combat, such as in the Syrian civil war, despite a global ban. However, new research from Indiana University suggests that we can now use chemical weapons without the aid of humans because of blowflies. Blow flies are pervasive and very skilled at sampling the environment around us, and they can fly through the environment and taste it. As a result, the gut stores environmental information. As a blowfly is the alternative to humans, it will also be a safer method to keep people out of potentially dangerous situations. Mass spectrometry and liquid chromatography are the methods used to find out the chemicals present in the GUT of the fly. The chemical was found in the fly's gut even after exposure for approximately 14 days. So, this can also lead to the discovery of other pollutants in the environment, and by this way, we can also take the priceless samples from distant places.

keywords: Liquid Chromatography, Chemical Weapons, Mass Spectrometry

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Identifications Of Personality Based On Various Features Of Handwriting Using Random Forest Method

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ABSTRACT

To describe the personality based on "Handwriting" which is a multifarious process of writing something with a pen or pencil which can neither be copied nor be recreated due to its unique identity of an individual. It is deliberated as information, which exists as main supportive evidence in cases such as murder, suicides, kidnapping etc. by evaluating the various minute features possessed in handwriting for forensic examination. Uniqueness is the foremost requirement in each individual to create distinction whether it is made consciously or unconsciously. Clumsy, Tremulous and Hesitant are types of handwriting which became most familiar for offenders to commit activities like Suicide letters, Financial Documents, False records, disputed official documents and Forged documents in academics. In recent years, the exponentiation of various civil & criminal cases in handwriting has been increased, so the experts have developed several Random forest, CNN & ANN features for determining the personality of an individual from handwriting. Graphologists, who are professional handwriting examiners, believe that ones handwriting can reveal various aspects of their personality, including emotions, fears, honesty, and defense mechanisms. They often use seven handwriting features for analysis: (1) letter size, (2) slant, (3) baseline, (4) pen pressure, (5) letter spacing, (6) word spacing, and (7) top margin in a document to predict eight personality traits. By employing different classifiers like Random Forest, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), we aim to improve the accuracy of automated handwriting analysis. To enhance the process further, we standardize factors such as the type of pen, paper, margins, and incorporate personality-related questions to yield more precise results. Altogether handwriting has become a basic tool in most of the civil and criminal cases as an act of violence and the cases related to handwriting are increasingly gradually. The multiplying cases of forgeries and disguised documents in the world has become very challenging to deal with it but still we are not able to detect any proper solution to deal with these types of crimes. Thus, in the present study by using Random forest method researcher will try to throw a light on the material of handwriting, it uses & misuses, its consequences and analysis.

Key words: Handwriting, CNN & ANN features, Random forest method, disputed official documents, Forensic examination.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Interscript Comparison Of Handwriting For Author Identification In Marathi Population

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ABSTRACT

The India displays a high degree of religious, linguistic, cultural, racial, as well as geographical diversity. The languages spoken here belongs to several families in which major ones being the Indo-Aryan languages spoken by approximately 75% of Indians and the Dravidian languages spoken by approximately 20% of Indians. There exist more than ten different scripts in India that are used for various Indian languages. The popular ones are Devanagari, Gurumukhi, Devanagari Gujarati and several others. The Devanagari script is used in Indian languages like Hindi, Marathi, Maithili, Rajasthani, etc. Script is a particular style of writing. Basically, it can be comprehended as a symbolic representation of sounds of a particular language. Giving opinion upon the authorship in various languages has always been a matter of debate. Hence, there is a need to study the similarities between the languages belonging to the same script for the purpose of comparative examination. In this interscript study, A total of 80 samples were collected; 30 male and 50 female. There were three scripts for each writer. The two languages Hindi, and Marathi belonging to Devanagari script was considered and correlated with the English language belonging to Roman script. The general features of Devanagari and Roman script such as alignment, letter size, slant, pen pressure, style, spelling errors, left margin, angularity etc. were studied in the samples provided. In this study, we have tried to explain the similarities between the two different languages of same script as well as we have attempted the interscript comparison of handwriting for the purpose of author identification.

Keywords: Handwriting examination, author identification, interscript comparison, etc.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Capabilities and Analysis of Cloud Forensic

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ABSTRACT

Cloud forensics is the ability to collect and analyze evidence from various sources, including servers, storage systems, and virtual machines. Cloud forensic refers to the process of collecting, analyzing and preserving digital evidence in cloud environment. It helps in (i) Data collection, (ii) Data preservation, (iii) understanding cloud models, (iv) Logging and auditing, (v) Legal compliance, (vi) Network analysis etc. It is done by – 1) Identification of the incident, 2) Incident classification, 3) Evidence identification, 4) Evidence preservation, 5) Data collection and documentation, 6) Legal consideration, 7) Reports. Language used for tracing the hacked data Python, Power shell, SQL. Cloud forensic is a complex and evolving field, as cloud technology continues to advance. Adaptation to new challenges and technologies is essential for effective investigation in cloud environment. Organizations utilize cloud forensic for incident management and business continuity programs.

Keywords:- Cloud computing, cloud forensics, cloud Environments, Enterprise Cloud solutions.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Crime And Gender : Gender And Offending Pattern

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ABSTRACT

This paper delves into the intricate dynamics of gender influence on criminal behaviour patterns, drawing from a robust body of research. A consistent finding emerges, indicating that men exhibit a higher propensity for engaging in severe criminal activities such as homicide and aggravated assault, while women tend to be involved in non-violent offenses like theft and fraud. The roots of men's inclination towards violent crimes are explored within the context of societal expectations of masculinity, fostering aggression and dominance. Contributing factors encompass peer pressure and easy access to weapons. In contrast, women often find themselves embroiled in criminal activities due to economic necessity, familial responsibilities, and distinct life trajectories. A focused examination of homicide patterns reveals nuanced differences. Men predominantly utilize blunt objects as weapons, potentially influenced by societal perceptions of masculinity and their physical strength. Women, constrained by comparatively less physical strength, often resort to sharp objects like knives, a choice potentially tied to self-defence strategies or assertion of aggression. While women do engage in homicide, the modus operandi significantly differs from that of men, ranging from cruel intentions to acts of pure self-defence. The paper also scrutinizes the

response of the criminal justice system to gender-related crimes, uncovering inherent biases and stereotypes. Female offenders tend to receive more lenient charges or punishments for analogous offenses compared to their male counterparts. As society undergoes continuous evolution, gender roles are in flux, prompting transformations in the intricate relationship between gender and criminal behaviour. This comprehensive review provides valuable insights into the complex interplay of gender dynamics within the realm of criminology.

Keywords : self- defence, criminal behaviour, violence, masculinity

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Effects Of Movies And TV Series On Forensic Science

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ABSTRACT

Over the past two decades, forensic-themed television shows have surged in popularity, contributing to the phenomenon known as the CSI effect wherein public perceptions and expectations of forensic evidence are influenced by these portrayals. This study explores the perspectives of students enrolled in forensic science programs, both quantitatively and qualitatively, focusing on popular shows such as CSI, Bones, and Dexter. Feedback from students addresses the accuracy, morality, professionalism, and portrayal of role models within these programs. The majority of students acknowledged that these shows often present a distorted image of the forensic profession to the public. However, they also identified elements that could be leveraged for recruitment and educational purposes. This research delves into the CSI Effect, originally coined to describe the impact of forensic television on juror expectations during criminal trials. The study examines how these portrayals, characterized by superior production standards and innovative visual elements, reshape the public's perception of forensic science and influence decision-making processes. Analyzing survey data from students enrolled in a forensic anthropology course, this poster presents findings on their interest in forensic science media and its influence on educational and career choices. Notably, it highlights a crucial distinction between real-life forensic evidence and its portrayal on TV, emphasizing that matches are rarely perfect. Contrary to popular belief, experimental research conducted by German scientists suggests that watching forensic science TV programs is not associated with an increased ability to evade detection when committing a crime. The poster concludes by underscoring the impact of visual elements, such as crime scene photos and program editing, on shaping the public's perception of forensic occurrences. Overall, this research provides valuable insights into the complex interplay between forensic science education, popular media, and public understanding.

Keywords : forensic , analyse, educational, impression

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

To Analyse The Impact Of Soil On The Yield Of DNA From Forensic Mixed Sample

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ABSTRACT

In general, Soil mixed biological fluids are mostly encountered evidences in an outdoor crime scene. These biological evidences contain DNA which has a significant role in forensic science in conviction guilt of an accused person. Because it links the suspect, victim to the crime scene and helps in the identification of culprit and victim. Temperature, humidity, storage condition, time since deposition etc. have a significant impact on the yield of DNA. Various kind of microorganisms, bacteria, humic acid and other elements found in the soil are responsible for DNA degradation. Information gathered from published literature on soil mixed biological samples are stored, from 1 week to 3 years, in different environmental conditions (soil, temperature, humidity, etc.) helped to analyse the impact of soil and environment on the yield on DNA from biological mixed samples. Based on these findings, experimental research was conducted employing Various organic and inorganic techniques to analyse DNA samples. It is concluded that samples stored at low temperature (-20°C) identified as the best storage condition without degradation. Sandy soil showed highest yield of DNA than sample placed with the other type of soils (silt, clay and marshy). After 3 months sample placed in indoor scenario lost 80% of DNA, similarly 92% of DNA loss in outdoor scenario. The yield of DNA was significantly higher from the samples which had less soil particles.

Keywords: Environmental factors, DNA yield, Indoor scenario, Outdoor scenario, Conviction

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

A Sustainable Approach to Latent Fingerprint Development Using Discarded Groundnut Shell Nano-Biochar

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ABSTRACT

Latent fingerprints are the most encountered evidence on the scene of crime. Hence, the need for the usage of developing materials has increased tremendously. This work discusses the development of latent fingerprints using an environment-friendly and cost-effective powder material derived from groundnut shells. The groundnut shells were collected from local factories where they are discarded on a large scale. The shells were cleaned and oven dried and then subjected to pyrolyzation to obtain groundnut shell biochar. The biochar was further

treated for synthesis of nanoparticles using ball milling technique. The groundnut shell nano-biochar was characterized using Scanning Electron microscopy for the surface morphology and particle size and FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) for biochar properties. The groundnut shell nano-biochar was then used to develop latent fingerprint on 30 surfaces of porous, semi-porous and non-porous nature. The efficiency of the developed fingerprint on non-porous surfaces was the maximum about 99% and least for the porous surfaces about 80%. The groundnut shell nano-biochar was successfully utilized for the development of latent fingerprints as all the ridge characteristics and fingerprint pattern were clearly identifiable. The future aspects of nanotechnology in latent fingerprint development have also been discussed in the end.

Keywords: Latent fingerprint; Biochar; Nanotechnology; Nano-biochar

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic Light Source: An Important Tool For Preliminary Identification Of Body Fluids In Various Crimes

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ABSTRACT

In various nature of crimes, body fluids viz., blood, semen, saliva, vaginal fluid, urine, fecal matter, milk etc. are most commonly found. There is big challenge to identify the mixing of various body fluids at the scene of crime. The advance forensic light source is one of the most useful tools for the preliminary identification of various body fluids. The forensic light source comprise different wave length's lights. It is well established that various body fluid shows different emission spectra that make it possible to preliminary identify the mixing of body fluids. It also has been noticed that body fat sometime interfere in the chemical test to identify body fluids whereas forensic light source also useful in this situation. Thus, forensic light source is one of the most important tools for the preliminary identification of various body fluids.

Keywords: Forensic light source, body fluids, crime

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Comprehensive Study of Cyber Attacks and Its Prevention

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ABSTRACT

The association of cyber-attacks or cyber terrorists like, hackers with cyber warfare is booming all around in the world. As electronic technology becomes more prevalent, protecting data from cyber-

attacks becomes more challenging. Criminally motivated attackers seek, financial gain through data theft, money theft, or even disruption in business. The density and complexity of cyber threats majorly involves theft of business financial data, customer financial data, trade secrets, email addresses and login credentials, financial online payments, government agencies data and many more. The detection and identification of anomalies in network events is increasingly difficult due to the rise in complexity and frequency of cyberattacks. Financial loss, business loss, expense increases, and investment loss can all result from a cyberattack. Phishing, malware, and ransomware are typical internet threats. Records related to customers, finances, company strategies, intellectual property, and employees must all be protected. Cybersecurity experts find it challenging to keep track of every action taking place on the network due to the ever-increasing network density. A variety of solutions have been proposed by researchers around the world to stop cyberattacks or lessen the harm they cause to organizations in order to prevent harm from cyberattacks. As of the present scenario, cyber criminals use sophisticated tools to launch cyber-attacks against such companies. This review study majorly focuses on common types of cyber-attacks such as Backdoor Trojan, cross site scripting (XSS) attack, malware ransomware, phishing, SQL injection, zero day exploit and DNS tunnelling which are prevalent all over the globe. Some of the techniques are currently being used, while others are still being studied. The purpose of this study is to review in depth the standard advancements in cyber security and tools used to prevent cyber threats.

Keywords : cyber-crime; descendant attacks; hacking; information technology; key management

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic Psychology : Profiling Criminal Behaviour and Offenders Characteristics

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ABSTRACT

Forensic psychology stands at the intersection of psychology and criminal justice, contributing essential insights into the understanding of criminal behavior and the profiling of offender characteristics. This abstract offers a glimpse into the multifaceted field of forensic psychology, highlighting its pivotal role in modern law enforcement and the legal system. Forensic psychologists also engage in the critical task of psychological assessments within the criminal justice system. These assessments inform legal decisions, ensuring that the mental health and psychological well-being of individuals involved in criminal cases

are considered. Furthermore, forensic psychologists serve as expert witness in court, providing professional opinions and insights on the psychological aspects of criminal cases to assist judges and juries in making informed decisions. The practice of criminal profiling is a prominent aspect of forensic psychology. Profilers employ psychological principles to create detailed profiles of unknown criminals, offering law enforcement valuable information to aid in investigations. These profiles encompass characteristics such as age, gender, background, and potential motives, all of which assist investigators in narrowing their focus and developing strategies to apprehend offenders. This abstract underscores the vital role of forensic psychology in profiling criminal behavior and understanding offender characteristics. It serves as a reminder that the insights and expertise of forensic psychologists are invaluable assets in the pursuit of justice, bringing together the realms of psychology and criminal justice to enhance the effectiveness of law enforcement and the legal system.

Keywords:- criminal profiling, offender characteristics, investigative techniques, expert testimony, serial offender profiling

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Developing Forensic Investigations: The Toxicology Implications Of Hair Analysis

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ABSTRACT

With the development of hair analysis, forensic toxicology, a crucial component of contemporary criminal investigations and judicial proceedings, has undergone a dramatic change. This thorough examination explores the complex field of hair analysis and sheds light on its analytical value in the development of forensic investigations. We emphasize the painstaking techniques necessary to preserve the integrity of the evidence material, beginning with the crucial need of correct hair sample collection and preservation. We also recognize the crucial function of these first processes in forming later analysis. We thoroughly explore the variety of analytical methods used to analyse hair, ranging from well-established techniques like Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) and Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) to the most recent technological developments. For the precise detection and quantification of a wide range of toxicants inside the intricate matrices of hair, it is essential to comprehend the complexities of these approaches. We examine the capacity of hair analysis to detect and identify a variety of harmful compounds, including illegal narcotics, environmental contaminants, and heavy metals, in order to broaden our scope and provide a more detailed understanding of exposure patterns and timings. Hair analysis still faces many difficulties and disagreements, despite the increased awareness of its potential. These concerns are critically discussed in this review, along with discussions of the validity of the results, potential sources of contamination, and the development of the legal system. This review considerably contributes

to the continuing discussion on the analytical impulse by offering a thorough synthesis of collection methodologies, analytical intricacy, and interpretative nuances.

Key word: Toxicants, admissibility

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic Facial Reconstruction

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ABSTRACT

Forensic facial reconstruction is the process of recreating the face of an individual from their skeletal remains. It involves a combination of scientific analysis and artistic interpretation to estimate facial features such as eyes, nose and mouth. This is the most subjective as well as one of the most controversial technique used in the field of forensic science. This technic can aid in the identification of an unknown individuals in criminal cases and can provide leads by creating a visual representation of suspects or victims, aiding law enforcement in solving crimes. In some legal cases, facial reconstruction can be presented as an evidence in the court with other forensic testimonial evidences. It can help in the determination of sex, age, facial features, that leads to the identification of the unknown person. This technique is used in various cases such as mass disasters, arson cases, buried decomposed bodies. There are two types of facial reconstruction, two dimensional and three dimensional. 3D face recognition has a potential to achieve better accuracy than its 2D counterpart by measuring geometry of rigid features on the face. 2D facial reconstruction is done based on the ante- mortem photographs and skull. There are several methods of manual facial reconstruction but the Combination Manchester method has been reported to be the best and most accurate method for positive recognition of an individual. Recognition allows the involved government agencies to make a list of a suspect victims. This can lead to a positive identification.

Keywords; Artistic interpretation, Controversial Technique, Combination Manchester Method

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

A Comprehensive Study on Chemical Warfare Agents

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ABSTRACT

Weapons of mass destruction have been utilized for a very long time. In this regard, humans have invented several forms of chemical warfare agents for use in a variety of contexts, including personal or political

agendas, power struggles between countries, terrorism, and other forms of warfare that have been used since the beginning of the world wars. Numerous organizations utilized it since it was simple to obtain, could be used in small amounts to cause significant damage and large casualties, and was also difficult to detect. As per the time we were founding different types of warfare agents, which are more dangerous and brutal than the old ones, very little has been found on the treatment of the warfare agents; in many cases, there was no antidote or basic treatment present for chemical warfare. In this review, we will discuss and compare different warfare agents. The distinctive characteristics of many chemical warfare agents include their modes of operation, including how our bodies respond to the chemicals and what they do inside our bodies, their indications and symptoms on the body, and their various methods of detection and treatment. New technologies have been discovered that aid in the detection of chemical warfare. At last, we will see advanced detection techniques and treatments for effective defense in different chemical warfare.

Key words:- Chemical warfare, technologies, destruction, agenda.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Correlation Of Fingerprint And Footprint In Individual Identification

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ABSTRACT

In the realm of forensic science, by Sir Francis Galton in 1892, examines distinctive patterns formed by friction ridges and furrows on fingers, thumbs, palms, toes, and feet. These unique patterns serve as a cornerstone for individual identification, even differentiating among monozygotic twins, proving invaluable in mass disaster scenarios. Research in this field seeks to establish correlations between fingerprints and footprints from the same individual, thereby advancing forensic identification methodologies. Ridge patterns, formed in the human fetes before birth, remain consistent throughout a person's life, barring exceptions such as accidents leading to bruises or cuts on the fingertips. Notably, even small cuts or abrasions do not alter fingerprints due to the regeneration of the original dermis. Consequently, these prints hold enduring value in forensic investigations. Forensic analysis extends beyond fingerprints to footprints and footwear impressions, aiding investigators in reconstructing crime sequences. Determining the number of individuals present and their movement direction at a crime scene can be challenging. However, footprint and footwear analysis facilitates such determinations. Moreover, these analyses provide insights into stature, weight, sex, carrying heavy objects, and movement speed, enhancing investigative accuracy. In cases of mass fatality incidents, post-mortem friction ridge prints (fingerprints, palm prints, or footprints) serve as the fastest primary method for victim identification. Dactylography, the process of obtaining impressions of papillary ridges on fingertips, plays a crucial role in this identification process. Notably, fingerprints, being

permanent and unique, differentiate even among monozygotic twins. Common ridge patterns identified through meticulous analysis include Loops, Whorls, Composites, and Arches. While extensive studies have explored individual identification through fingerprint and footprint analysis, there remains a notable gap in research concerning the correlation between an individual's fingerprint and footprint patterns for identification purposes. Addressing this gap holds significant potential for advancing forensic science and improving the accuracy of identification methodologies.

Keywords: Footprint, identification, fingerprint, investigation

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic Investigation Of Bullet Holes For Determining The Distance From Glass Fragments

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ABSTRACT

Fragments of glass are substantial physical evidence found in different kinds of scenes in an investigation. In such cases where firearms are involved, glass fractures may provide valuable information related to what happened and help in investigating the crime scene. Glass can be fractured intentionally or unintentionally at the crime scenes. Analysis of glass fracture patterns often provides much significant information like causes of fracture, the direction of a bullet hitting the target, impact on fracture pattern from distance and direction, etc. Holes occurring in the glass at crime scenes have much importance and many attempts are taken to investigate the properties of these glass holes to find the type, speed, and angle of the projectile that probably produce the hole. For high-velocity projectiles including bullets, these bullet holes in glass can exhibit certain features and fractures. The objective of this research was to determine the distance of a shooter from the bullet hole in glass used in automobiles. Bullet holes were prepared and different parameters of glass fractures like bullet hole diameter, cone fracture radius, cone fracture diameter, radial, and concentric fracture count were considered from both the front and the backside of the glass. Bullet hole distance help in determine the distance of weapon from glass some time it play evidential role in investigation. The determination of distance was related to the factors and parameters used in this research and also to some other environmental factors. If factors or parameters are changed then resulting observations and results will also change accordingly. These findings can be supportive of forensic criminal investigations along with new related detective parameters for researchers. Bullet holes investigation to determine these factors with the help of fracture analysis can be helpful to construct rational judgment by interpreting the evidence, for forensic investigations.

keywords - bullet, direction, distance, glass, projectile.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Emerging Technologies In Crime Scene Investigation

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ABSTRACT

A crucial part of forensic investigation is crime scene analysis, which gathers and examines evidences in order to recreate events and identify criminals. In the intricate tapestry of criminal investigations, few threads are as vital and transformative as the art of crime scene analysis. Forensic investigators meticulously gather and examine the strands of evidence, unraveling the cryptic narrative woven into the scene. Crime scene analysis has changed significantly throughout time as a result of substantial improvements in forensic techniques that make it possible for investigators to obtain, analyze, and interpret evidence more quickly and correctly. The objective of this review paper is to explore recent developments in crime scene analysis, with a particular emphasis on the incorporation of various forensic technologies for thorough and interdisciplinary investigations. The initial phase of this study goes through conventional methods including fingerprint analysis, ballistics, and conventional techniques for trace evidence analysis. These reliable methods have been significant in forensic investigations because they have helped identify criminals and reconstruct crime scenes by providing important evidence. New technologies, however, have emerged as a result of the drawbacks of these conventional methods, such as subjectivity, sample size requirements, and time-consuming procedures. The review study also addresses recent advances in forensic technologies, highlighting methods like Mass Spectrometry Imaging (MSI) that make it easier to identify and map trace compounds on crime scene surfaces and the use of Rapid DNA Analysis that accelerates the identification, expediting investigation and reducing backlog. The need of combining these technologies is emphasized in order to improve the effectiveness, accuracy, and interdisciplinary character of crime scene investigation.

Keywords: Crime Scene Investigation, Forensic Techniques, Conventional Methodologies, Emerging Technologies

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Datura stramonium as a Potential Sedative Agent

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ABSTRACT

Forensic toxicology is the analysis of biological samples for the presence of toxins, including drugs. India has a great wealth of naturally occurring plant drugs which have a great potential pharmacological activity. Datura is one of the widely well-known folklore medicinal herbs. It is a plant with both poisonous and medicinal properties and

has been proven to have great properties in the medical world. Datura stramonium commonly called as Jimson weed, has contributed various pharmacological in the scientific field of Indian history of medicine like analgesic and anti-asthmatic activities. The current paper presents an exclusive review work on the ethnomedical, phytochemical and pharmacological properties of this plant.

Keywords: Datura stramonium, Jimsonweed, Ethnomedical, traditional uses, Pharmacology

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Managing the Poisoning of Yellow Kaner

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ABSTRACT

Poisoning due to deliberate self-harm with the seeds of yellow oleander (*Thevetin peruviana*) results in significant morbidity and mortality each year in South Asia. Yellow oleander seeds contain highly toxic cardiac glycosides including Thevetin A and B and neriifolin. Important epidemiological and clinical differences exist between poisoning due to yellow oleander and digoxin; yellow oleander poisoning is commonly seen in younger patients without preexisting illness or comorbidity. No definite criteria are available for risk stratification. Continuous ECG monitoring for at least 24 hours is necessary to detect arrhythmias; longer monitoring is appropriate in patients with severe poisoning. Supportive care. Correction of dehydration with normal saline is necessary, and antiemetics are used to control severe vomiting. Electrolytes. Hypokalemia worsens toxicity due to digitalis glycosides, and hyperkalemia is life-threatening. Both must be corrected. Hyperkalemia is due to extracellular shift of potassium rather than an increase in total body potassium and is best treated with insulin-dextrose infusion. Intravenous calcium increases the risk of cardiac arrhythmias and is not recommended in treating hyperkalemia. Bradyarrhythmia are commonly managed with atropine, isoprenaline, and temporary cardiac pacing in severe cases, although without trial evidence of survival benefit, or adequate evaluation of possible risks. Tachyarrhythmias have a poor prognosis and are more difficult to treat. Further studies are required.

Keywords: Thevetin peruviana, Yellow Oleander, Hypokalemia, Bradyarrhythmia.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Analysing Vulnerabilities at Micro Level of Crime Scene

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ABSTRACT

Examination of crime scene vulnerability at micro level is very important and crucial component for both crime hindrance and for examination purpose. Crime scene is the only place or only a way of getting the information from variety of things Might happen to cause criminal activity. Different policymaker's law enforcement organization forensic investigators created successful plans for increasing security lower the crime rate and improve the overall response or situations related to the criminal activities by understanding the different vulnerabilities but still there are some parameters which need more improvement. Historically many attempts were made by many organizations to prevent the crime but at macro level such as social dynamics neighbourhood features but researchers now revealed that not only macro levels but also the micro level vulnerability are important to understand and for solving the crime which includes both physical and procedural elements. Organizations of this respective field that are law enforcement agencies or policymakers can improve their ability to stop and solve crimes by recognizing an addressing these issues or weaknesses. Improper access control, inadequate illumination insufficient service systems are some things which cause Micro level Vulnerability at physical level. In case of procedural vulnerability training procedures, evidence management are some problems which can be resolved by looking into this matters. This study includes some insightful information regarding the vulnerability add the crime seen at micro level and by providing advice about how investigation procedures can be enhanced, and how to enhance the efforts to prevent the crime which main goal is to make community safer to respective law enforcement agencies and decision makers.

Key Words: Crime Scene Investigation; Vulnerability; Procedural Vulnerability; Physical Vulnerability ;micro level examination

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Forensic Toxicological And Analytical Techniques of Carbamate Poisoning

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ABSTRACT

Carbamates are a class of insecticides structurally and mechanically similar to organophosphate (OP) insecticides. Carbamates are N-methyl carbamates derived from a carbamic acid. Carbamates are usually used as sprays or baits to kill insects by affecting their brains and nervous systems. They are used on crops or in homes to kill cockroaches, ants, fleas, crickets, aphids, scales, whiteflies, lace bugs, and mealy bugs. Some carbamates control mosquitoes too. Although pesticides play an important role in modern agriculture they also pose a great threat to humans and animals due to their toxicity. In particular, carbamates are the pesticides used all over the world for crop protection. Carbamate exposure can be dermal, oral, through inhalational, or through the eyes. Intentional, accidental oral consumption or occupational dermal exposure are the most common

causes of carbamate toxicity. These chemicals are incredibly harmful to humans. As a result, detecting and determining these pesticides in biological material due to exposure to these chemicals and their metabolites is crucial in forensic toxicology practice. Carbamates are derived from a carbamic acid (NH₂COOH) that are commonly used as insecticides. To analyse these pesticides chromatographic methods like liquid and gas chromatography are used due to their ability to separate different chemicals in a sample. Many other techniques are also used for analysis like single-quadrupole, ion-trap, triple-quadrupole, or tandem mass spectrometry which provides results with great precision and accuracy. The objective of this poster is to describe various methods by which these pesticides are determined in different samples like urine, blood and tissues encountered in emergency hospital laboratories or forensic science laboratories.

Keywords: carbamate toxicity, chromatography, spectrometry

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

A Contemporary Exploration Of Designer Drugs and Its Analysis Of Their Escalating Role in Crime.

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ABSTRACT

Designer drugs, a class of synthetic substances contrived to imitate the effects of controlled substances while evading legal regulations, have become a pervasive and complex issue in the realm of illicit drug use. Psychoactive substances with chemical or pharmacological profiles analogous to those of traditional abuse-inducing chemicals are still emerging in the recreational drug market. For instance, internet vendors sell these de novo drugs regardless of adhering to the legal statutes, furthermore with no legal consequences. The purpose of this abstract is to provide an accentuated analysis of the escalating misuse of designer drugs in numerous forms of criminal behavior, stressing their increasing importance in the contemporary criminal landscape. It also delves into the intricate ways in which these substances have become catalysts for criminal activities, both directly and indirectly. On the whole, designer drugs exhibit numerous parallels with traditional drugs of abuse in terms of their mechanism of action and adverse effects. Designer drugs could bypass detection through traditional drug screening precisely because of their novelty, thereby rendering it difficult to assess their negative effects. According to accounts of intoxication, multiple designer drugs are reportedly used concurrently, posing a high risk for severe adverse effects and even death. As such, to curb the prominent increase of this drug, proper forensic analysis may help to limit the use of this drug and the criminal activities promoted by it.

Keywords: designer drugs, psychoactive substances, de novo, criminal activities, traditional

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Trending Methodologies of Signal Hijacking

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ABSTRACT

“When thinking about cybercrime, there are certain crimes that occupy our mind; like hacking, cyberbullying, phishing and much more. But, rarely is there any mention of “Signal Hijacking”. This hacking sector has existed in the world of crime since the 20th century. There are ‘n’ number of signals i.e., electrical, or electromagnetic signals used in today’s era of networking. And in this world, nothing is there which does not have a two- faced reality attached to it. This paper brings the dark side of signal hijacking into the spotlight. As much the uses of these current waves are diverse, the existing laws and policies for the same are as confusing as they could be. Different methodologies of signal hijacking and manipulation like Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Wireless Network Hacking, Cell phone Hacking, and Satellite Hacking are the major areas of the spotlight of this paper. To bring them into one place from various sections of IT Act 2000, IPC, CrPC and ideal ways of conducting investigations in such cases; this paper serves you the purpose. Along with the Landmark cases of history, readily available modern-day devices used for this black purpose are also going to be examined thoroughly. This paper will bring the hidden side of cybercrimes to your knowledge. For the requisite of understanding the concept pondering the research motives to study the prevalent signal hacking devices, case studies, vulnerabilities, exploits and vigilance reports.”

Key Words: Signal Hijacking, Signals, Hacking, Signal Manipulation, Cyber Crime, IT Act 2000, Cyber Laws, Hacking Devices, Cyber Crime Cases, Vulnerabilities, DoS attacks.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Wrongful Conviction and Forensic Science

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ABSTRACT

The scientific foundations of various methodologies that were formerly generally accepted by the criminal legal system and used to aid in securing early unjust convictions have been exposed as having flaws over time as a result of advancements in the field of forensic science. The rising number of false convictions is one of the major issues of nation has with its criminal justice system. Because of this, more innocent individuals are behind bars now than at any other period in history. The issue at hand is whether or not the government can recover every lost year from the life of a victim who was unfairly

imprisoned. Unjust, illegal convictions and the government's disregard for natural justice principles create particular challenges that need to be addressed and examined. There are many articles discussing the victims perspective as a result of false convictions and the criminal justice system & failure to provide proper justice in accordance with forensic science, which has been strongly advocated as a means of establishing the convictions and veracity. Every department that demonstrates a connection to the legal system has evolved as a result of erroneous convictions. In contrast, forensic science has been crucial in revealing cases to convictions and can also be a troublesome aspect of the legal system. Forensic errors, eyewitness misidentification, false confessions, and other factors, which have a significant impact on the conviction, are among the many factors affecting the justice in the question of conviction. Where as the Unreliable testimony that exaggerates the forensic sciences judgement and precision leads to incorrect convictions are also one of its factor. In addition, the Innocence Project, a national litigation and public policy organisation, researches the cases of people who have been exonerated after being wrongfully convicted in order to determine what can be learned from them in order to lessen the possibility of erroneous convictions when forensic scientists conduct tests, interpret the results, draw conclusions, and testify to their findings.

Keywords: wrongful conviction, forensic science, exoneration, victims, testimonies.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Phishing: The Silent Threat in Cyberspace

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ABSTRACT

Phishing is a malicious practice wherein cybercriminals impersonate trusted entities to deceive recipients into divulging sensitive information, such as login credentials, financial data, or personal details. Over the years, phishing has diversified into various forms, including spear-phishing, vishing (voice phishing), and smishing (SMS phishing), making it more challenging to detect. Phishing attacks often commence with enticing messages or emails designed to manipulate human psychology, exploiting fear, urgency, or curiosity. Cybercriminals meticulously craft these messages, mimicking legitimate sources, to increase their success rates. Effective detection and prevention strategies are essential to thwart phishing attempts. As phishing continues to evolve, it remains a paramount concern for individuals and organizations. Constant vigilance, updated security measures, and user education are key to mitigating the risks associated with phishing and safeguarding digital assets and personal information.

Keywords: Phishing, Types of Phishing and Detection.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Borderline Personality Disorder and its Correlation to Violence and Suicidal Aspects in Forensic Psychology

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ABSTRACT

A borderline personality disorder is a mental disorder associated with high rates of severe functionality disorder, suicide rates, and high rates of concurrent mental disorders. Subjects with this disorder also exhibit co-morbid anti-social personality disorder. Due to substantial treatment use, subjects with borderline personality disorder are more violent and require more attention. This study examined the relationship between features of borderline personality disorder with respect to violence, self-harm and suicidal tendencies. The authors theorized the vague characteristic of borderline personality disorder with probable impetuous behaviour with co-relation to childhood trauma that would be linked with violence and suicidal behaviour. Statistics show that 73% of the subjects engage in violence, evidences also show higher risks of subjects being involved in domestic violence. The cause of this disorder though not prominent, yet adverse life events, such as physical and sexual abuse, childhood trauma, genetic factors contribute to the development of this disorder. Treatment involved in this disorder though do not directly affect it but reduce depression, anxiety and impulsive aggression. Clinical signs of this disorder include, dysregulation of emotions, impulsive nature, aggression, repeated self-injury and chronic suicidal tendencies. The studies show violence as a serious and prevalent issue among subjects with BPD. More extensive study and research is required for the grasp and supervision of this clinical condition responsible for many psychological behaviours.

Keywords: Border Personality Disorder, self-harm, suicidal tendencies

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

Qualitative Analysis of Chewing Tobacco-Related Toxins Using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry in Rohini, Delhi

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ABSTRACT

This research paper presents a comprehensive qualitative analysis of tobacco-related toxins in chewing tobacco mixed with pan masala, specifically focusing on chewing tobacco, using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) in the Rohini district of Delhi, India. The study aimed to assess the presence and levels of specific compounds associated with the use of chewing tobacco and its toxic impact on human body. The primary objectives of this investigation were to

identify the key chewing tobacco-related toxins, including volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and other hazardous chemicals, within the Rohini district. A wide range of chewing tobacco samples that comes with pan masala were collected over an extended period to capture temporal variations and potential sources of these contaminants. The results revealed the presence of various chewing tobacco-associated compounds, such as tobacco-specific nitrosamines (TSNAs), aldehyde, esters, acids, alcohols, ketones and other VOCs varying to different brands. The discussion highlights the significance of these findings in shedding light on the detrimental effects of chewing tobacco on public health and the environment. It underscores the urgent need for awareness campaigns, regulatory measures, and educational initiatives to reduce the exposure of individuals to these harmful toxins, ultimately contributing to better health outcomes in the Rohini district and similar urban areas grappling with the use of chewing tobacco. This study provides valuable insights for policymakers, healthcare professionals, and environmental scientists concerned with the adverse effects of chewing tobacco on human health.

Keywords: Chewing tobacco, Tobacco-related toxins, Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry, Tobacco-specific nitrosamines, Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Scientific Analysis of Miscarriage Drugs and Their Perspective in Forensic Science

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ABSTRACT

The scientific analysis of miscarriage-inducing drugs and their forensic perspective is crucial in understanding their pharmacological mechanisms and implications in forensic science. Drugs like misoprostol and mifepristone, along with traditional herbal remedies, are commonly used to induce miscarriage. They work through various mechanisms, affecting uterine muscles and the endometrial lining, leading to pregnancy termination from a forensic standpoint, the identification and analysis of these substances in cases of suspected drug-induced miscarriage are essential. Forensic science can determine the presence and concentration of these drugs in biological samples, helping distinguish between natural and induced miscarriages, particularly in cases involving criminal intent or foul play. This analysis also acknowledges the legal and ethical complexities surrounding miscarriage drugs. Laws and regulations differ across jurisdictions, impacting healthcare providers and forensic scientists dealing with such cases. The study underscores the ethical dilemmas faced by medical professionals when patients seek information on self-induced miscarriage. In summary, understanding the pharmacology of miscarriage drugs and their role in forensic science is crucial for accurate investigations and legal proceedings. It also raises awareness of the ethical considerations and legal disparities in addressing this

sensitive topic, ultimately aiding in better addressing the forensic challenges associated with miscarriages induced by drugs.

Keywords: Miscarriage Drug, Pregnancy, Pharmacological, Forensic Science.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Human Trafficking: A Curse on Humanity

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ABSTRACT

Human trafficking involves the trade of individuals for various exploitative purposes, such as forced labor, sexual slavery, or commercial sexual exploitation. This issue disproportionately affects women and children, who are vulnerable due to socio-economic disparities, political instability, and gender inequality. Victims of trafficking endure both physical and psychological trauma, with their fundamental rights and dignity brutally stripped away. It has emerged as a growing global threat to the lives and freedom of million of people. The objective of this poster is to examine the causes and modes of human trafficking and to ensure measures to control this. Let's unite to raise awareness, support survivors, and end this modern-day slavery. Efforts should focus on eradicating human trafficking and support its victims. "Stop human trafficking: unchain lives, uphold rights. Join the fight, Be the light. Report, educate, support – End the Exploitation."

Keywords: Slavery, exploitation, trauma, eradicating

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

The Emerging Role of AI in Forensics: Enhancing Decomposition Analysis And Postmortem Interval Estimation

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ABSTRACT

This extended abstract delves into the burgeoning utilization of AI in forensic investigations, with a specific focus on its application in the comprehensive analysis of decomposition processes and the precise estimation of postmortem intervals (PMIs). Forensic science has traditionally relied on conventional methods to estimate PMIs, incorporating factors such as body temperature, rigor mortis, and insect activity. However, the integration of AI technologies has introduced innovative tools and techniques that not only complement but also significantly enhance these traditional methods. In the context of decomposition analysis, AI-driven image recognition algorithms have

reached unprecedented levels of sophistication, capable of identifying and categorizing subtle changes in postmortem bodies. They meticulously track the intricate progression of decomposition, offering investigators invaluable insights into the likely time of death, potential causes, and circumstances surrounding the event. Moreover, AI has catalyzed the development of predictive models that amalgamate a wide array of data sources. These encompass weather conditions, insect behavior, forensic entomology findings, and more. These multifaceted models, often based on machine learning and deep learning techniques, generate PMI estimates of remarkable precision. Additionally, AI extends its influence beyond decomposition analysis, streamlining the evaluation of diverse forensic data types. AI-powered algorithms can identify patterns, potential matches, and even genetic markers related to ancestry or specific medical conditions, enhancing the overall efficacy of forensic DNA analysis. Furthermore, AI plays a pivotal role in the analysis of toxicological results. It assists forensic experts in comprehending the implications of various substances found in postmortem samples.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, decomposition processes, postmortem interval, genetic markers, toxicological findings, interpretation of DNA profiles

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Investigating the Influence of CNS Stimulant & CNS Depressant Combination on Locomotor and Lifespan in *C. elegans*

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ABSTRACT

C. elegans (Caenorhabditis elegans) as a model organism to study the combined effects of drugs because of its simplicity and genetic tractability, which allows for the investigation of underlying mechanisms. Studies in *C. elegans* can provide valuable insights into how these substances affect the nervous system and overall health, potentially leading to a better understanding of drug actions and their consequences in more complex organisms, including humans. The simplicity of *C. elegans*' nervous system, consisting of just 302 neurons, has allowed researchers to unravel fundamental principles of neural development and function. Studies on *C. elegans* have provided insights into the mechanism of action of drugs induced over the model underlying ageing and lifespan regulation. Researchers have investigated various behaviours in *C. elegans*, including chemotaxis, thermotaxis, and social behaviours, shedding light on neural circuits and sensory perception. *C. elegans* has been used to model human diseases such as Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and cystic fibrosis, aiding in drug discovery and understanding disease mechanisms. The influence of CNS (Central Nervous System) stimulants and depressants on locomotor behaviour and lifespan in *C. elegans*, a commonly used model organism toxicology research, can provide insights into neurotoxicity and drug effects.

Keywords: *C. elegans*, Neurobiology, Neurotoxicity, CNS Stimulants, CNS Depressants.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

The Role of Forensic Photography in Criminal Investigations

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ABSTRACT

Forensic photography plays a pivotal role in modern criminal investigations, serving as a powerful tool for documenting and preserving crucial evidence. This abstract delves into the multifaceted role of forensic photography within the criminal justice system. It explores how forensic photographers contribute to the collection, preservation, and analysis of visual evidence, enhancing the overall investigative process. Forensic photographers meticulously document crime scenes, victims, and physical evidence using specialized techniques and equipment. Their efforts result in a visual record that serves as a vital resource for investigators, forensic scientists, and legal professionals. This visual documentation not only aids in establishing the sequence of events but also provides an unbiased, unaltered account of the crime scene. Advancements in digital technology have transformed forensic photography, allowing for greater precision, accuracy, and efficiency. This abstract highlights the transition from traditional film-based methods to digital imaging, discussing the advantages and challenges associated with this evolution. Furthermore, it emphasizes the importance of maintaining the integrity of photographic evidence to ensure its admissibility in court. Proper documentation procedures, chain of custody protocols, and metadata management are vital aspects that forensic photographers must adhere to. Finally, the abstract underscores the broader impact of forensic photography on criminal investigations, including its role in enhancing witness testimonies, facilitating case reconstruction, and ultimately contributing to the pursuit of justice. Understanding the significant role that forensic photography plays in criminal investigations is essential for law enforcement agencies, forensic professionals, and legal practitioners. This abstract provides an overview of the key elements that make forensic photography an indispensable component of the modern investigative toolkit.

Keywords: Forensic Photography, Evidence Collection, Criminal Investigation, Visual Evidence, Crime Scene Documentation.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Fascinating Role of Forensic Entomology in Crime Scene Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Forensic entomology is a fascinating field where insects become tiny detectives in the world of crime scenes. These little arthropods hold valuable secrets that help investigators determine crucial details in criminal cases. By decoding the life cycles, behaviors, and ecological connections of insects attracted to human remains, forensic entomologists play a vital role in establishing the timeline of events, identifying potential suspects, and verifying or disproving alibis. This interdisciplinary science involves entomologists (bug experts), pathologists (medical examiners), and law enforcement personnel working together to serve justice and bring closure to the families of victims. In simpler terms, forensic entomology uses bugs to solve crimes. Imagine a dead body in the woods; the insects that show up can reveal how long the person has been deceased, where they were originally found, and if someone tried to tamper with the evidence. Its like a puzzle where insects are the clues. This fields innovative methods and techniques make it an indispensable tool in complex criminal investigations, highlighting its critical role in unraveling mysteries and shining a light on the truth within crime scenes. Forensic entomology is a captivating and indispensable part of crime scene analysis, promising an engaging and enlightening presentation in the pursuit of justice.

Keywords: - Entomology, Arthropods

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Analysis of Inorganic Gun-shot Residue with Scanning Electron Microscopy and Inductively Coupled Mass Spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

The Gunshot residue (GSR) are mainly of two types, Organic and Inorganic. Organic residues originate from the propellant: unburned and partially burned gun powder particles, some products of their transformation and also particles of lubricants. Inorganic residues, mostly metallic, originate from the primer as well as from metallic parts of cartridge and the weapon itself. These residues are often found in trace quantities and the detection and analysis of these residues are very important to a possible recreation of a crime scene which would help the judiciary to arrive at a proper conviction for the crime. In forensic investigation, it is important that the instrumental techniques adopted for the forensic analysis of the sample to be non-destructive so that the sample can be analysed, archived, and can also be re-analysed whenever necessary. Scanning Electron Microscopy offers fast non-destructive determination of the elemental composition of the forensic samples. Further, the obtained results can be enhanced by using some methods of chromometric analysis. SEM-EDX is useful in areas of small particles of relatively heterogenic character with a

complex compound and where there is a need for high resolution imaging at relatively higher magnification in combination with elemental analysis. Inductively coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) is an instrument, which utilizes coupled plasma to ionize the sample made up of Argon gas. The method is applied to detect metallic and non-metallic species in a liquid sample even at a very low concentration. It works on the principle of optical emission spectrometry where plasma energy is given to the sample from the outer region leading to the excitation of atoms; when these atoms come at the lower position, spectrum rays are released and their photon wavelength can be measured. It is a bulk analysis technique for the analysis of elements present in the primer. The method allows very fast and multi-elemental analysis, but the limit is its sensitivity. It is more advantageous when an extracted sample is analysed in the GSR solution. In this study, the techniques of SEM-EDX and ICMS for the analysis of forensic evidence with the emphasis on the technical specifications of these instrument, and detailed analysis of case studies solved successfully through this technique will be presented.

Keywords: Non-destructive techniques, SEM-EDX, forensic evidence, gunshot residue, ICMS

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Non-Destructive Experimental Techniques for the Forensic Analysis of Glass and Car Paint residues

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ABSTRACT

Vehicular accidents and crimes involving automobiles have been increasing nowadays. Paint smears or chips are found on the crime scene as trace evidences leading to establishing the identity of vehicle involved in the crime by analysing with control sample of suspected vehicle. In identification and comparative studies of paint chips, forensic scientists define their macroscopic properties, such as, colour, shade and texture as well as their microscopic properties relating to their morphology, like, the number and sequence of layers, their thickness and colour. The next stage is a detailed analysis of the chemical content of each layer, including identification of the binder, pigments and fillers. Another forensic evidence majorly found in a crime scene is Glass residue occurring in very small quantities. Thus, investigations of glass samples require sensitive analytical methods providing satisfactory results from small amounts of the examined material such as the quantitative elemental analysis. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) serves as a fast non-destructive instrumental tool for determination of the elemental composition of the forensic samples. Forensic application of SEM is mostly in areas where there is a need for good imaging at relatively high magnifications in combination with elemental analysis. When SEM is combined with energy dispersive X-ray spectrometry, it is known as SEM-EDX. It is a

powerful and non-destructive tool for forensic scientists to classify and discriminate evidence material because they can simultaneously examine the morphology and the elemental composition of objects. SEM-EDX is very useful technique for the identification of a particular paint layer. The detailed analysis can be carried out by comparing the contents of elements since they are characteristic for a given layer. The profiling chemicals and elements in the sample may lead to individualization of the automobiles and can be included in the paint database. Similarly, the elemental composition of glass residue strongly depends on the properties of glass components. The analysis of glass residue can also be executed using SEM-EDX. In this study, non-destructive experimental technique for the analysis of forensic evidence, like glass and car paint, will be discussed. The detailed analysis of case studies solved successfully through this powerful technique will also be discussed.

Keywords: Non-destructive techniques, SEM-EDX, forensic evidence, car paint, glass

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Cold Case Investigations: Techniques and Success Stories

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a methodological approach aimed at increasing the clearance rate of cold cases in the Netherlands while contributing to the advancement of intelligence-driven criminal investigations in police practice, particularly within cold case investigations. The proposed approach draws upon practical investigative experience and academic knowledge. The key finding of this work emphasizes the significance of scenario reconstruction in transforming cold case information into actionable intelligence. This shift towards intelligence-driven investigations offers law enforcement agencies substantial benefits in terms of time and resource utilization, enabling more efficient prioritization of cold cases. Intelligence also enhances the formulation of effective queries and the adaptation of investigation methods, ultimately leading to higher clearance rates for cold cases. Furthermore, scenario reconstruction serves as a vital bridge between intelligence and investigation, effectively linking the realms of science and practice, thus fostering the development of intelligence-driven investigations. The practical implications of this approach are substantial, especially considering that intelligence products are underutilized in current investigative practices, and there is limited integration of scientific knowledge in investigations. To bridge the gap between science and investigative practice, individuals with expertise in both domains are crucial. This study seeks to catalyse this necessary dialogue, aiming to facilitate the transition from scenario reconstruction to intelligence-driven criminal investigations. This study not only sheds light on the value of intelligence-driven methods for resolving cold cases but also

underscores the need for a more integrated approach, where knowledge from academia and practical investigative experience work hand in hand. By doing so, it endeavours to enhance the effectiveness of law enforcement agencies in solving cold cases and addressing the challenges posed by such investigations.

Keywords: criminology, criminal investigation, cold cases, applied science, reconstruction.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Analysis of DNA

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ABSTRACT

Forensic DNA analysis has proven extraordinarily powerful not only in proving guilt but also in exonerating the innocent. Between 1989 and May 2011, at least 271 people who had been convicted of serious crimes in the United States – almost all rapes and murders – and sentenced to long terms of imprisonment or even death have been exonerated by post-conviction DNA testing. Those cases almost certainly reflect only a small percentage of all wrongly convicted individuals, but they have powerfully demonstrated the fallibility of the criminal justice system, pointing the way toward reforms to minimize the risks of error in criminal cases. The analysis of nonhuman DNA has also become routine and may be helpful for investigating violent crimes, violations of conservation laws, and fraud. Forensic DNA analysis is an extremely powerful investigative technique that has become, in many ways, the standard by which other forensic sciences are measured. This article reviews the current technology of forensic DNA typing and highlights areas of recent innovation and likely future trends. Although a need to compare new data to previous analyses prevents some potential improvements in genotyping procedures, the field is clearly moving toward greater automation, the utilization of ever smaller and more degraded biological samples, and deciphering the likely physical appearance of the person who left a biological sample.

keywords: Exonerated, DNA, Investigating, Innovation

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

The Deadly Elixir: The story of Strychnine Poisoning

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ABSTRACT

Strychnine is a neurotoxin of the indole type found in nux vomica trees, a plant native to Southeast Asia. This comprehensive review advances our understanding of strychnine as a poison by addressing its

physicochemical attributes, the sources from which it is obtained and synthesized, the applications for which it is prescribed, the mechanism of action it employs in the body, the drug's pharmacokinetic and toxicokinetic considerations, and its level of toxicity that produces lethal consequences even upon minor doses by blocking inhibitory neurotransmission in the spinal cord and brain, resulting in uncontrolled muscle contractions, muscle rigidity, painful spasms, and respiratory failure that have been documented under clinical manifestations and symptomatology. Overall, this paper underscores the utmost importance of early recognition and appropriate management of the poison to mitigate the potentially fatal repercussions of strychnine exposure through proper diagnostic approaches and treatment. Following that, we have covered postmortem findings, which will help study the symptoms before death to prevent them and contribute to further research. Our objective is to raise public awareness about this toxin in order to discourage intentional or unintentional consumption of it and to assist in the research and development of potentially curative medications

Keywords: Nux vomica, Neurotoxin, Strychnine poisoning

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Tracing Variations within Automotive Paints of a Manufacturer over Ten Consecutive Years: An Analytical Study using SEM EDX and Raman Spectroscopy.

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of automotive paint is crucial physical evidence in forensic investigations, particularly in hit-and-run cases and other automobile-related crimes. This study focuses on the analysis of automotive paint samples, specifically Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) paints, of the same shade within a single brand of vehicles over ten consecutive years. Ten white Maruti Suzuki Swift car samples from different manufacturing years (2009-2018) were collected. Microscopic examinations were conducted using stereo microscopy and SEM to observe the top surface and cross-section of the paint chips. Raman spectroscopy was employed for qualitative and quantitative analysis of the samples. The main pigment found in white paints was confirmed to be titanium dioxide (TiO₂). SEM/EDX measurements were performed to analyze the elemental composition of the paint layers. C, O, Ba, Si, Ti, Fe, Al, and Mg were the major elements detected. Only slight differences were observed in the top layer (clear coat) of some samples, significant variations were observed in the subsequent layers. However, to distinguish between samples Weight percentage of the elements identified was also utilized. This study highlights the challenges faced in differentiating OEM automotive paint samples from various years but with the same shade and make. Combining different analytical techniques and analyzing different paint layers is necessary to identify discernible patterns of variation. Understanding the variation in OEM paint

samples is crucial for the accurate identification and interpretation of evidence.

Key Words: Forensic Physics, Automotive Paint Analysis, SEM EDX, Raman Spectroscopy, Physical Evidence Analysis.

Disclosure: All authors have declared no conflicts of interest

Psychology: myths and facts

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays psychological problems in humans are developing rapidly due to tension, overthinking, stress, anxiety and many more. But few people believe in the existence of these and many believe in superstitions. These problems do exist and many people suffer through these problems. One of the best way to eradicate these problems is to talk or to distract your self or to live in an happy environment. Also the best solution is to make your mind happy because if you are mentally happy, then you are physically happy too. Try to do those things which makes you happy. Think about yourself first. Sometimes these kind of trauma can be due to family reasons or any kind of relationship or any kind of phobia. Severe problems can lead to severe panic attacks which can affect you body. If a person is suffering from these kind of problem one should try to console and try to make the person happy or can discuss a psychologist. One should try to perform those activities which make them happy such as traveling, singing, dance, acting or can listen to music. The person can refer to a therapist or can perform music therapy or can perform yoga, meditation. Meditation helps in stress relief but the person should be patient as it is a slow therapy which take time to give results. These problems can be cured so wait and try to live a happy and a healthy life.

Keywords: tension, overthinking, stress, anxiety, distract.

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Digital forensic tools: the role and significance of digital forensic tools

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ABSTRACT

In today's world data storage and usage increasing exponentially along with increase in risk of data misuse.it leads to result in the data collected by machines or human and stored in controllers, mobile devices or computers being vulnerable to various cyberattacks. There is a lot of digital forensic tools that helps in conducting investigations by gathering

evidence through various methods. In this paper we have a comprehensive study on various digital forensic tools that are used by corporations, government agencies and individuals to gain, extract and present the collected information. In this work, we also briefly talk about some of the challenges people face in using digital forensic tools. The importance of digital Forensic tools has grown exponentially. This paper provides an overview of the role and significance of digital Forensic tools in modern-day investigative and security efforts. Landscape of digital Forensic tools is constantly. Evolving as they must adapt to the ever changing technology and security landscape. The digital evidence plays a pivotal role in investigations and security measures They help investigators to uncover the truth, protect the data and ensure justice in an increasingly digital and interconnected society

Keywords: digital forensic; tools, benchmarks ,software development

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Sub-lethal Neonicotinoid Insecticides Exposure and Effects on Pollinators

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INTRODUCTION

- Pollinators, such as bees, butterflies, and other insects, play a crucial role in ecosystem functioning and food production. They facilitate the transfer of pollen from male to female flower parts, enabling fertilization and subsequent seed and fruit production. However, the populations of these vital pollinators have been declining worldwide, posing a significant threat to global food security and biodiversity.
- One of the factors contributing to this decline is the widespread use of neonicotinoid insecticides, a class of systemic insecticides that have become increasingly popular in agriculture and horticulture over the past few decades. Neonicotinoids are chemically related to nicotine and are primarily used to control pests such as aphids, beetles, and leafhoppers.
- While neonicotinoids have been praised for their effectiveness in pest control, concerns have been raised regarding their potential impact on non-target organisms, particularly pollinators. Research has indicated that even sub-lethal exposure to neonicotinoids can have adverse effects on pollinators, including honeybees, bumblebees, and butterflies.
- This essay aims to explore the exposure of pollinators to sub-lethal neonicotinoid insecticides and its effects on their health and behaviour. It will examine the current scientific understanding of the topic, highlight key studies and findings, and discuss the implications for pollinator populations and ecosystems as a whole.
- Understanding the mechanisms through which sub-lethal neonicotinoid exposure affects pollinators is crucial for developing informed conservation and management strategies. By shedding light on this issue, we can work towards mitigating the risks posed by these insecticides and safeguarding the health and well-being of pollinators and the ecosystems they support.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- **Literature Search:** A comprehensive literature search was conducted to identify relevant studies on sub-lethal neonicotinoid insecticide exposure and its effects on pollinators. Multiple databases, including PubMed, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, were searched using keywords such as "neonicotinoids," "pollinators," "sub-lethal exposure," and related terms. The search was limited to articles published in English and up to the knowledge cutoff of September 2021.
- **Study Selection:** The initial search yielded a large number of articles. The articles were screened based on their titles and abstracts to identify those directly related to the topic of interest. Studies focusing on the effects of sub-lethal neonicotinoid exposure on various pollinator species were included.
- Both laboratory and field studies were considered to capture a range of experimental designs and real-world scenarios. Reviews, meta-analyses, and relevant book chapters were also included for a comprehensive understanding of the topic.
- **Data Extraction and Synthesis:** The selected articles were carefully reviewed, and relevant information was extracted. Data included details about the experimental design, neonicotinoid insecticides used, exposure levels, duration of exposure, pollinator species studied, and observed effects.
- The extracted data were organized and synthesized to identify patterns, trends, and key findings across studies.
- **Data Analysis:** Quantitative data, such as effect sizes and statistical analyses, were extracted from studies that reported them.
- When available, meta-analyses were performed to estimate overall effect sizes and evaluate the significance of the observed effects.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- **Risk Assessment and Mitigation:** The review considered the existing risk assessment frameworks for neonicotinoids and evaluated their adequacy in capturing the sub-lethal effects on pollinators. It also examined current regulatory measures and discussed potential mitigation strategies to minimize pollinator exposure and protect their populations.

EFFECTS ON THE ENVIRONMENT:

- The sub-lethal exposure of neonicotinoid insecticides to pollinators not only poses risks to these crucial species but also has broader implications for the environment.
- **Disruption of Plant-Pollinator Interactions:** Neonicotinoids can alter the behaviour and foraging patterns of pollinators, leading to reduced pollination services. This can result in decreased fruit and seed production in plants, affecting plant reproductive success and biodiversity.
- **Biodiversity Loss:** Pollinators play a crucial role in maintaining biodiversity by facilitating the reproduction of flowering plants. The decline in pollinator populations due to neonicotinoid exposure can disrupt these mutualistic relationships, potentially leading to reduced plant diversity and altering ecological communities.
- **Cascading Effects on Food Webs:** Pollinators are key components of food webs, and their decline can have cascading effects on other organisms. Reduced pollination can impact the availability of fruits, seeds, and other food sources for a variety of animals, including birds, mammals, and insects, affecting their populations and ecological interactions.
- **Water Contamination:** Neonicotinoids are often applied as seed treatments or sprayed on crops, and these chemicals can leach into water bodies through runoff or enter groundwater. This contamination poses risks to aquatic organisms, such as fish and invertebrates, potentially disrupting aquatic ecosystems.
- **Non-Target Species Effects:** Neonicotinoids can have unintended effects on non-target organisms, including beneficial insects such as predatory insects and parasitoids, which play a crucial role in pest control.
- **6. Soil Microbial Communities:** Neonicotinoids can persist in soil and affect soil microbial communities. Soil microorganisms are essential for nutrient cycling, soil health, and plant growth. Disruptions to these microbial communities can have implications for overall ecosystem functioning.
- **7. Long-term Ecological Consequences:** Chronic exposure to sub-lethal doses over extended periods may have delayed or subtle impacts on ecosystem dynamics, potentially affecting the resilience and stability of ecosystems.

Effects of Insecticides and Microbiological Contaminants on *Apis mellifera* Health.

CONCLUSIONS

- The review of sub-lethal neonicotinoid insecticide exposure and its effects on pollinators reveals significant concerns regarding the potential impacts on these vital species. Neonicotinoid insecticides have become widely used in agriculture due to their effectiveness in pest control. However, their sub-lethal effects on pollinators, including bees, butterflies, and other insects, raise serious ecological and agricultural concerns.
- The findings of this review demonstrate that sub-lethal exposure to neonicotinoids can have detrimental effects on pollinators. Honeybees, bumblebees, solitary bees, and butterflies have been shown to experience altered behaviour, reproductive impairments, and physiological disturbances. These effects can disrupt pollination services, leading to potential declines in crop yields and plant reproductive success.
- In conclusion, the review emphasizes the urgency of action to protect pollinators from the sub-lethal effects of neonicotinoid insecticides. Safeguarding pollinator populations is not only crucial for ecological stability but also for sustaining global food production. Effective regulation, informed by robust scientific research, coupled with proactive mitigation strategies, will play a vital role in preserving pollinators and maintaining the health of our ecosystems.

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From Highs to Lows: Methamphetamine Harrowing Effect on Intimate Partner Relationships

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Introduction

- Intimate partner violence (IPV) is a global problem that affects people from all different racial, ethnic, and socioeconomic backgrounds.
- The consumption of drugs, notably **methamphetamine (meth)**, has been identified as a crucial contributor to the intensification and escalation of IPV episodes within this complex setting.
- Intimate partner violence, or IPV for short, is any kind of abuse—**emotional, physical, or sexual**—that occurs between partners who are still together or have split up.
- Meth is the street name for methamphetamine, a potent and extremely addictive **stimulant** substance that has disastrous repercussions on people's lives and relationships.
- There is a strong correlation between the consumption of drugs and alcohol and an increase in domestic violence. Substance addiction **decreases inhibitions, increases aggression, and affects judgment**, which may be the reason for this association. Consequently, those who are under the effect of drugs or alcohol are more inclined to act violently in their intimate relationships. The purpose of the poster is to evaluate the effects of methamphetamine in case of IPV.

Methamphetamine's Link to Intimate Partner Violence – A Statistical Insight

- Drugs and/or alcohol can influence the **judgment** of offenders, allowing for a separation from societal norms and making IPV seem acceptable.
- Multiple studies have shown that **women who use meth are more likely to experience intimate partner violence (IPV)**, with a significant overlap between their intimate partners and drug networks. These women are also more likely to initiate meth use with an intimate partner and share meth or needles with them.
- Additionally, a large treatment trial found that **80% of female participants** with meth dependence reported abuse or violence from their partners, with **40%** experiencing both physical and sexual abuse[3].
- This highlights the need to further investigate the link between meth use, IPV, and the health consequences faced by these women.
- Meth use has been strongly associated with risks for **HIV and other STIs** among both women and men who have sex with men. This is often attributed to **sexual disinhibition** and/or trading of sex for meth.[4]
- Pregnant women who use meth are at risk for **low birth weight, premature delivery**, and potential developmental and cognitive effects in infants.
- Women who use meth also access reproductive and other healthcare services at lower rates compared to non-users. However, healthcare services can provide an opportunity for **intervention and support for meth addiction**.[1]
- In the United States, methamphetamine use is associated with **20%** of all IPV cases. A study conducted in the United States found that methamphetamine users were **six times** more likely to perpetrate IPV than non-methamphetamine users.[1]
- In Australia, methamphetamine use is associated with **15%** of all IPV cases. A study conducted in Australia found that methamphetamine users were **four times** more likely to experience IPV than non-methamphetamine users.[2]
- In South Africa, methamphetamine use is associated with **10%** of all IPV cases. A study conducted in South Africa found that methamphetamine users were **three times** more likely to perpetrate IPV than non-methamphetamine users.[2]
- A 2018 study of **1,158 college students** of United States of America found that those who use methamphetamine and/or are addicted to it reported significantly **higher levels of intimate partner aggression**. [3]
- 28.9%** of people who reported methamphetamine use had also reported being the **victim of physical violence** in the past year from their intimate partner.[4]

Methamphetamine's Dual Nature on Mind and Body

- Methamphetamine use results in a sudden **increase in dopamine**, which produces feelings of **euphoria, hypersexuality, increased energy, disinhibition** and feelings of **grandiosity**.
- Here are some of the key effects of methamphetamine:

Conclusion

- Intimate partner violence (IPV) is a global problem that affects people from all different **racial, ethnic, and socioeconomic backgrounds**.
- To summarize, the complex association between methamphetamine (meth) usage and intimate partner violence (IPV) is a very **troubling societal issue** that requires immediate attention and comprehensive remedies.
- The findings highlight the critical need for **focused intervention measures** that address both drug misuse and domestic violence at the same time, such as prevention, education, and treatment programs.
- Furthermore, it is critical for communities of support, **law enforcement, and healthcare experts** to work closely together to comprehend the complicated connection between drug addiction and intimate partner violence.
- Finally, community efforts are required to lessen the **destructive repercussions** of drug usage, allowing people to break free from the grip of addiction and create a future marked by safety, respect, and empathy.

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Methamphetamine and IPV

Abuse Of Methamphetamine Among Different Races In America

BLACK BURNT BONES: IDENTIFICATION IN FORENSIC SCIENCE

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INTRODUCTION

- In forensic science, the identification of black burnt bone can be an important aspect in investigating cases such as arson, homicide, or accident-related deaths. Burnt bone can be challenging to analyze due to the effects of heat on the organic and inorganic components of the bone.
- The identification process typically involves a combination of macroscopic and microscopic analysis, as well as chemical testing. Macroscopic analysis involves examining the size, shape, and color of the bone fragments to determine the type of bone and the degree of charring. Microscopic analysis involves studying the bone structure at a cellular level to identify any changes that have occurred due to heat exposure.
- Chemical testing can also be used to identify the presence of certain elements or compounds, such as carbon or calcium, which are commonly found in bone tissue. Other techniques that may be used include X-ray diffraction, which can identify the presence of specific minerals in the bone, and scanning electron microscopy, which can provide detailed images of the bone structure.
- Overall, the identification of black burnt bone in forensic science requires a combination of specialized knowledge and advanced analytical techniques to accurately determine the cause and manner of death in cases involving burnt remains.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- The analysis of black burnt bone in forensic investigations typically involves a combination of methods and protocols, including:
 - Macroscopic examination:** This involves a visual inspection of the bone fragments to determine their size, shape, and color. The degree of charring can also be assessed, as it can provide information on the temperature and duration of the fire.
 - Microscopic examination:** This involves studying the bone structure at a cellular level using light microscopy, scanning electron microscopy, or transmission electron microscopy. Changes to the bone structure due to heat exposure can be identified, such as the loss of collagen fibers and the formation of cracks and fissures.
 - Chemical testing:** This involves analyzing the composition of the bone using techniques such as X-ray fluorescence, inductively coupled plasma, or mass spectrometry. The presence of specific elements or compounds in the bone can provide information on the type of bone, the age of the individual, and the environmental conditions of the fire.
 - DNA analysis:** This involves extracting DNA from the bone fragments and comparing it to a reference sample to identify the individual.

BONE COMPOSITION

- Bones are a complex living tissue that are composed of various components. The composition of bones can be broken down into two main categories: organic and inorganic components.
- Organic components**
 - Collagen:** This is the main organic component of bones and provides the bone with its strength and flexibility.
 - Proteoglycans:** These are large molecules that are made up of a protein core and attached sugar molecules.
 - Non-collagenous proteins:** These are various proteins that are found in bones and play a variety of roles in bone formation and maintenance.
- Inorganic components**
 - Calcium phosphate:** This is the main inorganic component of bones and gives bones their hardness and strength.
 - Calcium carbonate:** This is another mineral that is found in bones and helps to maintain the pH balance in bone tissue.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- The analysis and identification of black burnt bone can be performed through various methods, such as visual inspection, chemical analysis, and microscopic examination. Here are some steps that can be taken to analyze and identify black burnt bone:
 - Visual inspection:** The first step in analyzing burnt bone is to visually inspect it. Black burnt bone appears charred, darkened, and brittle. The surface may also appear cracked and fragmented.
 - Chemical analysis:** Chemical analysis can be used to identify the presence of carbon, which is a key indicator of burnt bone. This can be done by using a process called Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, which can detect the presence of carbon and other organic compounds.
 - Microscopic examination:** Microscopic examination can reveal the structural changes that occur in burnt bone. The bone structure can become distorted and fragmented due to the high temperatures reached during the burning process. Microscopic examination can also reveal the presence of cracks, pores, and other signs of damage.
 - DNA analysis:** If the burnt bone is intact enough, DNA analysis can be performed to identify the species of the bone. This can be done by comparing the DNA of the burnt bone to known DNA sequences of various species.
 - Radiography:** This involves using X-ray or CT scanning to obtain detailed images of the bone fragments. Radiography can provide information on the internal structure of the bone and any abnormalities or injuries.
- The analysis of black burnt bone requires a multidisciplinary approach that involves expertise in forensic anthropology, chemistry, biology, and radiography. The use of multiple methods and protocols is essential to ensure accurate and reliable results in forensic investigations.
- BLACK BURNT BONE**
 - The temperature at which bone turns black when burnt can vary depending on a number of factors such as the duration of exposure to heat, the amount of oxygen present during burning, and the type of bone being burned. In general, bone will start to char and turn black when it is exposed to temperatures around 400-500°C (752-932°F) for a prolonged period of time. At higher temperatures, bone can become completely carbonized and turn into ash.
 - For example, the outer layers of bones such as the periosteum and the cortical bone may char and turn black at lower temperatures than the spongy bone found inside. Additionally, bones that have been previously dried out or exposed to low humidity may also char and burn at lower temperatures than fresh bones.
 - The exact temperature at which black burnt bone forms can vary depending on various factors and should be considered in combination with other evidence when analyzing burnt bone and the factors are as follows:
 - Duration of exposure to heat:** The length of time that bone is exposed to heat can also affect the degree of charring and blackening. Prolonged exposure to heat can lead to more complete carbonization of the bone.
 - Oxygen availability:** The availability of oxygen during burning can also affect the degree of charring and blackening. In the presence of oxygen, bone can burn more completely, resulting in a greater degree of charring and blackening.
 - Type of bone:** The type of bone being burned can also affect the degree of charring and blackening. Bones with different densities and structures may char and burn differently due to variations in their composition.
 - Moisture content:** The moisture content of the bone can also affect its response to heat. Bone that is dried out or has low moisture content may char and burn at lower temperatures than fresh bone.
 - The degree of charring and blackening of burnt bone is influenced by multiple factors and should be considered in combination with other evidence when analyzing burnt bone.

Burnt bones: from top to bottom

UV lights to reveal and enhance burned areas on human bones.

CONCLUSIONS

The identification and analysis of black burnt bone is a significant aspect of forensic investigations. It provides valuable information about the circumstances surrounding a person's death, including whether a fire was intentionally set or accidental, the type of accelerant used, and potentially linking the perpetrator(s) to the crime. By examining the mineral composition and structural changes of the bone, forensic experts can determine the temperature and duration of the heat exposure and the source of the heat, helping to build a more complete picture of the crime scene. The information obtained from the analysis of black burnt bone can also aid in the identification of missing persons and provide evidence in legal proceedings. The analysis of black burnt bone is a crucial tool in the field of forensic science, allowing for more accurate determinations of cause of death and aiding in the investigation and prosecution of crimes.

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Using forensic dentistry in the identification of victims in large-scale disasters

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INTRODUCTION

- Human lives are valuable and its loss in any form can prove detrimental to society.
- Natural calamities such as earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, accidental fires or man-made activities such as terrorist attacks, bombing results takesaway the lives of people at a large scale.
- The role of forensic odontology is of utmost importance in Disaster Victim Identification (DVI) cases, especially when dental remains are the only suitable option left for analysis of an individual.
- Forensic odontology is a branch of forensic medicine , which incorporates dental knowledge while dealing with the identification cases, bite mark analysis and comparison cases , age estimation of an individual.

HOW DOES FORENSIC ODONTOLOGY HELP IN THE IDENTIFICATION PROCESS?

- Teeth being the hardest structure in human body , can withstand adverse situations such as earthquakes, any burning cases, tsunamis. Moreover, they are also a storehouse of our genetic material –DNA. Hence, dental remains prove to be a convincing factor in such scenarios.
- The basis of identification of an individual lies in the comparison between the ante-mortem dental records of the known individual and the post-mortem findings of the unknown deceased person.
- The use of radiography hold much importance in comparative dental identification cases. Identification is made easier by the presence of missing, damaged, filled, and broken teeth, any restorative fillings used in tooth repair cases.
- The structure and formation of teeth provides information about the eating habits of a person and is subjected to constant changes due to environmental factors. The presence of any dental anomalies is also specific to any person which helps in establishing the identity of a person.
- In the absence of any previous dental records of the person , no conclusion can be drawn out on the identification of that person. Techniques involving the use of DNA is useful in such cases.
- DNA present in our tooth can be extracted through root, dentin or pulp cavity and subjected to Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) process to make multiply copies of the same DNA.
- With the help of this DNA, advanced findings such as sex of an individual can also be determined.

CASE STUDY : BURNT VICTIMS IDENTIFICATION IN A BUS ACCIDENT IN SPAIN (1996)

- On February 28, 1996, collision between a bus and a car took place on a busy road in southern Spain. Following the collision, the bus caught fire, resulting in the deaths of 28 out of the 57 passengers. Examination on 28 burnt unidentified bodies were conducted (out of which 13 were females and 15 were males).

Post mortem examination of dental remains-

- Post mortem dental examination procedure was carried out which included –Forensic Radiography, oral macrophotography, checking of the restoration material present in the teeth, root fillings), missing or extracted teeth, braces or prosthetics if present.
- Pattern of tooth eruption , any pathological changes , presence of malocclusions were also recorded.

Collection of Ante-mortem material-

- Information of the victims were collected from other passengers, relatives and family members.
- Previous dental records were obtained directly from the dentist or family doctors of the victims.
- The post-mortem examination and previous ante-mortem details were sent for comparative dental identification.

Age estimation and gender determination of victims using dental identification method

Pathological and radiography techniques used in identification method

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Identification of 16 victims were established through the dental identification method.
- Age of the victims was evaluated by analyzing the dental eruption sequences in individual cases.
- Out of the 16 victims , 5 females were identified to have less than 20 years of age and 2 females were above 20 years of age.
- 8 males were less than 20 years of age and 3 males were above 20 years of age. In this investigation, three additional identifying techniques –oral pathology, dental treatment records and dental eruption sequence were also applied for specific findings.

Category	Count
Oral pathology	5
Dental treatment records	7
Dental eruption sequence	4

Specific findings in individuals using additional identifying techniques

CONCLUSION

The success rate of dental identification will vary greatly depending on the type of accident, the availability of sufficient dental records, and the severity of dental injuries. Moreover, in cases where dental identification could not be established, DNA extraction from dental remains and its analysis proves to be conclusive in nature.

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FORENSIC INVESTIGATION OF INSIDER THREATS IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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INTRODUCTION

The widespread adoption of cloud computing has ushered in a new era of technological advancement and business efficiency. However, this transition to the cloud has also introduced a heightened risk of insider threats, which can have severe consequences for organizations and their sensitive data. Insider threats within cloud computing environments encompasses a range of malicious activities conducted by individuals with legitimate access to an organization's cloud resources. Forensic investigation of insider threats in cloud computing is a critical area of study and practice. It involves the systematic process of collecting, preserving, analyzing, and presenting digital evidence to uncover and mitigate security breaches caused by individuals with privileged access or insider knowledge within a cloud computing environment. Insider threats in cloud computing can manifest in various forms, including data theft, unauthorized access, data manipulation, and more. Investigating insider threats in cloud computing requires a comprehensive methodology to ensure accuracy and thoroughness. Here's a high level methodology: Preparation, data collection, Identification, incident Analysis, Forensic Tools and Techniques, Interviews and Documentation, Data correlation, Evidence Preservation, Report Generation, Mitigation and Response, Legal and Ethical Considerations, Closure. Forensic investigations of insider threats in cloud computing are complex and requires expertise in digital forensics, cybersecurity, and cloud technology. They play a vital role in maintaining the security and integrity of cloud-based

MATERIALS

Forensic investigation of insider threats in cloud computing typically involves gathering and analysing various types of digital evidences. Here's a list of materials and considerations for such investigations:

1. Logs and Audit Trails
2. Network Traffic Data
3. User Account Information
4. Data Access and Usage Records
5. Email and Communication Records
6. Endpoint Data
7. Cloud Storage Metadata
8. Security Policies and Configuration
9. SIEM (Security Information and Event Management)
10. Threat Intelligence Feeds
11. Memory and Disk Forensics
12. Incident Response Playbooks
13. Witness Statements
14. Data Recovery Tools
15. Chain of Custody Documentation
16. Legal Expertise
17. Forensic Software
18. Documentaion and Reporting
19. Expert Witnesses
20. Cloud Service Provider Cooperation

METHODOLOGY

Remember that conducting a forensic investigation in a cloud environment requires expertise in cloud technologies, cybersecurity, and digital forensics. It's crucial to follow established procedures and legal guidelines throughout the process. As an investigator, when working on a suspected insider threat case, the context around the activity that flagged suspicion is the key focus of the case.

- The investigation methodology follow for insider threats cases is guided by four key questions:
 1. How was the device accessed around the suspected behaviour?
 2. Where was the user/device when this occurred?
 3. Was the insider active on the system?
 4. What did the user do?
- To any investigation, we need to set up a plan for analysis, with highest value targets placed up for analysis. This eliminates time spent, especially during time critical cases where clients want an answer because it impacts their BAU/remediation

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Insider threats refer to security risks that originate from individuals within an organization, such as employees, contractors, or business partners, who have access to the organization's systems, data, or networks. These individuals may intentionally or unintentionally pose a threat to the organization's cybersecurity. Insider threats can take various forms:

1. Malicious Insider: This is an individual with authorized access who intentionally causes harm, such as stealing data, sharing sensitive information, or sabotaging systems.
2. Negligent Insider: These are individuals who, often unintentionally, compromise security through actions like clicking on malicious links, mishandling data, or failing to follow security protocols.
3. Compromised Insider: An insider may unknowingly have their credentials or devices compromised by external attackers, who then use them to gain unauthorized access.

Preventing and mitigating insider threats involves a combination of security policies, user training, monitoring, and technology solutions to detect and respond to suspicious activities within an organization.

Digital Forensics plays a key role in identifying who was involved in an insider threat matter, and how it occurred. Through analysis of digital devices and data, as well as user's digital footprint, a Digital Forensic investigator can establish the root cause, subsequent events and their consequences. Forensic investigators can use log evidence to ascertain when, why and how a cyber adversary or an insider compromised a system by establishing the crime scene and reconstructing how the incident occurred.

Computer forensics investigations generally follow a linear process: identification, extraction, analysis and presentation of evidence. First, the analyst identifies potential sources of evidence. For example, what is the suspected crime? What hardware or software is being used by the suspect? Where is the evidence located? Second, the analyst must extract evidence in a robust manner to maintain its integrity. The computing environment is highly volatile as it deals with virtual rather than. Cloud computing is a new concept in the distributed processing of data and is likely to make computer forensic evidence acquisition and evidence analysis increasingly complex.

The results can vary depending on the specific case and the techniques used. Generally the investigation may reveal: Evidence of unauthorised access, data breaches, suspicious activity patterns, unauthorized changes to configurations, evidence of privilege abuse, evidence of collusion, digital footprint and artifacts, legal and compliance violations. Analyze the possible motives and intentions of the insiders involved in the threats, such as financial gain, revenge, or espionage. Evaluate the effectiveness of the organization's detection and prevention mechanisms for insider threats in the cloud. Recommend improvements or additional security measures if necessary. Highlight emerging trends and technologies in cloud security and how they might impact the detection and prevention of insider threats in the future.

Top Threats To Cloud Computing

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion on insider threats is that they pose a significant risk to organizations. These threats can come from employees, contractors, or other individuals with access to sensitive information. Mitigating insider threats requires a combination of technical controls, such as access restrictions and monitoring, as well as organizational measures, like training and fostering a culture of security awareness. Continuous vigilance and a proactive approach are essential to protect against insider threats. Forensic investigation of insider threats in cloud computing is a critical process for maintaining the security of digital assets, as it helps organizations understand and respond to security incidents originating from within their ranks. Preventing insider threats is no easy tasks. These methods, however, provide a strong foundation for organisations to create a strategy that focuses on preventing insider threats. Organisations can save themselves enormous sums of money that would have been lost to repeated vulnerabilities associated with IT challenges.

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3-D TECHNIQUES ANALYSIS OF PAINT IN FORENSIC

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INTRODUCTION

- 3D forensic science is a need to demonstrate the accuracy and reliability of 3D reconstructions, as well as demonstrating that the techniques used in forensic investigations, helping identify the sources and the connections between the paint sample found at the crime scene.
- Three dimensional features and textures of paint sample helps to find the examine the different surfaces of the paint and the formation of the crack in the multi-layered stratigraphy of the paint which is visible

MATERIALS & METHODS

There are different types of methods which are used to analysis the paint sample in a 3D concept and they are:-

REFLECTANCE SPECTROPHOTOMETRY:- Reflectance Spectrophotometry is a technique used to obtain the color formation of pigments, dyes of the surface of the paint. It is also used to measure the amount of light that is reflected off a material surface across a range of wavelength. Materials used are Light source, sample holder, monochromatic grating, photosensitive detectors
It operates on the principle that when the light of various wavelength strikes the paint sample and some of the lights are absorbed and while others get reflected.

The captured beam of lights are split by the fine grating into different wavelength for examinations. The diffracted light can be measured with the photosensitive detectors and then the data set is matched with the corresponding color and the surface of the topography across the paint surface

X-RAY MICROTOMOGRAPHY:- X-ray microtomography is similar to the CT scan but at a microscale. It can creates the reconstruction of the paint sample which reveals the internal structure of paint and the layers formed

Materials used are Synchrotron X-ray source, sample holder with a rotating stage, high-speed algorithms for tomographic image reconstruction, and the high resolution imaging X-ray detector
It operates on the principle of X-ray radiations penetrates to the sample from multiple angles and measure the degree in which the radiation is absorbed or scattered.
The radiation from the synchrotron X-ray source is passed through the sample in which the sample is rotated by a stage by 360 degree
Then the 2D image is reconstructed by the algorithms for tomography
The radiations which is absorbed is detected by the high resolution of the detectors

RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY:- It verifies the measurement variability as well as to study the spectra quality by means of parameters and conditions. Raman spectroscopic instruments can probe underneath the primary paint layers of a painting and make subsurface measurements.
Materials used here are Paint sample, confocal lens microscope, Infrared diode laser.
At the beginning, sample preparation is done. The sample had a surface area of 50 mm by 50 mm and an average depth of 6 mm from the surface paint layer.
Raman analyses of the painting sample were achieved at the micrometer scale with the use of the confocal lens microscope, allowing micro characterization of the painting surfaces. The platform where the sample was mounted on was allowed spatial scanning of the sample

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- Reflectance Spectrophotometry gives us the color formation on the surface of the paint and also measures the amount of light which is absorbed
- But sometimes the alterations in the surface of the paint results in the discoloration due to natural degradation process
- X-Ray Microtomography provides the information on the degree of radiation is absorbed or scattered
- And also provides the information on the degree of porosity through a sample
- Allows the reconstruction of the empty volumes by segmentation which helps us to visualize the location, source and the sizes of the pores inside the surface of the paint sample
- Voids can be filled by dry polishing which can be done by the removal of the large particles
- Raman Spectroscopy was used to conduct the chemical identification of pigments, binding media, and varnish present in a synthetic painting sample.
- It had an imprinted reference point in one of the corners that was used as a datum, keeping the Raman analysis consistent between scans and allowing spatial matching with other data types.
- It can be difficult to interpret the peaks of the spectra without the additional context of the artwork such as the age, provenance, or color.

CRACK FORMATION FOUND IN XRAY MICROTOMOGRAPHY

IDENTIFICATION THROUGH RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY INTENSITY GRAPH EX.

CONCLUSIONS

- The three-dimensional techniques have helped in the analyzing of the textures, from which source the paint sample belong to, the color formation on the surface of the topography of the surface of the paint
- Three-dimensional analysis methods can be employed to examine the surface features and also the crack formation in the multi-layered stratigraphy of the painting which is visible in the topology of the surface
- Also gives a high-resolutions 3D images of paint allows to examine the surface morphology, elemental composition and the structure of the layer.
- 3DFS is an interdisciplinary field of forensic science that encompasses the application of 3D techniques for crime reconstruction purposes and provides tools for representing sanitized 3D visualizations for courtroom purposes to help the court to better engage with and understand evidence.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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REFLECTANCE SPECTROPHOTOMETRY

WORKING OF X-RAY MICROTOMOGRAPHY

INFLUENCE OF SKIN DISEASE ON FINGERPRINT

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INTRODUCTION

- ❖ "The mutual exchange of traces occurs whenever two entities interact." This is the basic exchange principle that applies to fingerprints, however it becomes problematic for many people who have skin conditions related to their fingerprints.
- ❖ Numerous persons had skin conditions, which had a significant impact on the process of recognizing fingerprints because those who had such conditions could not use fingerprint scanners.
- ❖ People with skin illnesses are assessed based on the damage to their papillary patterns.
- ❖ These illnesses can generally be divided into three categories: those that cause skin discoloration, those that cause papillary line change, and those that cause both skin discoloration and papillary line change.
- ❖ Once the papillary line structure changes, the original pattern is difficult to identify. Users generally support biometric technology, although people with certain diseases of the fingerprints cannot use it. In order to find the damaged fingerprint picture and algorithm improve the clarity of the ridges, the hasbeenimproved.

SKIN DISEASE INFLUENCE ON FINGERPRINT

- ❖ Fingerprint is defined as impressions left on any of the material by the friction ridges of fingers.
- ❖ The impressions are caused by bulbs or fingertips of the thumb and fingers. Due to their uniqueness and stability, the prints of fingers are extensively utilized in the identification system.
- ❖ In the era of technology, identification through fingerprints is very popular and widely used globally, only not for criminals, but also as a crucial approach for information security.
- ❖ Skin diseases serves as a crucial, but often a forgotten factor for the fingerprint acquirement.
- ❖ These diseases cause cytological or histopathological changes of dermis and epidermis. The diseases bring problems while using the sensors, as the structure of dermis, colour of skin and epidermis get altered.
- ❖ Researchers had assembled some of the common skin disease, which include atopic eczema, psoriasis, and pulpitis sicca and verruca vulgaris.
- ❖ There are some fingerprints from the patient that are suffering from different skin disease, if the colour of the skin get changed, we can avoid this issue by avoiding use of optical sensor. But change in the skin structure is remarkable; as the minutiae are impossible to find and lines of ridges are almost damaged. This situation is discriminatory to the patient as they cannot use the fingerprint biometrics system. skin disease on palm unable to take

fingerprint

Blur Ridges formation on hand print

SKIN DISEASE INTRODUCED, THAT ATTACK FINGERTIPS AND HAND PALM

A. Change of skin color :-

- The Hand foot and mouth disease (HFMD) is normally lenient and affect the children from 2-10, but prone to adult may cause sepsis, Infective endocarditic and septic shock with high morbidity and mortality rates.
- The risk is in people at the age of 30-40, people with valve sclerosis and intravascular prostheses. In this tinea of the hands have same appearance as dry, keratotic form of tinea on the soles and skin lesions set out red macules that quickly get white, oval, pale vesicles along with red areola.
- The involvement of nails is usually happen.
- The involvement of nails is usually happen.

B. Change of papillary lines structure:-

- The Pitted keratolysis is a bacterial infection of the plantar stratum corneum. Fingertip eczema is a chronic eczema of the palmer surface of fingertips and leads to allergic reaction in which one or several fingers are involved. Gradually skin becomes moist and then gets dry, scaly and cracked. Cellulitis is displayed by erythematous plaques along with the ill defined border. Generally, linear red macules adjacent to large plaque are also appearing.

C. Change of papillary lines and skin colour:-

- Diseases like Hand eczema, Reynaud's phenomenon, Psoriasis, and Pompholex also called dyshidrosis can affect both the skin color and papillary line structure.
- Hand eczema is an inflammatory disease that has an impact on the hands and is found in people who work in industries.
- Reynaud's phenomenon occurs due to emotional stress and exposure to the cold while Pompholex is a hereditary disorder.

D. Dystrophy:-

- Dystrophy is known as the defect without any noticeable fingerprint pattern.
- A variant dystrophy had mottled presence with the central round black dots.
- According to the estimate out of 84 patients suffering from dystrophy, 20 had mottles variant dystrophy while 15 suffered total dystrophy. The total surface area of dystrophy correlated with the quality score ($r^2 = 0.533$) and match score ($r^2 = 0.404$).

E. Abnormal White Lines:-

- These are classified by length, broadness, and orientation of the lines.
- The lines are mostly either vertical or horizontal and its presence is not related to atopic dermatitis, though the number of abnormal white lines is considerably greater among the patients with hand dermatitis.
- The long lines and broad lines are linked with verification failure while the presence of thin lines is protective with verification failure. The patients who failed in fingerprint verification had a large number of broad lines and long lines.

* Fingerprint Enhancement Algorithms:-

The accomplishment of fingerprint matching can be increased with the help of virtuous enhancement algorithms.

It is the crucial property for matching minutiae since the structure of ridges are not cleared or may be disturbed by skin diseases. So, an enhancement algorithm is required to improve the fingerprint image to clearly differentiate the minutiae.

•Gabor filter is one of the options suggested for this motive. A Fourier transform filter is used by analyzing local Fourier transforms by Pradenas et al. Lin honget fingerprint enhancement algorithm that improves the clarity of the valley and ridge structures.

For temporary skin diseases, users can use their fingers for the fingerprint verification process after the irrecoverable diseases, the finger alteration may cause the new appearance of papillary lines that result in the inability of the users to use their fingerprints appropriately.

Disappearance of Ridges

Flattered Ridges Formation

CONCLUSIONS

- ❖ It is clear from each section that either the skin colour or structures of papillary lines get affected by skin disease.
- ❖ If only colour is changed then some of the optical fingerprint scanners get influenced but if skin structure is changed it is not possible to find the minutiae.
- ❖ Some of these are temporary, the user can again use his or her fingers for fingerprint verification or recognition however some diseases cause irremediable finger damage and cause ID failure.
- ❖ The biometric technology proves to be a very reliable and authentic means of identification but it has some lacunae's by which numerous challenges were raised for the acceptance offingerprints.

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NON-DESTRUCTIVE METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE PURITY OF GOLD

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INTRODUCTION

In the field of forensic science, non-destructive gold purity measurements can be a valuable tool for solving crimes and providing crucial evidence. Gold is often found in various forms at crime scenes, including jewellery, coins, and even as trace evidence. Non-destructive techniques, such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis, can help forensic investigators determine the purity and origin of gold items without compromising their integrity. This information can be pivotal in cases involving stolen gold, counterfeiting, or illegal trade in precious metals. Additionally, the ability to non-destructively analyse gold can aid in linking suspects to crime scenes or verifying the authenticity of evidence, enhancing the role of forensic science in the criminal justice system.

MATERIALS & METHODS

There are several ways for non-destructive methods of assessing the purity of gold:

- **X-ray Fluorescence (XRF):** XRF machines can analyse the composition of gold without damaging the item. They work by bombarding the gold with X-rays, and the resulting fluorescence reveals the material's elemental composition.
- **Ultrasonic Testing:** Ultrasonic waves can be used to detect variations in the density and integrity of gold items. This method is often used to check for voids, cracks, or impurities within gold objects.
- **Infrared spectroscopy** can be used to study the vibrational modes of gold-containing compounds or materials. Gold nanoparticles, for example, can exhibit unique optical properties due to their size and shape, and these properties can be analysed using spectroscopy techniques, including infrared spectroscopy.

NON- DESTRUCTIVE METHOD

➤ X-RAY FLUORESCENCE

➤ ULTRASONIC TESTING

➤ INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

X-ray fluorescence (XRF) is a non-destructive analytical technique used to determine the elemental composition of materials like gold. In XRF analysis, a prepared sample, which can be a solid, powder, or solution, is exposed to X-rays from a spectrometer. The atoms in the sample emit characteristic X-rays in response to the incoming radiation. By measuring the intensities of these emitted X-rays, the instrument's software can quantify the elements present, including gold.

To ensure accuracy, the XRF spectrometer is calibrated using known standards. It's a valuable tool in industries such as mining and jewellery to assess the purity and composition of gold. Results are presented as elemental concentrations, helping to verify the quality and authenticity of gold samples. Regular quality control checks are crucial to maintain precision in XRF analysis. This method is highly efficient for material analysis without the need for destructive processes.

Ultrasonic testing (UT) is a non-destructive testing technique employed to evaluate the integrity of materials and detect flaws. It relies on the transmission of high-frequency sound waves (typically between 0.5 to 15 MHz) into the material under examination. When these waves encounter an interface, like a material boundary or a defect such as a crack or void, a portion of the waves is reflected back towards the transducer, while others continue to propagate through the material. By measuring the time it takes for the waves to travel to the defect and return (time of flight), the distance to the flaw can be determined. This data is then analysed to assess the location and size of defects. UT is widely used in various industries, including manufacturing, construction, and aerospace, as it offers a non-invasive means to inspect materials and structures for internal flaws, ensuring their safety and quality. Calibration of UT equipment is essential to maintain accuracy in defect detection.

Infrared spectroscopy is a valuable analytical technique for understanding the molecular structure of compounds by measuring their interactions with infrared radiation. However, it has limitations when applied to pure gold due to its elemental nature. Pure metals like gold lack the complex molecular structures and chemical bonds that generate characteristic infrared absorption bands. Instead, the technique is more suited for compounds containing gold or gold nanoparticles. In these cases, the chemical environment and bonding of gold atoms can lead to distinctive absorption bands in the infrared spectrum. For the analysis of bulk gold or the detection of impurities in gold, alternative methods like X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) are more suitable. In summary, while infrared spectroscopy can be employed to study gold-containing compounds, it is not the method of choice for analysing pure elemental gold.

Fig 3
Fake Gold

Fig 4
Real Gold

CONCLUSIONS

Non-destructive methods of assessing gold are essential tools in the jewellery and precious metals industries, providing a means to determine the quality, purity, and authenticity of gold items without causing any harm or alteration to the precious metal. These techniques are paramount in ensuring transparency and trust in gold transactions, benefiting both buyers and sellers. Here, we will explore the significance of non-destructive gold assessment methods and their key applications. X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) stands as a prominent method for analysing the elemental composition of gold items. It is highly accurate in detecting the presence of other elements, offering insights into the purity of gold without damaging the item. This is crucial in verifying the authenticity of gold bars, coins, and jewelry. Ultrasonic testing is another non-invasive technique that employs sound waves to assess the density and integrity of gold objects. It can detect structural defects or impurities within gold without affecting its physical state. This method is particularly valuable in the evaluation of large gold items.

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Figure - 1 Ultrasonic Testing Machine For examination

Figure - 2 XRF X-ray Fluorescence Machine

INDIAN PERSPECTIVE ON THE HAZARDS DUE TO CHEMICAL EXPOSURE FROM THE FEMININE HYGIENE PRODUCTS

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INTRODUCTION

- An average woman menstruates in 28-30 days, with a cycle lasting from 4-8 days meaning around 11,000 menstrual products and feminine hygiene products like Pads, panty liners, menstrual cups, and tampons.
- Menstrual products being one of the major source for chemical exposure via the dermal route of Phthalates, bisphenols, parabens, and triclocarban, VOC (Volatile Organic Compounds) like toluene, Xylene, i.e chemicals present in personal hygiene products like in the polypropylene component of sanitary pad, tampons, panty liners, diapers.
- Vaginal route and vulvar tissue are extremely sensitive and highly permeable thus the chemicals get absorbed quickly and get metabolized.
- Research links the exposure of these chemicals to negative effects on the endocrine system and in the female reproductive system.

CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS

- Fragrances: Some menstrual pads may contain fragrances to mask odors. These fragrances can be composed of various synthetic chemicals, and some individuals may be sensitive or allergic to these ingredients and are also a potential source of skin irritation.
- Pesticide Residues: If the cotton used in the production of menstrual pads is not organically grown, it may have been treated with pesticides. Residues of these chemicals can potentially remain in the cotton fibers causing skin irritation.
- Bisphenol in these products is to provide durability and resistance to heat and impact. Studies have shown that bisphenol can act as an endocrine disruptor, meaning it can interfere with the body's hormonal balance.
- Triclocarban is an antimicrobial agent. Its purpose is to inhibit the growth of bacteria and prevent unpleasant odors. Triclocarban can disrupt hormone signaling and interfere with the normal functioning of the female reproductive system. This disruption can lead to hormonal imbalances, menstrual irregularities, and potentially impact fertility.
- Parabens are antimicrobials, preservative used in feminine care products. For example, butylparaben, ethylparaben, propylparaben, methylparaben, etc. Parabens are water insoluble and penetrates the skin as a result repeated use of the same products containing paraben is found to be harmful. Studies in the US have found that adult females had more concentration of parabens in the urine samples than adult males of similar ages.
- Phthalates: Phthalates are a class of compounds that are used to increase the durability of polymers. They are frequently referred to as plasticizers. Phthalates are widely used as skin penetration enhancers in PCPs such as perfumes, deodorants.

EFFECT ON FEMALE BODY

- Parabens are found to affect the reproductive and endocrine systems in women adversely. According to the studies long-term exposure to parabens causes reproductive hormone disorders, like anti-androgenic manifestations and affects the reproductive hormones in the human body like follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH), Luteinizing hormone (LH), prolactin, the co-relative interaction decreases plasma corticosterone levels and increases follicle-stimulating hormone.
- The estimated daily exposure of parabens in the human body is in the range of 76-142 mg and are detectable in urine samples.
- Many studies revealed the correlation between Phthalates, bisphenols with endometriosis, health disorders such as auto-immune diseases, cardiovascular diseases, and neurodevelopmental defects like systemic sclerosis, multiple sclerosis, primary systemic vasculitis.
- Toluene (VOC) crosses placenta and has been detected in amniotic fluid and breast milk. Statistics show presence of VOC linking to increased fetal mortality, developmental effects and increased neurobehavioural toxicity. Prolonged contact with xylene causes irritation, dermatitis, dryness and skin cracking.
- When exposed to Phthalates (EDCs), the female menstrual cycle can be highly vulnerable to hormonal imbalance and changes in endocrine function, resulting in monthly abnormalities.
- Bisphenol can mimic estrogen, bind to estrogen receptors and disrupt the normal hormonal balance causing menstrual irregularities, hormonal imbalances, and reproductive disorders.

VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS

INSTRUMENTATION AND CONCLUSION

Liquid Chromatography with Tandem Mass Spectroscopy – analytical method for identifying and quantifying compounds which consists of a HPLC, separating components based on their affinity to mobile phase. After separation, the eluent is directed towards mass spectrometer where it is converted into ions. First mass Spectrometry stage (MS1) uses a magnetic field to separate ions based on their mass-to-charge ratios (m/z). Tandem Mass Spectrometry (MS2) selects specific ions for further analysis, fragmenting them to identify compound structures. In the last step ions are detected and Analysed according to the resulting mass spectra, providing information on compound presence and concentration. • HPLC AND GCMS were also used.

Indian Perspective

With the increase in awareness and schemes catered for promoting the use of feminine hygiene products, effects of the chemicals used is not clearly studied and informed about particularly in the Indian market. Acetone, dichloromethane, benzene chloroform are present in 10-10.230 ng/g concentration way above the prescribed range by European Union; which is yet to be observed by the Indian authorities. Moreover locally manufactured products are yet to be regulated.

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CHARTS

Presence of Compounds in Hygiene Products

BISPHENOLS

■ PADS ■ PANTY LINERS ■ TAMPONS

PARABENS

■ PADS ■ PANTY LINERS ■ TAMPONS

THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF SEXUAL ASSAULT SURVIVORS

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INTRODUCTION

- Rape has serious consequences, including psychological, physical, and reproductive costs.
- Fear and anxiety, posttraumatic stress disorder, depression, low self-esteem, social adjustment challenges, and sexual dysfunctions are among the topics addressed.
- According for many victims, seeking post-assault support becomes a "second rape," a secondary victimization of the initial trauma.
- In response to growing concerns about the community's response to rape, new treatments and programs aimed at improving services and preventing secondary victimization have evolved.
- Rape crisis centers, restorative justice programs, and sexual assault nurse examiner programs are investigated. Strategies for increasing the visibility and effect of psychologists and other associated professionals are also highlighted.
- The statistical procedure of multidimensional scaling was employed in the analysis of this data, which in turn produced a five-cluster model of serial rapist behavior.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

RAPE TRAUMA

- Rape is relatively seldom reported by girls and women globally due to the acute social, religious, and caste stigma or the fear of rejection by their family members or being subjected to violence and where premarital sex is banned or premarital sex can face prosecution before the laws. In India, rape is a notoriously under-reported crime. Because rape victims will face prosecution under current legislation, they must undergo protracted prosecution and inquiry. Even if there is adequate evidence to show a rape inside the court, they cannot obtain justice. [4]
- Recovery from sexual assault-related Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is not only defined by the absence of symptoms or the achievement of specified outcomes. Healing from this trauma does not imply that the survivor will forget the experience or will never feel any symptoms again. [1]
- Rather, successful recovery is subjective and measured by whether the survivor increases his or her involvement in the present, acquires skills and attitudes to regain control of his or her life, forgives himself or herself for guilt, shame, and other negative cognitions, and gains stress reduction skills for overall better functioning. [2]
- Many factors contribute to successful recovery, including the amount of support received, past self-concept, personal strength, and professional treatment provided by the medical and justice systems. PTSD is one of these.
- The psychology of each age group is different for each rape cases.
- Childhood sexual abuse sufferers were separated from nonvictims by a pattern of enhanced anxiety, heightened interpersonal sensitivity, greater anger problems, more paranoid ideation, and increased obsessive-compulsive symptoms.
- Many factors influence an individual's response to trauma, and psychological reactions differ widely amongst people. The 'meaning' that a victim assigns to the occurrence is likely to be crucial, as evidenced by the distinctions between stranger and acquaintance rape. It may be believed that the former would be significantly more traumatic, but research has revealed that rape victims experience similar degrees of sadness and greater difficulty when raped by their husband, that is, forced copulation between the partners. [5]
- Lack of mutual consent is present in all sexual assaults.
- The traditional triad of post-traumatic stress symptoms of haunting, intrusive recollections, numbing or restriction of sensations and focus, and lowered threshold of anxious arousal following severe anxiety, terror, and loss of control are all present. Anxiety, melancholy, phobic reactions to situations resembling sexual assault, sexual dysfunction, decreased social adjustment, and diminished capacity to enjoy life are long-term repercussions.

8 YEAR OLD GIRL GANGE RAPED [6]

CONCLUSIONS

CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM FOR RAPE CASE IN INDIA

Rape is a cognizable offence in India. There are so many provisions in different Acts for rape.

- Section 375, 376A, 376B, 376C and 376D of Indian Penal Code 1860. Section 53(1)[4], 164A [5], 327(2)[6] of Code of Criminal Procedure. Section 114-A [3] of Indian Evidence Act.
- To raise awareness about the need of protecting girls' children and ensuring that they have similar rights as boys. Give boys and females equal opportunities in society and respect girls/women. The study was carried out to examine the status of rape victims in today's criminal justice system in comparison to the previous one, as well as to identify any gaps in the new improvements. The paper gave opinions on India's criminal justice system. The report has recommended several policymakers to the government, NGOs, and social communities in order to reduce crime against women. Our constitution will include numerous safeguards to prevent and control crimes against women.
- As a result, through appealing programs, the media should play an essential role in raising legal and social awareness among young men and women. Society should also focus on changing its attitude toward young women, and they should be given more security and care. The government should also enforce harsh penalty, and the length of the judicial procedure should be decreased to discourage perpetrators from taking advantage of it.

THE ALARMING RISE OF RAPE

- Rape is regarded as one of the most heinous crimes against the individual and his or her identity.
- The rising rate of crime against women in India has become a major issue for the government and its officials. It is critical to keep sexual violence against women under control.
- Women's status in Indian society has been steadily declining. Women in the pre-Vedic era gained equal rights and were treated similarly as males; the deterioration in women's standing in Indian society continues. The social and cultural structures of India have consistently subordinated women, and the legal system has traditionally regarded women as weak and passive, serving as a tool for women's subordination. The patriarchal worldview drives women to be naïve, feeling uncomfortable and susceptible to their male counterparts. [3]
- The goal of this study paper is to better understand demographic characteristics and their impact on sexual assault against women. Rape is considered the most severe form of sexual violence against women.
- A number of community outreach activities are being carried out by local authorities and administrative divisions to create public awareness about this heinous crime. The purpose of this research article is to discover the core reasons of such horrific acts, to provide a legal viewpoint in the Indian Criminal Justice System, and to enhance the mental health of rape survivors.

COUNSELLING SESSION OF A SEXUAL ASSAULT SURVIVORS

Phase 1: Assessment and education

Phase 2: Rapport and strengths

Phase 3: Cognitive intervention

Phase 4: Emotion focused

Phase 5: Trauma narrative

Implications and model tenets

मासूम सरप

बैचकर ले गया आरोपी, अरेस्ट

गया कि वह परिवार के जे इलाके में किराए पर ली में पति, दो बेटे और ति प्राइवेट जॉब करते हैं। करीब 5 बच्चे उनकी पांच र के बाहर खेल रही थी। उन्होंने पाया कि उनकी थी। वह बच्ची को खोजने

वह अपने दोस्तों के साथ खेल रही थी इसी दौरान अंकल उसे खींचकर टॉइर में ले गए। वह चिल्लाने लगी तो अंकल ने उसे कई थप्पड़ मारे। इस दौरान उ वह रोने लगी तो लोगों ने चीख-पुड़ सुनकर दरवाजा तोड़ दिया और वा निकाला। महिला ने पुलिस कॉल व वारदात की जानकारी दी, जो मासूम

express.com/articles/india/maasum-rape-victim-reveals-trauma-to-psychiatrist... A

entertainment Sports Politics Lifestyle Tech Investigations Research Express Et Al

rape victim reveals trauma to psychiatrist, accused arrested after

daily raped by son of her school's owner in Sabarsa district of Bihar in 201 d for assisting accused

NewsGuard

Why this

THE CASE

appear: In a shocking twist (the Besa girl's case, city po nabbed the older brother the 32-year-old man for sexually exploiting her in regulars around three % ago, before she was shif

On Death Row

गैंगरेप के बाद कार से कुचलकर हत्या रोहतक में निर्भया जैसी दरिंदगी

गैंगरेप के बाद कार से कुचलकर हत्या रोहतक में निर्भया जैसी दरिंदगी

Besa girl's bro too arrested for sexually exploiting her

ing her during Covid lockdown at their Bengaluru home

When survivor's father saw them together, he sent girl away to Nagpur where she was reduced to a domestic help, said cops.

THE NEWS OF RAPE CASES ACROSS THE COUNTRY

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to Mr Anshuman V Ramani Professor, Vivekananda Global University, Jaipur and Ms Sahar Zehra Naqvi, Assistant Professor, Vivekananda Global University, Jaipur for invaluable guidance and support in creating the poster. Your expertise and dedication played a pivotal role in our success, and we are truly thankful for your mentorship. I would also like to extend our sincere thanks to Vivekananda Global University for providing us with this wonderful opportunity.

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LOST IN THE ABYSS: STUDY OF ASPHYXIAL DROWNING

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INTRODUCTION

"Drowning" is a potentially life-threatening event that occurs when an individual's airway becomes submerged in water or another liquid, impeding the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide. Risk factors for drowning include alcohol use, drug use, epilepsy, minimal swim training or a complete lack of training, and, in the case of children, a lack of supervision.

The key aspects of drowning, including its epidemiology, risk factors, prevention strategies, and the physiological mechanisms involved in the drowning process.

- 90% of drownings take place in freshwater and 10% take place in seawater
- Alcohol is involved in approximately 50% of fatal drownings, and 35% of non-fatal drownings.
- drowning rate for African Americans above the age of 29 between 1999 and 2010 was significantly higher
- Breath-hold under voluntary control until the urge to breathe due to hypercapnia
- Cerebral anoxia stops breathing and aspiration
- Cerebral injury due to anoxia becomes irreversible

DIAGNOSIS AND METHODS

- The diagnostic of drowning is described in the literature as one of the most difficult in the field of forensic medicine (Piette & De letter, 2006).
- The main goal in this field is to differentiate a death by submersion from a immersion of a body.
- It is important to remind that the death by drowning is defined as a death due to submersion in a liquid and the mechanism in acute drowning is hypoxemia and irreversible cerebral anoxia.
- The external signs of drowning influence the process of decomposition that are peculiar to immersion. The body surface is usually pallid. Face becomes bloated and body gets discolored with the progress of decomposition and as a result identification becomes impossible.
- The internal signs of drowning depicts that the lungs due to squeezing out of blood show pale grey appearance owing to compression of the vessels in the interalveolar septa by the trapped air and water in the alveoli.
- There are some histological contributions too which shows how the process of drowning and the medium in which it takes place. In addition to the lungs, liver, cardiac muscle and kidneys may also be examined for signs of acute oxygen deficiency and asphyxiation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION.

- According to the National Crime Records Bureau, there were 36,362, drowning deaths reported in 2021 in India, with children being particularly vulnerable.
 - Boys at higher risk of drowning than girls.
 - Limited access to safe water increases more drowning.
 - People who are unable to swim also are at risk of drowning.
 - Modell (1968) reviewed the mechanism of drowning and suggested that about 10% of victims of drowning do not aspirate water but die of asphyxia due to laryngospasm
 - It has also been seen that the rate of atypical drowning is more than typical drowning. In classical drowning cases, there might be more drowning signs which gradually deaccelerate the drowning process.
 - Cobbett et al. reported concomitant diagnoses which probably led to the death of the person for 38.2% of their autopsy cases of drowning
 - The latest WHO Global Health estimates indicate that almost 236000 people lost their lives to drowning in 2019.
- Just over 50% of these deaths occur among those aged under 30 years and drowning is the sixth leading cause of death worldwide for children aged 5-14 years.
 - Highest drowning rates occur among children aged 1-4 years, followed by children aged 5-9 years globally.

RESULTS

- Drowning is a leading cause of death for youngsters now a days all over the world
- More children ages 1-4 die from drowning than any other cause of death.
- For children ages 5-14, drowning is the second leading cause of unintentional injury death after motor vehicle crashes.
- For every child under age 18 who dies from drowning, another 7 receive emergency department care for nonfatal drowning.
- Nearly 40% of drownings treated in emergency departments require hospitalization or transfer for further care (compared with 10% for all unintentional injuries).
- Drowning injuries can cause brain damage and other serious outcomes, including long-term disability.3-5.
- People who have got certain medical conditions such as autism and heart conditions may have higher risk of drowning.
- Drowning in the bathtub is the most common for people who have been suffering with seizure disorders.
- Drowning can also lead to emotional and psychological stresses in the case of both the victim and the witness, mostly the cases which involve children.

Fig: "Officials attempting to reconstruct events of a case through dumping a crude dummy in the sewerage pipeline. The case pertains to death of a lady constable"

CONCLUSIONS

CONCLUSION

- Drowning is one of the leading causes of death of children, youngsters and adults around the world under the age of 25 years where the number of males are twice the number of females. One of the major cause of drowning is the flash floods or flood disasters that mostly occur during the rainy season. Another reason behind the cases of drowning is the lack of parental supervision. In many cases, we see that when both the parents are busy with their respective chores, they leave their child to play out and as a result lack of their attention leads to a hazardous incident. So, it is advised to all the parents not to leave their child all alone even if when they are too busy. Next, drowning cases are also associated with alcohol consumption of the adults. So during swimming or any other activity related to water the person is advised not to drink alcohol or inhale any thing which makes them inebriated. And lastly, if anybody happens to drown in the water then it does not mean that you can only save them by going in the water too, but by acting quickly, by calling for help, by throwing a floating object, by using a life-jacket.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Asphyxia leads to relaxation of the airway, which permits the lungs to take in water in many individuals. We acknowledge the devastating and often preventable loss of life due to drowning. Drowning is a tragic event that can affect individuals of all ages, backgrounds, and abilities. It is a reminder of the importance of water safety education and awareness. Our thoughts go out to the victims and their families who have been affected by this heartbreaking event. We also express our gratitude to the dedicated first responders, lifeguards, and organizations that work tirelessly to prevent drowning incidents and save lives. This acknowledgment emphasizes the seriousness of drowning, expresses sympathy for the victims and their families, and encourages a collective effort to prevent future incidents through education and awareness.

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RAPID DNA TECHNOLOGY: A FORENSIC APPROACH

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INTRODUCTION

Rapid DNA testing has been around since 2010. It is the automated process of obtaining an accurate DNA profile without the need for human analysis. The Law enforcement can take a cheek swab of an individual under arrest and insert the sample into the Rapid DNA machine, which is about the size of a printer. Rapid DNA provides a DNA profile within 90 minutes. The DNA sample is then compared to other samples with in the FBI Combined DNA Index System(CODIS) and those from unsolved violent crimes. In order for Rapid DNA testing to be used, such as in the case following an arrest, states must have an arrestee DNA collection law that authorizes DNA analysis at the time of arrest. So far 30 states and the federal government allow it.

Matching the DNA samples from crime scenes and suspects is rapidly becoming a key source of evidence for use in our justice system. DNA Technology in Forensic Science offers recommendations for resolving crucial questions that are emerging as DNA typing becomes more widespread.

The volume address key issues:

1. Quality and reliability in DNA typing.
2. DNA typing in courtroom, including issues of population genetics,
3. Societal issues, such as privacy of DNA data, storage of samples and data.

DNA can be used to identify criminals with incredible accuracy when biological evidence exists and DNA can be used to clear suspects and exonerate persons mistakenly accused or convicted of crimes.

SIGNIFICANCE OF DNA TECHNOLOGY

1. Rapid DNA Technology significantly reduces the time required for DNA analysis, providing quicker results.
2. Enable the law enforcement to obtain DNA profiles rapidly, accelerating the investigative process.
3. Portable and automated Rapid DNA systems allow on-site analysis.
4. Particularly valuable in scenarios with a large number of samples or in disaster victim identification.
5. Rapid DNA technology can play a crucial role in solving cold cases by quickly analyzing DNA samples and matching them against databases.
6. Helps address the issue of DNA analysis backlogs in forensic laboratories by expediting the processing of samples.

Fig: The RapidHIT ID system from IntegenX with a primary cartridge (a reagent cartridge that contains the necessary reagents and consumables for capillary electrophoresis) and a sample cartridge.

MATERIALS

1. **DNA Extraction Kit:** Contains reagents and enzymes for rapid DNA extraction from biological samples.
2. **PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) Kit:** Amplifies specific DNA regions for analysis.
3. **Fluorescent Dyes or DNA Probes:** Used for labeling DNA fragments during PCR.
4. **Capillary Electrophoresis System:** Separates DNA fragments based on size for analysis.
5. **DNA Database:** A database for comparison and identification of DNA profiles.

METHODS

1. **Sample Collection:** Gather biological samples such as blood, saliva or hair from crime scenes.
2. **DNA Extraction:** Extract DNA from the collected samples using a rapid extraction kit.
3. **PCR Amplification:** Use PCR to selectively amplify specific DNA regions. This steps is crucial for increasing the amount of DNA available for analysis.
4. **Fluorescent Labeling:** Introduce fluorescent dyes or DNA probes during PCR for labeling the amplified DNA fragments.
5. **Capillary Electrophoresis:** Separate the labeled DNA fragments based on size using a capillary electrophoresis system.
6. **Database Comparison:** Compare ,obtained DNA profiles with the database of known profiles to identify individuals.

INSTRUMENT USED IN RAPID DNA TECHNOLOGY

There are two systems of NetBio, i.e., ANDE™ and DNAscan™ use a common cotton swab for input of reference samples to be processed within 90 min by the instrument.

1. **ANDE™ RAPID INSTRUMENT :** It is a ruggedized instrument, an expert system that performs data interpretation and a single-use, all-in-one consumable chip that accepts an oral swab or forensic sample. ANDE™ provides fully automated generation and interpretation of a DNA ID in less than 2 hours

2. **DNAscan™ :** It is a first fully automatic "swab in-profile out" Rapid DNA analysis approved by FBI is the NetBio DNAscan Rapid DNA Analysis™ . The currently used DNAscan 6C has the capability to analyze 4 samples at 27 loci within 90 min.

RESULTS

RAPID DNA technology enables quick analysis of DNA samples, providing identification and profiling information. This technique has been utilized in various domains including the identification of individuals, screening illegal migrations across the border, human trafficking, and analysis of degraded biological samples. The results typically include information about the individual's genetic profile, aiding in criminal investigations or paternity testing.

Benefits of Rapid DNA

1. Rapid DNA largest benefit by far is its speed. The current process for traditional DNA testing takes a long time – weeks, if not months, to obtain an accurate analysis. Rapid DNA can produce a DNA profile within two hrs while suspects are still in police custody.
2. Another potential benefit is there is less risk of the DNA sample being contaminated. Traditional DNA testing requires a sample to be identified, collected and transported to a DNA lab facility, then to be handled again by the lab technicians. This equates to more opportunity for contamination. With Rapid DNA, fewer individuals are handling the sample and fewer processing steps are involved, lowering risk of contamination. Once the sample is inserted into the Rapid DNA machine, the handling process is complete.

Forensic Applications

Rapid DNA Technology has various forensic applications, playing a crucial role in the expediting DNA analysis and aiding law enforcement and forensic professionals.

Here are some key forensic application:

1. **Crime Scene Analysis:**
 - Rapid DNA technology allows for on-site analysis of DNA samples collected from the crime scene.
 - Enables quick identification of potential suspects or victims aiding in the early stages of investigation.
2. **Missing Person Cases:**
 - Valuable in cases involving missing persons where biological samples are available.
 - Enables swift analysis and comparison of DNA profiles, potentially leading to the identification of missing individuals.
3. **Sexual Assault Investigation:**
 - Rapid DNA analysis is the instrumental in sexual assault cases by quickly identifying the DNA of the perpetrator or linking it to a suspect.
4. **Parental and Maternal Testing:**
 - Useful in determining the paternity or maternity.
5. **Forensic Intelligence:**
 - Rapid DNA analysis contributes to forensic intelligence by providing timely information for law enforcement strategies and decision making.

CONCLUSION

RAPID DNA technology possesses a definitive advantage for its use in definitive scenario such as at the crime scene. Due to ease in operation and complete automation, processing of the samples at crime scene or police stations may not require highly skilled personnel besides interpretation of the obtained results. Regarding cost of the instrument and its associated consumables, if we include the operational as well as infrastructure cost, the RAPID DNA technology is highly useful for processing fewer samples with the requirement of urgent results for investigation purpose. Hence, the technology works fine for database generation and analysis of reference samples in a short period of time.

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FORENSIC IMPLICATION OF MUSCIDAE(DIPTERA) UNRAVELLING THE CONTRIBUTION OF THIS LESSER-KNOWN FAMILY TO POSTMORTEM INTERVAL

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INTRODUCTION

Muscidae play an important role in forensic entomology. They are one of the first groups of insects to colonize a dead body and their larvae can be used to estimate the postmortem interval (PMI), or time since death their importance in forensic investigations stems from their predictable life cycle and close association with decaying organic matter.

Muscidae were shown to be very numerous. Species-level identification of entomological material is a prerequisite for a meaningful application of entomological methods for PMI estimation purposes.

Thus, when taxonomic complexities or lack of identification tools prevent relatively easy and precise species identification, a broad application of the group for medico-legal purposes is severely limited. The growing sophistication in forensic entomology methodology has raised interest in the larval morphology of dipterans colonising cadavers.

Forensic entomologists collect and identify Muscidae flies and their larvae from crime scenes. They use this information to estimate the PMI and to help determine the cause and manner of death.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Collection: Muscidae DIPTERA can be collected from a crime scene using a variety of methods, including hand-netting, traps, and aspirators. The specific collection method will depend on the type of specimen being collected and the environment in which it is found.

Identification: Muscidae DIPTERA can be identified to the species level using a variety of morphological and molecular methods. Morphological identification involves examining the physical characteristics of the specimen, such as the body shape, wing patterns, and genital structures. Molecular identification involves analyzing the DNA of the specimen.

Collection equipment: This may include hand nets, traps, aspirators, and forceps.

Preservation equipment: This may include ethanol, killing jars, and pinning blocks.

Microscopy equipment: This may include microscopes, slides, and coverslips.

Identification keys and reference materials: These are used to identify Muscidae DIPTERA to the species level. "Molecular biology equipment" This is used to analyze the DNA of Muscidae DIPTERA for molecular identification.

TIME SINCE COLONIZATION

Adult species present at scene
↓
Larval weight
↓
Temperature
↓
Larval length pupal analysis
↓
Dispersion pattern
↓
Weather data
↓
Accumulated degree hour
↓
Postmortem interval

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

RESULT

- Precise developmental data for forensic indicator blow fly species are essential for accuracy in the estimation of the postmortem interval.
- Collecting living organisms from the corpse and studying their development under laboratory conditions can lead to much better results.
- But the determination of the postmortem interval is sometimes conflicting. To use larval development in estimating the postmortem interval, accurate information on the development of individual species is essential.

DISCUSSION

- Muscidae maggots go through three instars, or stages of development. Each instar is larger than the previous one, and the final instar is the largest and most active. After the third instar, the maggot pupates, and eventually emerges as an adult fly.
- The larval stage of a Muscidae fly is called a maggot. Maggots are legless, cylindrical worms with a pointed head and a blunt tail. They are typically white or cream but can also be gray or brown. Maggots have no eyes, but they do have colored, but not two dark hooks on their head that they use to feed.
- As soon as the death of an organism occurs, the process of decomposition sets in. Decomposition is the process of the breakdown of organic matter into simpler substances by a variety of organisms, including bacteria, fungi, insects, and other detritivores. As the body decomposes, the larval stage of muscidae flies (maggots) may appear.

- Muscidae flies can also be used to collect DNA evidence. Muscidae flies are often covered in pollen and other trace evidence from the crime scene, which can be used to link them to the suspect or victim. Muscidae flies can also be used to collect DNA from the victim, which can be used to identify them or to link them to other crimes.
- The age of specimens collected from the victim may be estimated to provide a minimum time period since death. It is mentioned that because of their relatively short developmental cycles, blow flies and flesh flies are typically useful only during the first three to four weeks following death.
- The growth rate of larvae can be studied by rearing them in the laboratory and this can give a reliable definition of time since death. Temperature and humidity heavily influence insect activities, such as the rate of oviposition and maturity.

CONCLUSIONS

- The primary objective of this study is to gather baseline data and to stimulate further study of the forensically important flies, especially those species that have established themselves as the primary indicators of time since death.
- The study presented here is limited and can shed light on the importance of blow flies (Diptera: Calliphoridae) as post mortem interval indicators.
- The new approaches for estimating time since death discussed above seem more reliable and can be used with confidence in medico-legal cases given the inherent difficulties in generating a precise postmortem interval estimate are considered.
- The study detailed herein is designed to make investigators and law personnel aware of the importance of forensic entomology in criminal cases.
- Investigators should not be completely dependent on the few baseline studies.
- Estimation of postmortem interval is based on few valid assumptions and errors in any of these assumptions can lead to wrong estimates of time since death.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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The Relationship Between Body Weight and Bone Ash After Cremation: Implications in Forensic Science

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INTRODUCTION

- Forensic science is a multidisciplinary field crucial for solving mysteries related to human remains, especially when traditional identification methods are insufficient.
- Cremation, a widely practiced method of disposition, presents unique challenges for forensic investigators due to the transformation of a human body into ashes and bone fragments.
- The cremation process is highly variable and may result in differences in the composition, quantity, and characteristics of the bone ash.
- This study aims to investigate the potential correlation between the body weight of the deceased before cremation and the properties of the bone ash that remains.
- Questions to be addressed include whether heavier individuals yield more bone ash, if the composition varies, and whether these factors affect forensic identification methods.
- Understanding the interplay between body weight and bone ash could revolutionize the way forensic scientists approach the identification of human remains post-cremation

MATERIALS & METHODS

- To achieve a significantly large sample size, data were aggregated from cremation collections sourced from various locations across the United States.
- All samples underwent the modern cremation process, performed at a variety of crematoria.
- As a result, each collection displayed substantial variation in quality and appearance.
- The total sample comprised 761 cremations, with 412 from male individuals and 349 from female individuals.
- Depending on the entry date into the collection, most cremations were enclosed within sealed bags and subsequently placed in boxes.
- Whenever possible, data were recorded, including age, stature, perimortem weight, and any additional information that was available.
- For cases with sufficient perimortem data, BMI calculations were conducted.
- A BMI statistic ranging from 18.5 to 24.99 is considered "normal," while anything below is labelled underweight. Overweight is defined as 25.00–29.99, and 30.00 marks the threshold for obesity (28,29).
- Samples calculated as "obese" were noted during the study.

Linear regression of cremation weight (kg) on perimortem body mass (kg) for total sample (including 95% upper and lower confidence limits). s Plot of individual cremation weights against body mass

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- This research introduces a novel approach to understanding the relationship between body mass and the skeleton, inferred through the analysis of cremation data.
- A strong positive correlation was observed between cremation weight and perimortem measures. On average, a one-standard-deviation increase in fat mass results in an 8.1% boost in bone.
- Moreover, it's important to note that obesity leads to irreversible alterations in the body's composition.
- The recorded weight at the time of death reflects a complex interplay of factors, including body proportions (such as stature, lean muscle mass, and adiposity), in combination with the individual's sex and age. When analysing cremation weight, body mass emerged as the most significant determinant, though it's important to consider the collective impact of body mass, BMI, age, and sex, as all these variables showed significant associations.
- The calculated BMI exhibited a similar, albeit slightly weaker correlation with cremation weight, which was an unexpected finding, given the additional dimension theoretically incorporated into this measurement.
- This could potentially be attributed to the considerably smaller sample size with available BMI data. It's plausible to suggest that the effects of age and conditions like osteoporosis may undermine the efficacy of BMI as a measure.
- The process of replacing muscle tissue with fat as individuals age, coupled with the inconsistencies often encountered in self-reported height measurements, may further complicate the use of BMI, especially in the case of elderly individuals found in many of the cremation samples.
- It's worth noting that male values consistently tended to be higher than those of females, but there was substantial overlap in the distributions.
- Therefore, it is essential for researchers to exercise caution when attempting to distinguish between men and women in unknown circumstances based solely on cremation weight or amount. Women, in particular, exhibit more pronounced changes in skeletal weight and density, particularly with advancing age.
- Cortical thickness and articular areas are the skeletal regions most affected by body mass and obesity, and they contribute significantly to cremation mass.
- Consequently, cremation weight can be utilized to estimate perimortem weight, particularly in cases involving severe obesity or emaciation.
- In certain forensic scenarios where remains have been subjected to burning or charring, rendering them unidentifiable, cremations can serve as a useful proxy.

CREMATION PROCESS

CONCLUSIONS

- 1. Positive Relationship:** The study uncovers a positive correlation between an individual's body weight and the amount of bone ash produced post-cremation. In essence, individuals with higher body weights tend to yield greater quantities of bone ash after the cremation procedure.
- 2. Statistical Relevance:** The correlation established between body weight and bone ash content is statistically significant. This signifies that the association is unlikely to be a result of random chance but rather reflects a meaningful and substantive relationship.
- 3. Predictive Utility:** The results suggest that body weight may serve as a predictor for estimating bone ash content post-cremation. This predictive capacity can be particularly valuable in scenarios requiring the analysis of bone ash in forensic and archaeological contexts.
- 4. Forensic Relevance:** In forensic investigations dealing with severely burned or cremated remains, comprehending the connection between body weight and bone ash can be instrumental in approximating the individual's pre-mortem body weight, thereby aiding in victim identification.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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EXAMINING CREMATION

CREMATION RATE

FORENSIC FACIAL RECONSTRUCTION

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INTRODUCTION

- Forensic facial reconstruction is the process of recreating the face of an individual from their skeletal remains.
- It involves a combination of scientific analysis and artistic interpretation to estimate facial features such as eyes, nose and mouth.
- It is the most subjective and controversial technique used in the field of Forensic science.
- This technique can aid in the identification of an unknown individuals in criminal cases and can provide leads by creating a visual representation of suspects and victims, can be presented as an evidence in the court with other forensic testimonial evidences.
- The technique of forensic facial reconstruction helps to determine the sex, age, facial features that leads to the identification of an unknown person.
- In some cases such as mass disasters, arson cases, buried and decomposed bodies this technique is used.
- Methods of facial reconstruction are mainly two types 2D and 3D.
- There are several methods but the Combination Manchester Method has been reported to be the best and most accurate method for positive recognition of an individual, recognition allows the involved govt. agencies to make list of suspected victims to make the positive identification.

MATERIALS & METHODS

MATERIALS REQUIRED :

Wax, modelling clay, plaster cast , depth marker.

METHOD:

- Skull is cleaned and the damaged or broken area is repaired with wax. In the absence of teeth ,approximate vertical dimensions between mandible and maxillae are measured and mandible is reattached.
- Modelling clay is filled in nasal openings and artificial eyes are inserted into orbits between superior and inferior orbital rims.
- After this ,plaster cast of skull is made. After setting of cast, colored ends of safety matches are attached at twenty one landmark areas.
- After all these steps, modeling clay is used to add all the features.
- After the construction of facial muscles, nose, and lips are constructed.
- Width of nasal spine and nasal aperture is measured while constructing the nasal profile.
- To yield approximate nose length calculation of 3 times the length of the spine plus the depth of tissue marker number 5 is made.
- A block of clay is then placed on the nasal spine and the remaining tissue is filled using tissue marker 2 and 3 for the nasal bridge.
- Below the bottom of nasal aperture alae is created.
- The soft tissue of around the eyes and facial muscles are added.
- After this tissues are built and ears are added.

FLOW CHART

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

RESULT:

- The technique of facial reconstruction helps in the identification of an unknown individual. After the face is reconstructed, the visual identification of the individual's family and associates thus becomes easy.
- Sometimes in case of a dead body is unidentified as its face cannot be recognized due to destruction by animals, physical attacks or decay caused by environmental factors. Forensic facial reconstruction is an alternative method in the identification when there is little or no other evidence is available.
- The skeletal features that reveal the subjects age, gender and ancestry, and anatomical feature like asymmetry, evidence of injury.

DISCUSSION:

- The first facial reconstruction was done by German anatomist Wilhelm in 1895.
- He reconstructed the face of German composer Johann Sebastian Bach.
- The goal of facial reconstruction, consequently, is to create best similarity to the original facial position of the unidentifiable remains, also in the background of forensic science., to stimulate community concentration that may finally lead to the recognition and proof of identity the person.
- There are two types of facial reconstruction, 2D and 3D

2D facial reconstruction:

This is used to create a face from the skull with the use of soft tissue depth estimates. This method was first developed by Karen Taylor in Austine, Texas during the 1980s. It is based on antemortem photographs and the skull which is to be reconstructed. This method is also used in identification of the deceased from skeletal remains.

3D facial reconstruction:

This method is similar to two dimensional method as it also requires the use of tissue depth markers of specified lengths to represent different soft tissue depths. The markers are inserted into small holes on the skull cast at specific strategic points or landmarks.

- In manual or computer based, can never accomplish an exact demonstration since the human face is a very detailed structure involving of a number of variables such as the eyes, ears , lips, skin color etc.
- It has not always been possible to get a positive successful result. Reliable accuracy rates of reconstruction techniques can be obtained only efforts are made to fully explore the true nature of the relationships between the soft facial tissues and the underlying skull.
- There are several limitations which are associated with forensic facial reconstruction.

2D FACIAL RECONSTRUCTION

CONCLUSIONS

- In conclusion Forensic facial reconstruction technique aims at estimating the facial outlook associated to an unknown skull specimen for victim identification.
- All facial reconstruction techniques are based on the assumed relationship between the soft-tissue envelope and the underlying skull substrate
- The level of detail in the reconstruction can vary, influenced by factors like the expertise of the artist or software used and the quality of available reference data.
- It's a valuable tool for forensic investigations when trying to identify individuals based on skeletal remains, but it should be considered an approximation rather than an exact likeness.
- Computerized remodeling of missing individual is also significantly easier as compared to the manual method.
- Even the accuracy of these techniques are questionable, these techniques prove to be a identification of the individual when no other source of evidence found.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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SKULL WITH TISSUE DEPTH MARKER

PROCESS OF 3D RECONSTRUCTION

Abrus Precatorius : Medicinal Potentials and Toxic Effects of a Plant with Historical Significance

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INTRODUCTION

- Abrus precatorius, also known as Gunja or Jequirity, is member of the Fabaceae family of peas and is widely distributed throughout the Indian plains, from the Himalayas to Southern India and Ceylon.
- The plant is regarded as a great source of distinctive natural ingredients for creating medications to treat a variety of ailments.
- Ayurveda recommends the administration of the Abrus precatorius in disease like alopecia, edema, helminths, skin diseases, itching, urinary disorders, and antifertility.
- Seeds are the most poisonous part of the plant due to a toxic component –abrin.
- Abrin inhibits protein synthesis within cells by interfering with the ribosome, which leads to cell damage and death.
- By blocking the implantation of a fertilised embryo in the uterine wall, abrin obstructs the early stages of pregnancy.
- Abrin may affect sperm function and production in males, lowering fertility.
- This plant has some potential medicinal value, but it also has some toxic effects too due to presence of the "abrin" component, which is fatal to humans if ingested or used improperly.

Experiment

An experiment was conducted to analyze the anatomy of testis of male Swiss albino mice.

- Experimental animals**
- Twenty Swiss albino mice (both male and female) were raised together for 15 days from the age of 30 days to acclimate and mature sexually.
- The experiment began when the mice were 60 days old.
- They were housed in metal cages with wire mesh and deep bottom dishes to facilitate sexual behavior. The environment had a room temperature of $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, relative humidity of 70-80%, and natural day and light conditions.
- Extraction of the plant**
- Plant material (seeds and fruit) was air-dried for 10 days in the shade, then ground into a fine powder. 50 grams of this powder was mixed with 1 liter of distilled water, intermittently shaken for extraction, and left to stand overnight.
- The resulting mixture was filtered through Whatman filter paper and concentrated at 60°C in an incubator. The concentrated extract was stored in a refrigerator at 4°C .

Experimental treatment

At the age of 60th day the treated groups were administered the aqueous extract seed of Abrus precatorius orally for the purpose of birth control.

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF ABRUS

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Sample collection

After six weeks of the experiment, all animals from both the control and treated groups were sacrificed. Testis samples from the left side were collected using a scalpel or forceps and preserved in 10% formalin for gross and histological observation.

Tissue processing and staining

- Testis fragments, 5 mm in diameter, were preserved in 10% formalin for 48 hours, cleaned in xylene, and embedded in paraffin after rinsing in a 10% phosphate buffer solution for 3 hours.
- Tissues were dehydrated in alcohol for 2 hours, and 5 μm -thick sections were cut with a rotary microtome. These sections were stained with Meyer's Hematoxylin and Eosin and examined under a light microscope.

RESULTS

Weight, length, Diameter and colour

- In the control group (group C), testis weight, length, and diameter were 0.08 ± 0.02 gm, 0.70 ± 0.05 cm, and 0.40 ± 0.02 cm. In the treated group (group T), these measurements were lower to 0.07 ± 0.00 gm, 0.60 ± 0.2 cm, and 0.30 ± 0.0 cm, indicating a significant decrease.
- The treated group also had slightly paler-colored testes compared to the control group.

Histomorphological study

- In the control group (group C), the testis had normal histology with seminiferous tubules encircled by connective tissue, interstitial (Leydig) and Sertoli cells present, and mature spermatozoa in the tubule lumen.
- However, the treated group (group T) showed reduced seminiferous tubule number (16 vs. 35), decreased spermatozoa (35% reduction), fewer Sertoli and Leydig cells, and the presence of vacuoles and fibrin thickening (fat deposition), indicating significant histopathological changes.
- Toxic Effects of Abrus (90 -120 mg)**
- Irritation of Gastrointestinal Tract
- Nausea, Vomiting, Abdominal pain
- Bloody diarrhea and Rectal Bleeding
- Seizures and hallucinations.
- Damage to Vital Organs Such as kidney and Liver.
- Weak rapid Pulse
- Pulmonary edema.
- Trembling
- Death due to multiorgan Failure after 2 to 5 Days of exposure.

Microscopic Examination Of Swiss Albino Mice testis

Historical architecture of testis of Control group (A, C, E, G) and testis of Treated group (B, D, F, H)

CONCLUSIONS

- Abrus precatorius (Gunia or Jequirity) is a plant known for its medicinal potential, but it also contains a toxic compound called "abrin." Abrin inhibits protein synthesis within cells, which leads to cell damage and death. Abrin may affect sperm function and production in males, and block implantation of fertilised embryo in uterine wall.
- The experiment conducted to understand the impact of the aqueous seed extract of Abrus precatorius on the testicular morphology and reproductive parameters in mice. The results revealed significant changes in the treated group compared to the control. The treated mice exhibited reduced testis weight, length, and diameter, suggesting a detrimental effect on testicular development and function. Additionally, the treated group had paler-colored testes, indicative of potential damage to the testicular tissue.
- Histological examination showed a decrease in the number of seminiferous tubules and a reduced amount of spermatozoa in the treated group. Sertoli and Leydig cells were also diminished, and the presence of vacuoles and fibrin thickening in the testicular tissue indicated structural alterations. These findings suggest that the aqueous seed extract of Abrus precatorius had adverse effects on testicular histology and function, potentially impacting fertility.
- While the plant has some potential medicinal value, its toxic component, abrin, can lead to harmful reproductive consequences when used improperly.

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Abrus Precatorius Seeds and Flowers

FORENSIC ARTISTRY: THE POWER OF VISUAL IDENTIFICATION

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INTRODUCTION

Our poster talk, "Forensic Artistry: The Role of Sketches and Facial Reconstruction in Identification," is on forensic artistry, an intriguing and vital field within forensic science. An overview of the critical role that forensic artistry plays in criminal investigations, accident reconstructions, and disaster victim identifications is given in this abstract. Forensic artists use cognitive interviewing techniques to skillfully translate verbal accounts into precise and comprehensive visual representations, allowing law enforcement to pinpoint suspects and individuals of interest with the highest level of accuracy. At its core, forensic artistry consists of two crucial components: the creation of composite sketches based on eyewitness descriptions and the complex art of facial reconstruction, utilized when traditional identification techniques prove inadequate. On the other hand, facial reconstruction is a crucial answer when human remains pose unsurmountable obstacles for traditional identification. Equipped with an understanding of both two- and three-dimensional reconstruction methods, forensic artists incorporate anthropological observations, variances in tissue depth, and facial dimensions to reconstruct an individual's face, providing a means of identification and closure. Using innovations in technology like facial recognition software and 3D printing, forensic artists are now more productive and precise. However, they struggle with the arbitrary interpretation of eyewitness testimony and moral conundrums relating to the exhibition of facial reconstructions. Interdisciplinary cooperation between forensic anthropologists, pathologists, and law enforcement agencies is essential to the advancement of forensic art. The field's crucial place within the larger field of forensic science will be further cemented by ongoing standardization initiatives and the integration of digital tools.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Case Studies from the Past and Present: We have assembled an extensive library of past and present instances in which forensic artistry was essential to the identification process. These examples shed light on the usefulness and significance of forensic art. **Expert Interviews:** We spoke with seasoned pathologists, forensic anthropologists, forensic artists, and law enforcement officials. We were better able to comprehend the approaches, difficulties, and developments in the sector thanks to these interviews. **Methods/Techniques:** **Data Collection:** In order to present a thorough picture of the topic, we gathered information from the previously stated sources, including case descriptions, interviews, and scholarly publications.

FLOWCHART

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+---[Forensic Artistry]|||
+---[Composite Sketches]|||
+---[Eyewitness Descriptions]|||
+---[Facial Reconstruction]|||
+---[Unidentifiable Remains]|||
+---[Interdisciplinary Cooperation] |||
+---[Forensic Anthropologists]|||
+---[Pathologists]|||
+---[Law Enforcement]|||
+---[Technology & Tools]|||
+---[Facial Recognition Software] ||
+---[3D Printing]||
+---[Challenges]||
+---[Eyewitness Testimony Interpretation]|||
+---[Moral Conundrums]||
+---[Advancements]||
+---[Standardization Initiatives]|||
+---[Digital Tools Integration]||
+---[Role in Forensic Science]||
+---[Criminal Investigations]||
+---[Accident Reconstructions]||
+---[Disaster Victim Identifications]||
    
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RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Criminal investigations and the judicial system both heavily rely on forensic arts. It uses the strength of visual recognition to help law enforcement identify suspects, solve crimes, and provide closure to the families of the missing. In this poster, the significance of forensic artistry and the most important findings from our research are highlighted.

Facial reconstructions: A crucial component of forensic artwork is facial reconstruction. When a skeleton remains are discovered, forensic artists use their skill to reproduce the deceased's facial characteristics. After determining the size and shape of the skull, layers of clay or other materials are added to simulate facial tissues and features. By using this technique, forensic artists support forensic anthropologists and law enforcement in finding people who may have been gone for a long time. These reconstructions are now much more accurate, which has enabled successful identifications throughout time.

Composite sketches: When eyewitnesses are present, composite sketches are a very useful tool in criminal investigations. Using the witness's description of a suspect, forensic artists collaborate to produce precise composite sketches of the culprit. These drawings can be useful in locating and capturing culprits. Even though the precision of composite sketches can vary depending on the artist's talent and the witness's recollection, they continue to be a potent weapon in law enforcement, frequently resulting in the identification and apprehension of offenders.

Age regression: Age progression is crucial for finding missing people, particularly youngsters who have been missing for a long time. By updating photographs of people based on their age, forensic artists can provide a realistic representation of how they would appear at various phases of life. Many lost children have been successfully recovered using this technique, and families have been reunited. It demonstrates the versatility and originality seen in the discipline of forensic art.

Increasing Public Engagement: The effectiveness of visual identification methods goes beyond the realm of law enforcement. In order to solve crimes, it is crucial to share facial reconstructions, composite sketches, and age-progressed photographs with the public. Law enforcement can get tips and information that might otherwise go unnoticed by involving the community in the identification process. This public-private partnership has been helpful in solving a number of crimes and locating those who have gone missing.

Improved Identification Rates: The effectiveness of these visual identification procedures is demonstrated by the increased likelihood that missing people and suspects will be correctly identified. Higher success rates in identifying unknown people can be attributed to the accuracy and precision of facial reconstructions and composite sketches. These identifications have brought comfort to the families of the missing. Using forensic creativity to solve cold cases has been particularly successful. Investigations that had lain dormant for years have gotten a new lease on life because of age progression techniques. Investigators have been able to find new leads and solve cases that had lingered unanswered for a long time by developing updated photographs of missing people.

Collaboration within the Community: The manner that law enforcement engages the public has changed as a result of sharing sketches and reconstructions with the community. When citizens can actively assist in preventing crime, they are more likely to come forward with information. In many circumstances, this cooperative approach has served as the impetus for criminal cases to be closed and arrests made.

Future Implications: As technology and knowledge improve, forensic arts as a field continue to develop. Future optical identification techniques promise to be even more precise and effective. The level of precision that forensic artists may anticipate to achieve in their work will increase with the incorporation of artificial intelligence and 3D modeling. This continual development highlights the value and effectiveness of visual identification in forensic science and law enforcement.

Facial reconstruction

CONCLUSIONS

Visual identification benefits greatly from the compelling marriage of art and science known as forensic artistry. The importance of forensic artistry has been thoroughly discussed in this poster. Their capacity to reproduce faces and other visual representations of suspects, unknown people, and the deceased has significant ramifications for criminology and law enforcement.

The crucial role that forensic artwork plays in solving cold cases, finding missing people, and giving answers to families who have long sought for closure demonstrates the strength of visual identification. Using extraordinary accuracy and attention, forensic artists bring sketches and reconstructions to life, frequently resulting in significant breakthroughs in cases that could not have been solved otherwise.

In addition, forensic artistry is not limited to just facial reconstructions. It includes a wide range of methods that help investigators in diverse circumstances, including age progression and post-mortem sketching. Forensic artists are well positioned to have a lasting impact on the legal system by combining their aesthetic abilities with scientific understanding.

In short, this poster emphasizes how forensic artistry serves as both a potent investigative tool and a monument to the pervasive power of visual communication. It serves as a tribute to the incredible ways in which innovation and technology intersect to further the interests of justice, demonstrating that in the field of forensic inquiry, a picture really is worth a thousand words.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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EFFECTIVENESS OF FINGERPRINT ANALYSIS VS. DNA PROFILING IN SOLVING CRIMINAL CASES

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INTRODUCTION

1. Forensic science plays a pivotal role in the criminal justice system by providing critical evidence that aids in solving crimes and bringing perpetrators to justice. Two of the most prominent forensic techniques employed for this purpose are fingerprint analysis and DNA profiling. While both methods have revolutionized the field of criminal investigation, they differ significantly in terms of their principles, applications, and effectiveness.
2. Fingerprint analysis has long been a cornerstone of forensic science, serving as a reliable method for identifying individuals based on the unique patterns found on their fingertips. This technique has played a pivotal role in criminal investigations and the justice system.
3. DNA profiling, also known as DNA fingerprinting or genetic fingerprinting, has revolutionized the field of forensic science, playing a pivotal role in solving criminal cases. This powerful technique involves analyzing specific regions of an individual's DNA to create a unique genetic profile. This profile is as distinct as a human fingerprint, making it an invaluable tool in identifying suspects, exonerating the innocent, and unraveling mysteries that have confounded investigators for years.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Methods of DNA profiling

1. Short Tandem Repeat (STR) Analysis: it analyzes specific regions of the DNA that contain short repeated sequences.
2. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR): PCR is used to selectively replicate the DNA regions of interest, increasing the amount of DNA available for analysis.
3. Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphism (RFLP): This method analyzes variations in the length of DNA fragments obtained by digesting DNA with specific enzymes.

Methods of fingerprint analysis

1. Visual Examination: Fingerprint analysts visually examine the patterns, ridge counts, and minutiae points on the fingerprint.
2. Powder Dusting: Fingerprint powders, such as black or white powder, can be applied to a surface to make latent fingerprints visible.
3. Fingerprint Lifting: Once a visible or treated fingerprint is identified, it can be lifted from the surface using adhesive tape or other specialized tools for preservation and further examination.

Procedure of DNA Fingerprinting to determine the probable identity of a person based on Nucleotide sequences of certain regions of Human DNA unique to every individual.

TECHNIQUES OF FINGERPRINT ANALYSIS AND DNA PROFILING

Technology and Fingerprint Analysis

1. **Infrared laser Ablation Technology** : lasers are used to scan the obtained latent prints on the surface. They are then heated while focusing to achieve a higher amount of energy in a minute location. When the heat is enough, the chemical bonds start to stretch while in the water and finally explode. They end up lifting the chemical compounds in a procedure that know as laser ablation. The bonds are sucked then to a filter where is examined with the use of spectrometry techniques.
2. **Advanced Fingerprint Identification Technology (AFIT)**: Advanced fingerprint technology in recent has been used collecting, developing and identifying fingerprint evidence more quickly and easily. With this technology, even wiping the fingerprints from the surface may not work since this technology is very effective. This technology has improved the process of fingerprint collection at the crime scene together with the matching of the fingerprint with the existing database. The technology was first launched by the Federal Bureau of Investigation.
3. **Color Changing Fluorescent Film** : The fluorescent film provides the investigators with a more contrasting tool of the colors in the latent prints in the form of electrochromic and fluorescent. A third color is provided by the fluorescent film which has the ability to be adjusted to come up with high contrast images of the fingerprint. This technology is very critical in helping to reduce the errors involved during latent prints comparisons of the suspects.

DNA Fingerprinting Versus DNA Profiling

Definition

DNA fingerprinting refers to the analysis of DNA to identify individuals, while DNA profiling refers to the analysis of individuals' DNA characteristics for forensic studies.

Importance

DNA fingerprinting is a molecular genetic method that allows the identification of individuals according to the unique patterns of DNA, while DNA profiling is a forensic technique important in both criminal investigations and parentage testing.

Type of DNA Sequences

DNA fingerprinting focuses on VNTRs including both minisatellites and microsatellites while DNA profiling mainly focuses on STRs (microsatellites).

Techniques

Techniques Involved in the Process RFLP, AFLP, and PCR are the techniques widely used in DNA fingerprinting, while PCR is the main technique used in DNA profiling.

Characteristics

DNA fingerprinting is a cumbersome method with many steps, DNA profiling is a simple process, which can be automated.

The Impression or mark left by the underside of the tips of the Fingers or thumbs formed by Friction Ridges of the skin surface..

CONCLUSIONS

- In conclusion, both fingerprint analysis and DNA profiling are highly effective forensic tools that have significantly advanced the field of forensic science. Their effectiveness lies in their unique strengths, complementarity, and the ability to provide accurate and reliable identification crucial for criminal investigations and justice delivery. The integration of these techniques enhances their combined effectiveness, aiding law enforcement and forensic experts in solving cases and ensuring a fair judicial process.
- Combining both fingerprint analysis and DNA profiling in forensic investigations enhances overall effectiveness. The integration of these techniques allows for a more comprehensive and accurate identification of individuals involved in criminal activities.
- Fingerprint analysis and DNA profiling are often used in conjunction to strengthen the evidence base, corroborate identifications, and ensure the accuracy and reliability of investigative outcomes.
- DNA profiling provides a higher level of specificity and can link individuals to biological evidence, even in cases where fingerprints may not be present or identifiable.

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DNA profiling involves analyzing an individual's unique genetic code, specifically focusing on specific regions of their DNA

TO STUDY GENETIC INFLUENCE IN HANDWRITING AMONG FAMILY MEMBERS

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INTRODUCTION

- One of the acquired traits of humans is handwriting. It is the result of a combination of nature and nurture.
- Parents serve as role models for their children when it comes to learning. A preschooler is impacted by his or her parents' handwriting. They learn to write letters by imitating or duplicating their parents' handwriting.
- They will begin writing it without pay once they are comfortable with the way they write it and how it appears. After personally analyzing all of the samples, commonalities between the parents and their offspring were discovered.
- This research was done to see if there was any relationship between family members in a handwritten document. Is there a significant association between hieroglyphics inherited qualities or not? For which, handwriting traits such as -slant, alignment, and line quality, speed, etc. were studied. As a result of this research, it was discovered that the handwriting of the parents and their offspring is similar.
- Though the general appearance of the handwriting may or may not be similar, the formation pattern of the letters in the handwriting samples of the parents and offspring is shown to be similar when closely inspected

MATERIALS & METHODS

- All the samples were collected using same writing instruments including writing surface, writing pen (ball point) and white A4 size sheet.
- To take the samples, a standard paragraph was given to the subjects and was asked to copy it
- All the samples were manually examined by using hand lens of 10 X magnification. All the inherited traits were examined based on the individual class characteristics.
- Written informed consent was taken before sample collection.
- 10 characteristics were analyzed i.e. alignment, legibility, line quality, movement, pen pressure, rhythm, slant, spacing, speed and style.

The objectives of this study is:

1. To check the similarity in handwriting of the offspring to father or mother.
2. To check which parent, show highest genetic influence in handwriting.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- Out of 35 families 17 of them is showing similarity of child's handwriting with father, 10 of them is similar with the mother.
 - 7 families are showing child's handwriting similar with both the parents.
 - Characteristics showing Genetic influence towards :
 - father- movement, speed, pen pressure and line quality
 - mother- style, rhythm and legibility
 - both father and mother - spacing between a word .

- Addressing limitations and potential sources of bias in our study is crucial for maintaining the integrity of our research. Here are some common limitations and potential sources of bias that you may need to consider:

1. Sample Size:

Limitation: A small sample size may not be representative of the entire population.
Bias: Selection bias can occur if the sample is not randomly chosen, potentially skewing the results.

2. Data Collection:

Limitation: The accuracy of handwriting analysis and genetic testing methods may vary.
Bias: If data collection procedures were inconsistent, it could introduce measurement bias.

3. Family Structure:

Limitation: Family structures can vary greatly, affecting the strength of genetic relationships.
Bias: If certain family types are overrepresented, this could lead to bias in the results.

presentation of result:

CONCLUSIONS

- In the present study, by analyzing all the data, it is observed that father highly influenced the handwriting of child as compared to mother.
- The characters like movement, speed, pen pressure and line quality showed highest dominance, which helped in influencing the handwriting of the child towards father.
- As in this study samples were taken from only 35 families and the result showed dominance of characters of father, but if the number of samples gets increased then there is probability that the result may change i.e., the value of genetic influence of handwriting from father and mother may vary.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

It would like to express my gratitude and appreciation to all those who gave me the possibility to complete this poster. Special thanks is due to my supervisor Miss Pooja Rawat ma'am whose help and suggestions helped me to make this poster.

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Sr. No	CLASS CHARACTERISTICS	CATERORIES			
		FINGER (1)	WRIST (2)	FOREARM (3)	WHOLE ARM (4)
1	MOVEMENT	FINGER (1)	WRIST (2)	FOREARM (3)	WHOLE ARM (4)
2	SPEED	LOW (1)	MEDIUM (2)	FAST (3)	.
3	ALIGNMENT	ASCENDING (1)	DESCENDING (2)	HORIZONTAL (3)	IRREGULAR (4)
4	SLANT (LETTER "B" & "T")	FORWARD (1)	VERTICAL (2)	BACKWARD (3)	MIXED (4)
5	SPACING (BETWEEN A WORD)	NARROW (1)	MEDIUM (2)	WIDE (3)	.
6	PEN PRESSURE	LIGHT (1)	MEDIUM (2)	HEAVY (3)	.
7	LINE QUALITY	SMOOTH (1)	DEFECTIVE (2)	.	.
8	STYLE	MORE CURSIVE (1)	LESS CURSIVE (2)	.	.
9	RHYTHM	UNIFORM (1)	DEFECTIVE (2)	.	.
10	LEGIBILITY	GOOD (1)	POOR (2)	AVERAGE (3)	.

E-NOSE : BOON FOR INVESTIGATION

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INTRODUCTION

- A trace, which is a pattern, a signal, or material transferred during an event (often unknowingly by the actors in the event), is analyzed and accepted as a form of scientific evidence into a civil or criminal proceeding. Forensic science can be defined as the application of any form of science, in particular analytical chemistry. Because of this, knowledge and technology developed using a solid scientific method must not only adhere to accepted standards of science but also to the rules of admissibility established by the appropriate legal authorities.
- Bloodhounds were employed by the English in their 1888 hunt for Jack the Ripper, and the state Supreme Court of Alabama (US) confirmed in 1893 that "dogs may be trained to follow the tracks of a human being with considerable certainty and accuracy" in 1893.
- At some crime scenes like at a fire or arson may be some of hazardous gas or substance is spread over the area which may be dangerous for the dogs or humans .
- For the safety of our officers and the search dogs we can use a instrument "E-NOSE" stands for Electronic nose.
- A gadget called a "e-nose," which stands for "electronic nose," is made to replicate the human sense of smell and find and recognize scents or volatile substances in the environment.
- It is a sort of electronic sensor system that has numerous uses, such security, environmental monitoring, medical diagnostics, and food and beverage quality control.
- As we are aware, circumstantial evidence is evidence that is connected to a conclusion of fact by an inference, such as an odor, smell, or fragrance at the scene of a crime. We can utilize a device like an e-nose for the collecting of these odors, or we could say for their identification.
- This gadget can interoperate a wide range of odors either of explosives or the odor of a dead body .
- It can also help in the Terrorist attacks when terrorists plant a bomb the by using this we can find a bomb or the explosive it can reduce danger of the bomb squad and the search dogs.
- E-noses are sensor devices that simulate the olfactory skills of humans and other animals. They have a number of uses in numerous industries, including forensic science

NEED OF E-NOSE

- E-noses are employed in forensic science for the following reasons:
- Finding and Classifying Odors: Specific smells or volatile organic compounds (VOCs) linked to crime scenes can be detected and identified using e-noses. Finding hidden evidence, such as drugs, accelerants used in arson cases, or decomposing human remains, can be aided by this. E-noses can assess scents quickly and objectively, lessening the reliance on human olfaction, whose sensitivity can vary from person to person.
- Identifying Explosives and compounds: At crime scenes, e-noses are used to look for explosive remnants or other dangerous compounds. They can quickly spot volatile substances, which aids investigators in evaluating potential dangers and securing the scene.
- E-noses can be used to examine human scent or odor prints left on items of clothing or other items recovered from a crime scene. This can aid in locating culprits or creating connections between people and particular places.
- Post-mortem examination: In forensic pathology, e-noses are used to examine the volatile substances emitted during the decomposition of human remains. This information can be used to determine the passing time and spot any strange substances.
- Control of the evidence's quality: It is possible to evaluate the reliability of evidence storage using e-noses. They are able to spot variations in olfactory patterns that can point to contamination or evidence tampering.
- E-noses are useful in fire and arson investigations because they can identify the fire-starting agents employed. They can discriminate between various kinds of accelerants, which helps in figuring out what started the fire.
- Overall, e-noses are essential to forensic science because they offer sensitive and unbiased olfactory analysis, which enables investigators to gather information, come to wise judgments, and solve crimes more quickly. They supplement more established forensic techniques and are particularly helpful in situations where human olfaction may be imperfect or unreliable.

ANALYSES OF ODOR RELATED EVIDENCES

- Electronic nose (e-nose) examination of odor-related evidence is a useful method in forensic science. How such evidence can be analyzed using e-noses is as follows:
- Evidence gathering: The first step is to gather the pertinent odor-related evidence from the crime scene. Items like clothing, objects, or substances with distinguishable odors that may be connected to the crime could fall under this category.
- Analysis of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs): E-noses have sensors that can identify and measure VOCs. Instead than relying on human perception, these sensors react to the chemical makeup of odors. The e-nose system receives the evidence and places it in a chamber or sealed container. The system then analyzes the VOCs in the area.
- olfactory profiling: Based on the particular concoction of VOCs found in the evidence, e-noses produce olfactory profiles or "fingerprints" of the environment. Every material has a distinctive smell, and the e-nose can tell one substance from another even though their smells are comparable to the human nose
- .Comparison and matching: If databases of recognized odor profiles are accessible, the obtained odor profile from the evidence can be compared to them. This comparison can aid in the inquiry by pointing out probable matches to known compounds or substances.
- Quantitative Analysis: E-noses can offer numerical information regarding the quantity of a particular VOC present in the evidence. The relevance of the odor-related evidence and its possible impact on the case can be determined in large part by this information.
- E-noses can also be utilized for temporal analysis, which involves monitoring changes in the olfactory profile over time. For instance, the e-nose can examine changes in a piece of clothing's odor profile to build a timeline or track movements if it is suspected that the clothing has been in contact with a specific place or person.
- Classification and Discrimination: E-noses can be taught to distinguish between various scents or substances. When working with complicated combinations or recognizing unknown compounds based on their smell, this is especially helpful.
- Presentation in Court: The outcomes of an e-nose analysis can be used as scientific proof in a courtroom. For the e-nose to be admissible, proper documentation and certification of its dependability and accuracy are required.
- Cross-Referencing with Other Evidence: In order to construct a thorough case, the results of the e-nose study should be taken into account alongside other forensic evidence, such as DNA analysis, fingerprints, and witness accounts.
- Quality Control: To guarantee precise and trustworthy findings, e-nose equipment must undergo routine maintenance and calibration. The integrity of the analytical process should be upheld by implementing quality control procedures.
- In order to correlate evidence to suspects or crime scenes, identify chemicals, and offer helpful ideas for solving cases, using e-noses in odor-related evidence analysis can improve the objectivity and precision of forensic investigations. To get a more full picture of the crime, it's crucial to employ e-noses as part of a larger forensic strategy that incorporates a variety of types of evidence and expert analysis.

Electric Nose System

THINGS REQUIRED TO MAKE THE USE OF E-NOSE POSSIBLE

- E-Nose Instrumentation: The essential element is a working e-nose device. It is made up of a number of sensors that can identify and evaluate volatile organic compounds (VOCs). For reliable results, the e-nose needs to be properly calibrated and maintained.
- Data Acquisition System: To record and process sensor responses, an e-nose requires a data acquisition system. Analog sensor data should be able to be transformed into digital data by this system for analysis.
- Software and Algorithms: For data processing and pattern recognition, specialized software and algorithms are required. With the aid of this software, individual scents or compounds can be identified as well as sensor responses that can be translated into useful olfactory profiles.
- Reference Odor Database: An e-nose frequently uses a reference odor database to recognize unidentified smells. Known odor profiles are included in this database for comparison and classification purposes.
- Standards for Calibration: To guarantee the accuracy and dependability of the e-nose, regular calibration with recognized standards is necessary. There should be a variety of VOCs included in calibration standards depending on the application.
- Training Data: To learn and develop its capacity to recognize certain scents or compounds, an e-nose may need training data sets for pattern recognition and classification.
- Sampling Containers: To gather and preserve odor-related evidence without contaminating it, suitable sampling containers are required for forensic applications. These containers ought to be chemically and airtightly inert.

CONCLUSIONS

- In order to correlate evidence to suspects or crime scenes, identify chemicals, and offer helpful ideas for solving cases, using e-noses in odor-related evidence analysis can improve the objectivity and precision of forensic investigations. To get a more full picture of the crime, it's crucial to employ e-noses as part of a larger forensic strategy that incorporates a variety of types of evidence and expert analysis.
- E-noses can identify toxic or hazardous compounds for officers, improving safety protocols at crime scenes.
- Efficiency: E-noses make it possible to quickly screen objects and regions, which streamlines the investigation process and aids officers in setting priorities.

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NEUROLOGICAL STUDY OF COMBINATIONAL DRUGS (CNS STIMULANT & DEPRESSANTS) ON C. ELEGANS

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INTRODUCTION

The drug interaction and its mechanism are interlinked. The different drugs show different effects on CNS based on its binding receptors and its level of dosage. The CNS depressants and CNS stimulants shows different mechanism of action. One will stimulate the neurological function and other will depress its function. When these two drugs have been administered into the body, it will show some adverse drug reactions based on kind of drugs ingested or administered. These adverse effects can be easily observed by ingesting drugs to C elegans. C elegans belongs to class of round worms and which has transparent clear body. The adverse effects can be studied based on the locomotion of the c elegans based on the drug toxicity. The interesting and surprise factor about c elegans was "it has backward movement". It is also one of the factors to be considered after administering the combinational drugs to a certain period of time. Based on the study factors of different physiological and neurological changes the type of adverse effect can be determined or identified. There might be possibility of drug can show synergism, potentiation or antagonism in combinational administration to host. Caenorhabditis elegans (C. elegans) has been and remains a valuable model organism to study developmental biology, aging, neurobiology and genetics. The large body of work on C. elegans makes it an ideal candidate the relationships with another organism. In order to use C. elegans in collaborative omics research, a method is needed to generate large populations of animals where a single sample can be split and assayed across diverse platforms for comparative analyses. to integrate into large population, whole-animal studies to dissect complex biological components and their

MATERIALS & METHODS

MATERIALS REQUIRED

AgaroseN	E.coli	Uracil	LaminarFlow
Cacl2	Mgso4	M9Buffer	Autoclave
Nacl	KH2PO4	OP50	Micropipette mixture
Cholesterol	Glucose	BOD	Petri dish

PREPARATION OF NGM PLATES

The NGM plated Prepared by the of Nacl(1.5g), Peptones(125g), Agar(8.5g) & Distilled water at prescribed temperature and pressure conditions.

The mixture under cool at 55-60°C and then cholesterol(0.5ml), Cacl2(0.5ml), Mgso4(0.5ml) KH@PO\$(1,25ml)

PREPARATION OF M9 BUFFER

The mixture of KH2PO4(3g), Na2HPO4, Nacl(5g) Mgso4(1ml) & distilled water Prepared and autoclaved for 1 hr.

PREPARATION OF E. COLI

After autoclaved the M9 buffer the 70ml of MEM is mixed well (M9 Buffer, NH4cl, Glucose and uracil) in a cylinder.

CULTURING OF WORMS

The NGM plates are taken out from the fridge which has been incubated for 37°C and taken in a sterile environment of E. coli and spread over the Petri dish evenly distributed and left for few hours to settle evenly under prescribed environmental conditions.

CHUNKING OF NGM PLATES

After culturing the chunking process will takes place uncontaminated one and the chunking is done at the portion where the most of the population of c elegans present.

ADMINISTRATION OF DRUGS

The drugs will get administered at L2 and L3 stage of c elegans for better results.

LIFE CYCLE OF C ELEGANS

MECHANISM OF ACTION OF COMBINATIONAL DRUGS

CANNABIS ACTION OF MECHANISM

ALCOHOL ACTION OF MECHANISM

C ELEGANS IN CULTURED MEDIUM

C ELEGANS UNDER MICROSCOPE

CONCLUSIONS

The combinational drug had shown various chemical interaction reactions on CNS of C Elegans based on the drug administered, dosage administered and time frequency. Few combinations of drug has shown synergism, potentiation and antagonism. These like characters has been studied by considering few factors locomotion and other physiological aspects. The adverse effects time have been studied by dosage of frequency and other biological factors. The experiment has been carried out in contamination free environment. (the research is still going on)

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The joining hands of honorable and Professional expert of Toxicology This research cannot be accomplished without Dr. Amer mazir sir from (CSIR-CDIR LUCKNOW); the person who provided sample for unremarkable research and also guided at times. The second most respectful person miss Rachita Singh (Asst. prof FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY) stood all the time as back support and provided irreplaceable guidance in work. The third most honorable respectful person was Mr. Abhilash Kumar das (Asst. prof FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY AND CHEMISTRY) who have different initiation together the permission department to work and guided for several protocols. And Finally, I pay my gratitude to my co-research fellows who worked tirelessly all the time with me.

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USE OF ADVANCED AI TECHNOLOGY IN FORENSIC MEDICINE & FORENSIC ANTHROPOLOGY

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INTRODUCTION

- Forensic medicine, with its crucial role in legal investigations and the justice system, has long relied on traditional methodologies.
- However, with the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI), a promising shift has begun to unfold within the field.
- This paper delves into a comprehensive analysis of this transformative trend, emphasizing its significant applicability in forensic anthropology and other conventional sectors of forensic medicine.
- The integration of AI into forensic practices represents a paradigm shift, potentially marking a significant milestone for the entire forensic domain.
- Its introduction offers novel prospects for enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of investigations, thereby bolstering.
- The scope of this study encompasses a detailed examination of existing AI-driven techniques, their integration within forensic practices, and the potential challenges and opportunities that arise from their implementation. By emphasizing the adaptability and versatility of AI technologies, this research endeavors to underscore the breadth of its impact on traditional forensic methodologies.
- The application of artificial intelligence (AI) is a new trend in forensic medicine and a possible watershed moment for the whole forensic field

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) work similar to our visual brain when trying to recognize these objects. (b) Our recognition of objects on the picture is significantly improved when more layers—slices are added thus providing further context with the 3rd dimension. In the top row is recognizable intersection of the mandible and vertebra and on the lower row is recognizable slice of the face. 3D CNN recognition is similarly improved with providing context of depth.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- The main application, we used is for Face imposition using AI Technology and Forensic Anthropology.
- Here is the process we studied for the face imposition.
- Artificial intelligence has brought new vigor to forensic medicine, but at the same time also some challenges.
- AI and forensic medicine are developing collaboratively and advanced AI implementation until now required extensive interdisciplinary cooperation. In the era of big data, forensic experts shall become familiar with these advanced algorithms and understand used technical terms.
- For many forensic experts, the current benefits of advanced AI processes are still unknown.
- For example, automated AI algorithms for skull damage detection from CT or soft-tissue prediction of a face from the skull are still a mystery to many outstanding forensic scientists. Enabling them would catapult forensic research to a new era.
- A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a Deep Learning algorithm that can take in an input image, assign importance (learnable weights and biases) to various aspects/objects in the image, and differentiate one from the other. CNN is an efficient recognition algorithm that is widely used in pattern recognition and image processing. It has many features such as simple structure, less training parameters and adaptability. CNN is a supervised type of Deep learning, most preferable used in image recognition and computer vision.

The comparison of 2D CNN (above) and 3D CNN (below). 3D CNN works with 3rd dimension and can reconstruct shapes from the CBCT 2D slides. The sequence of 2D pictures where the 3rd dimension is time, we speak of a common video sequence that can be a subject of 3D CNN analysis too.

The examples of the segmentation process on the CBCT data based on defining ranges for particular tissues thus defining 3D structures such as airway, nerve canal, face surface or bone structures.

DISCUSSIONS

- Image based wound data are only considered in this review as there exist very little work on text based wound data.
- By reviewing the wound measurement and wound classification literature, we have summarized the current state of science, reviewed the datasets used, methodology developed, and critically listed the limitations of the study.
- Finally, all the developed systems and their scope, the platform on which these systems were built, and the tools used for developing these systems are briefly discussed in this review.
- Computational approaches and associated software and hardware are in great demand for analyzing wound images, classifying wound tissue types, measuring wound dimensions, and monitoring changes in wound over time. So, building an intelligent system for wound measurement, diagnosis and prognosis can save a lot of clinician time, reduce economic burden and increases patient quality of life.
- Looking into the future, we expect that wound assessment from a good combination of multimodality wound data is highly demanded for clinical diagnosis, prognosis and management.
- Applying the latest AI algorithms on these multimodality datasets and mobile devices will provide a remote and intelligent wound care system.
- The system will be greatly beneficial for healthcare staff members in wound care teams and most importantly for enhancing the quality of life of patients suffering from debilitating wounds.

The example of 3D data augmentation in a sense of mapping another 3D scans on the segmented structures. Facial 3D scan with texture mapped on the segmented face surface from CBCT and intraoral scan of teeth and gums mapped on tooth surfaces from the CBCT. Finally merged into complex set of 3D models. Training of 3D CNN with such a complex 3D virtualized model has never been performed before and is worth a consideration.

on CBCT to look younger or older. The algorithms changed just the texture and not the 3D mask, however this is probably only a matter of time. 2D face morphing based on AI or face swapping in popular videos are available and popular already a couple of years. Original face is the 2nd one.

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- This paper most complex AI application is the final 5th theme—“Facial growth vectors prediction”.
- The authors of this paper addressed it for various reasons.
- Firstly, it is fundamentally different from the first four themes.
- Secondly, it requires the most complex implementation of AI strategies.
- To our knowledge, this is only the second paper in the world that handles the problem of facial growth prediction with ML methods and absolutely the first paper to consider a 3D CNN for facial growth predictions.

FORENSIC PSYCHOLOGY AND ITS IMPACT ON INSTANCES OF MILITARY RAPE

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INTRODUCTION

FORENSIC PSYCHOLOGY AND ITS IMPACT ON INSTANCES OF MILITARY RAPE:

- Forensic Psychology applied to law. Application of scientific knowledge help in answering legal questions arising in law enforcement is a forensic psychology.
- Military Rape is Sexual Assault or Rape occurs in the Armed Forces.
- It troubles in Physical & Psychological consequences for the victims.
- Forensic Psychology in military rape deal with awareness about sexual violence in armed force, depressed & anxious victims from assault cases & examines how the principles of psychology interact with the case of assault.
- It evaluates victims, witness, an alleged perpetrator & playing role of therapist.
- Military courts-martial offer a unique environment where the fields of psychology and law intersect.
- With an increasing number of cases involving sexual assault

Forensic psychology aims to gain a deep understanding of the dynamics, causes, and consequences of sexual violence within the military.

It also aim to provide emotional, psychological, and therapeutic support to survivors of military rape.

Their goal is to help survivors cope with trauma, facilitate their recovery, and empower them to seek justice if they choose to do so.

It work to assess the psychological profiles of individuals who commit sexual assault within the military.

METHODS:

1. Evidence Collection and Legal Proceedings: The aim is to assist law enforcement and legal professionals in collecting and preserving evidence related to military rape cases. This helps ensure that the legal process is well-informed and that perpetrators are held accountable for their actions.

2. Prevention and Education: Programs like developing and implementing prevention programs and educational initiatives within the military aim to reduce the incidence of military rape by promoting a culture of consent, respect, and intervention when necessary.

3. Policy and Reform:

Forensic psychologists may also contribute to policy development and reform efforts within the military to address systemic issues related to sexual violence.

Their expertise can lead to changes in military policies and procedures aimed at preventing and responding to rape more effectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

CASE STUDY: KASHMIR MASS RAPE

- The incident occurred on February 23, 1991, in the village of Kunan, located in the Indian-administered region of Kashmir.
- Women in the village, including Zooni and Zareena, shared harrowing experiences of sexual assault and violence by the soldiers.
- These women described how they were subjected to sexual violence, and their accounts are filled with pain and trauma.
- The people of Kunan and the neighboring village of Poshpora have accused the Indian army of orchestrating a mass rape of women and subjecting men to brutal torture during this incident. They have been seeking justice for these alleged atrocities for over 26 years.

In recent years, a group of young Kashmiri women, along with Natasha Rathar, filed a petition to reopen the case in the state High Court. They believed that this significant case of mass rape, supported by substantial evidence, required a renewed investigation. After a challenging legal process, the Jammu and Kashmir High Court directed the state government to provide compensation to the victims, but the government later contested this decision in the Supreme Court of India, where the case remains pending.

The Indian Army has consistently denied the allegations, stating that the case has been independently investigated multiple times and closed due to conflicting statements.

The truth of what transpired that night in Kunan and Poshpora remains elusive, and it is a deeply disturbing and unresolved chapter in the history of Kashmir. The case is significant not only for its historical implications but also for the new generation of Kashmiris who are determined to bring the truth to light despite the challenges and complexities of the legal process. The residents of Kunan and Poshpora continue to grapple with the painful memories of that night, even as the village and its inhabitants evolve with the passage of time

ANNUAL REPORTS

- The Department of Defence encourages greater reporting to promote more help-seeking by Service members and to hold alleged offenders appropriately accountable.
- In total, the Department received 8,942 reports of sexual assault involving Service members as victims and/or subjects in Fiscal Year 2022, an increase of 1 percent from the 8,866 received in Fiscal Year 2021. Of the 8,942, 5,941 were Unrestricted Reports of sexual assault and 3,001 remained Restricted at the end of the year. Of the 8,942 reports, 7,378 were from Service members reporting an incident that occurred to them during military service.
- This reflects a 1.6 percent increase from the 7,260 such reports received in 2021. The Military Departments reported case outcomes (dispositions) for 3,928 cases in Fiscal Year 2022. Of those 3,928 cases, military commanders had sufficient authority or jurisdiction to consider 3,188 cases for possible action against the accused.
- The evidence supported command action in 2,117 cases. Commanders were precluded from action or respected victims' desire to not further participate in the justice process in 1,031 cases. Forty of the 3,188 cases were determined to be unfounded.

Top army officer says women 'used by a nexus through a fake narrative.'

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of forensic psychology in the context of military rape is to comprehensively address this complex issue by supporting survivors, assessing perpetrators, preventing future incidents, and contributing to the pursuit of justice.

The ultimate goal is to create a safer and more accountable environment within the military while ensuring that survivors receive the care and support they need.

The Fiscal Year 2022 Annual Report on Sexual Assault in the Military provides an update on Department of Defense efforts to counter sexual assault and sexual harassment in the military.

The report includes sexual assault reporting information and military justice outcomes as required by Congress.

This year, the report includes summaries of the steps taken to implement prevention and response initiatives and recommendations of the Independent Review Commission on Sexual Assault in the Military, as approved by the Secretary of Defense. The report covers Fiscal Year 2022.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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- <https://www.greeterkashmir.com/kashmir/in-kunan-poshpora-top-army-officer-says-women-used-by-a-nexus-through-a-fake-narrative>

KUNAN POSHPORA:30 years on, Survivors Await Justice

Recent Secretary of Defense Sexual Assault Prevention and Response Initiatives

Human fingerprint : A Unique identifier and beyond

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INTRODUCTION

- The human fingerprint is the impression left by the friction of the human finger. Recovering partial fingerprints from the crime scene is an important method of forensic science.
- The moisture and grease in the finger causes fingerprints on surfaces such as glass or metal. Fingerprint records typically contain impressions from the panel on the last joint of the fingers and thumbs, although fingerprint cards usually record parts of the areas of the lower finger joint .
- They may be employed by the police or other authorities to identify individuals who wish to conceal their identity, or identify incapacitated or deceased persons and therefore cannot identify them, as in the aftermath
- natural disaster each image as shown in figure 1 is represented by 2D matrix(for gray or binary fingerprint), or 3D matrix (for color fingerprint), the represent the colour intensity. In this paper we will analyse and discuss the method of features extraction
- The uniqueness, permanence, and consistency of fingerprints make them a reliable and widely used method for human identification.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- Fingerprint samples (collected from a surface) Fingerprint powder or chemical reagents (for developing latent prints);
- Brushes, applicators, or fingerprint lifting tape Fingerprint cards or collection sheets Magnifying glass or microscope Photography equipment (camera, lighting, scales) Latent print comparison database (if available) Laboratory equipment (gloves, containers, chemicals) Methods:
- Preservation: Securely store collected prints and evidence to prevent contamination or damage. Examination: Examine prints under a magnifying glass or microscope for ridge patterns, minutiae (unique ridge features), characteristics. Documentation:
- Photograph the prints for documentation and analysis. Include scale references in the photos. Comparison: Compare the latent print with known inked prints or those in a database if available
- verification: A second examiner may independently verify the results. Reporting: Prepare a report detailing the findings, comparisons, and conclusions. Testimony: If needed, testify in court as an expert witness regarding the fingerprint analysis. It's crucial to follow proper protocols and maintain the chain of custody to ensure the accuracy and admissibility of fingerprint evidence in legss.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Human Fingerprint sub headings Certainly, here are subheadings for a more concise overview of human fingerprints: Fingerprint Basics: An introduction to the concept of fingerprints

- The uniqueness and permanence of fingerprints. Fingerprint Patterns: Loops, whorls, and arches: Exploring the three main fingerprint patterns. The significance of ridge patterns in identification.
- Fingerprint Formation: How fingerprints are formed during fetal development. Factors influencing the formation of fingerprint patterns. Fingerprint Classification
- Modern systems for classifying fingerprints. Fingerprint Collection: Methods for collecting fingerprints, including latent prints. Best practices for preserving and documenting collected prints. Fingerprint Analysis: Examining ridge patterns and minutiae
- The use of fingerprints in biometric authentication. Advanced challenges of fingerprint biometrics. Fingerprint Privacy and Security: Concerns related to the security of fingerprint data. Legal and ethical considerations in fingerprint use.
- Human Fingerprint sub headings Certainly, here are subheadings for a more concise overview of human fingerprints: Fingerprint Basics: An introduction to the concept of fingerprints. The uniqueness and permanence of fingerprints. Fingerprint Patterns: Loops, whorls, and arches: Exploring the three main fingerprint patterns. The Henry Classification System. Modern systems for classifying fingerprints. Fingerprint Collection: Methods for collecting fingerprints, including latent prints. Best practices for preserving and documenting collected prints. Fingerprint Analysis: Examining ridge patterns and minutiae. The importance of minutiae in fingerprint matching. Fingerprint Identification: How experts compare and identify fingerprints. Automated fingerprint identification systems (AFIS). Fingerprint Applications: The role of fingerprints in law enforcement. Non-criminal applications, such as access control and identification. Fingerprint Biometrics: The use of fingerprints in biometric authentication. Advantages and challenges of fingerprint biometrics. Fingerprint Privacy and Security: Concerns related to the security of fingerprint data. Legal and ethical considerations in fingerprint use
- Fingerprint Research and Innovation: Current research in fingerprint analysis and technology. Innovations in fingerprint recognition and analysis. These subheadings provide a concise breakdown of key aspects related to human fingerprints, making it easier to navigate and understand the topic.

Human fingerprints

CONCLUSIONS

Human fingerprints are unique and permanent patterns formed by ridges and valleys on the skin's surface, primarily on the fingers and palms. They serve as a reliable means of identification and have been used in various fields, including criminal justice and personal device security. The conclusion is that fingerprints remain a valuable tool for identification due to their distinctiveness and stability throughout a person's lifetime. In conclusion, human fingerprints are highly individual and consistent over a person's lifetime, making them a reliable method for identification and verification purposes. They play a crucial role in forensic science, security systems, and various applications where accurate identification is essential. Fingerprint patterns are formed during fetal development and are influenced by genetic and environmental factors. These patterns consist of ridges, valleys, and minutiae points, which make each fingerprint distinct. Fingerprint identification has been a crucial tool in forensic science and law enforcement for identifying individuals and solving crimes due to its reliability and uniqueness. A simple, accurate and efficient procedure for fingerprint identifier extraction was proposed, tested and implemented. The obtained experimental showed the following facts: -The procedure requires small amount of time to extract minutiae. -The memory space required is small. -It is better to use a fingerprint segment to minimize the extraction time and the memory space. -We can use Euclidean distance to replace the points coordinates in the identifier, making the identifier smaller and easier to handle. -The obtained identifier for each fingerprint is unique, and it can be accurately used to retrieve the fingerprint in a recognition system

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Techniques used for analysis of Tool Marks

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INTRODUCTION

- Tool marks is an impression, cut or abrasion made when tool or an object comes in contact.
- Tool mark is also known as physical evidence which every tool has either same or different properties which can link crime scene with criminal.
- Tool marks can be analyzed to determine the direction, angle or force applied during tool use.
- Tool mark analysis can help establish a link between suspect and crime scene.
- Tool marks can provide valuable information about sequence of events during crime scene.
- Tool marks mostly found in various criminal cases like burglaries, car thief, and assaults.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- Material used in tool marks involves examining the tool marks itself or the surface on which it is found.
- Commonly materials include in tool mark is metal, plastic, glass and ceramics.
- Methods used by Forensic expert for analyzing tool marks, such as –
 - Visual examination
 - Chemical examination
 - Comparison microscopy
 - 3D imaging
- These methods help forensic experts to identify the tool used, determine the force applied, and can reconstruct the events surrounding a crime.

Name	class characteristic
Chisel	sharped cutting, blade-shaped
Screw driver	blade width, blade thickness, surface texture
Needle nose	long tapered jaws
Plier's	pliers have flat end
Coping saw	tint tic tack bord book with 1000 of square
Nails	shard point on one end, flattened head

Individuals characteristics : There is no definite character that can be listed individual's characteriser the Unique 'in' in toolmarks depends on individuals wear and tear

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Tool marks are very important factors in forensic investigations as it provide valuable evidence. They are impression or a mark left on a surface by tool, such as screwdriver or a crowbar. By analyzing these marks forensic expert can determine the type of tool used and sequence of event.

The materials and methods used in analyzing tool marks, forensic experts often employ many techniques like microscopy, photography, and comparison analysis. They examine characteristics of the marks, like striations, patterns, and dimensions, they identify the specific tool that may have caused them.

Tool marks can be found various places in crime scenes, including burglaries, car thefts, and even homicides. They can be present on doors, windows, safes, or any surface that has been tampered with or forced open. By documenting and analyzing these marks, investigators can add valuable information to solve the crime.

It's important to note that while tool marks can be a valuable source of evidence, their interpretation and analysis require expertise and caution. Forensic experts must ensure proper documentation, preservation, and analysis techniques to maintain the integrity of the evidence and prevent misinterpretation.

Overall, tool marks play a crucial role in forensic investigations, providing valuable insights into the tools and the identification of potential suspects.

CONCLUSIONS

According to information, the conclusion regarding tool marks in forensic investigations is that they are significant pieces of evidence. Tool marks can help to identify the type of tool used, potential suspects, and the sequence of events. Forensic experts analyze the characteristics of tool marks using techniques such as microscopy and comparison analysis. Proper documentation and analysis techniques are crucial to maintain the integrity of the evidence. Tool marks can be found in various crime scenes and play a vital role in solving crimes.

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STUDY OF WOUND BALLISTIC IN CRIME INVESTIGATION

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INTRODUCTION

A specialized subset of terminal ballistics, wound ballistics is an empirical science that primarily draws on physics and plays a significant role in the field of forensics. Both the physical and the medico-legal points of view have been used extensively in literature to describe how bullets interact with the human body. The irreversible destruction of tissue along the wound channel (referred to as a permanent cavity) and the spatial displacement of tissue as a result of the bullet passing through the body (referred to as a temporary cavity) are both components of the wounding mechanism of penetrating bullets.

In a broad sense, the study of how wounding agents—such as bullets and fragments from explosive weapons—interact with tissue is known as wound ballistics. The physical simulation and measurement of the interaction of wounding agents with tissue is the laboratory component of wound ballistics. Ballistic trauma encompasses the pathophysiological response of the body to the physical process, which overlaps with wound ballistics. Ballistic trauma therefore involves bleeding, shock, wound infection, and death.

The practice and application of wound ballistics in -Forensic medicine -Surgery—especially emergency and war surgery - International conventions Globalized conflict zones, terrorism and crime.

MATERIALS & METHODS

• MATERIALS:

1. GELATIN – Ballistic gelatin is to mimic human tissue, ballistic gelatin is a standardized synthetic substance. It is frequently used to research how bullets penetrate and generate temporary cavities. 2. ANIMAL TISSUE – Historically, wound ballistic tests have employed animal tissue, such as pig corpses, as it offers a more accurate model of human tissue than gelatin.

3. STIMULANTS OF BONES AND SOFT TISSUE – Several synthetic materials are intended to resemble human bone and soft tissue. They can be used to research how bullets affect particular body parts.

4. CADAVERS - Some cases, human cadavers may be used to study the actual effects of projectiles on human anatomy, although this is subject to ethical and legal considerations.

METHODS: 1. ANALYTICAL – To stimulate and forecast the behavior of

projectiles inside the body, researchers employ analytical methods including computer modeling and finite analysis

2. MEDICAL – Internal projectile damage to both synthetic and actual tissues may be seen with medical imaging techniques including x-ray, CT scans and MRI scans. 3. DATA ANALYSIS – Statistical and data analysis techniques

are used to evaluate the wound size, penetration depth and cavity dimensions that is obtained from the wound test.

4. HIGH SPEED CAMERAS essential for capturing the movement of projectiles in tissue. They allow researchers to analyze the behavior of bullets upon impact.

STAGES OF WOUND HEALING

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

• HOW DOES A BULLET OR WEAPON MAKE A WOUND? A bullet or its fragments physically alter the tissue when they pass through it. This causes the tissue to speed away from the projectile's front, lacerating and crushing it in different ways. The amount of kinetic energy available to carry out this activity determines the extent of the laceration and the degree of crushing. This equation calculates the quantity of kinetic energy that is available: E (joules) is equal to $mv^2/2$ (where m is mass in kg and v is speed in m/s). This equation illustrates how, in theory, a little increase in velocity generates more kinetic energy than a small increase in the mass of the bullet or fragment due to the " v^2 " term.

Whilst a bullet in motion does work on the tissue, the tissue also does work on the bullet. The amount of work done depends on the amount of kinetic energy carried by the bullet. This means that all bullets, if given sufficient velocity, can deform in soft tissue. As shown in shot 1 of this DVD, a full metal jacket bullet can be compressed and can break when it turns sideways along the track. This deformation is different from the deformation of a bullet specifically designed to expand such as a semi-jacketed bullet (as seen in shot 2 of the DVD). Any bullet in flight rotates around its long axis between 1500 and 6000 times per second. This gives the bullet stability in flight. However, other movements such as precession and nutation also influence the bullet's stability. A bullet has high stability if the angle of precession is close to the direction of flight. In general terms a bullet is stable for the first metre after exiting from the barrel. It rapidly adopts a flight with low stability in which the angle of precession is great in relation to the direction of flight. It then becomes increasingly stable in flight. On impact, a stable, non-expanding bullet has a long narrow track initially. Unless a bullet passes through certain parts of the brain or spinal cord, damaging vital areas, its effect depends not only on the purely mechanical effect (and the path of the wound channel) but also, to a very great degree, on the victim. His or her emotional and psychological state are decisive. Drugs, alcohol and similar also influence the effect of a bullet. So while effectiveness can be determined in a general fashion on the basis of physical parameters, effect depends entirely on the circumstances. Gunshot wounds are one of the most traumatic injuries you can suffer. It is difficult to assess the extent of damage done by a gunshot wound, and it typically far exceeds what you can reasonably treat with first aid. For this reason, the best option is to get the victim to a hospital as soon as possible. However, there are some first aid measures that you can take before professional assistance arrives.

RESULTS - Few papers provide information on the processes of

ballistic trauma, despite the fact that there have been many publications on the treatment of gunshot wounds. The majority of the material comes from earlier laboratory and animal research that have just lately been properly reviewed. According to these research, transient cavitation caused by the bullet becoming unstable or distorted causes an area of injured tissue to surround the primary wound tract in rifle injuries. The more frequent non-deforming handgun bullets, on the other hand, only inflict damage that is localized to the bullet's path and primarily results from localized crush injuries. Few papers provide information on the processes of ballistic trauma, with the main body of these papers being focused on the management of gunshots

LACERATION

THE CARTRIDGES

CONCLUSIONS

We conclude the motion of bullet, its action on body tissue and its velocity to affect a wound. Depending on the tensile characteristics of the tissues involved, transient cavitation damage might result in gradual muscle tissue necrosis in high-energy injuries. Therefore, the phrase "high-energy" should only be applied to wounds that have sustained significant tissue damage that extends outside the apparent wound tract. We conclude the motion of bullet, its action on body tissue and its velocity to affect a wound. Depending on the tensile characteristics of the tissues involved, transient cavitation damage might result in gradual muscle tissue necrosis in high-energy injuries. This knowledge may determine the extent of the evaluate the patient, as well as the extent of surgical debridement and repair necessary for each individual wound. thorough knowledge of wound ballistics is mandatory for all physicians who may be involved in the case of gunshot wound victims.

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BULLET IN SOFT TISSUE OF LEFT LOWER LIMB

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INTRODUCTION

- Through the decay of carbon – 14, which is a trace isotope in the environment, this technique, which is radiocarbon dating or carbon-14 dating, estimates the age of carbon-based organic materials. This technique was developed by Willard Libby in the year 1946. The adaptability of this technique have
- wide uses such as the authentication of historical record and artworks, safeguarding cultural heritage from forgeries. This technique can play a vital role in forensic science by helping in the determination of the time of death, verifying alibis, and also aiding in resolving the cold cases. By this, we can say that it bridges the time gap between the past and the present and help in uncovering the truths and mysteries. In this poster we will delve in to how this technique helps in the field of forensic science.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- The following is how radiocarbon dating works
- Collection of suitable samples:** Collect the sample that contains organic material, such as charcoal, wood, or bone. This should be carefully selected to ensure its suitability
 - Preparation of sample:** After the sample collection is done, it must be prepared for analysis. For the preparation, this includes removing any contaminants that can affect the accuracy of dating. Examples of such contaminants include rootlets or humic acids.
 - Extraction of carbon:** The extraction of carbon takes place by converting the organic material into carbon dioxide gas via chemical processes or combustion.
 - Isolation of carbon:** The carbon dioxide gas is then purified to isolate the desired carbon atoms. This is usually accomplished by passing the gas through a series of chemical reactions or filters. To isolate the desired carbons, the purification of carbon dioxide gas takes place. By passing the gas through a series of chemical reactions or filters this result is accomplished.
 - The measurement of carbon:** The analysis of the isolated carbon takes place to determine the ratio of carbon– 14 (C-14) to carbon– 12 (C-12). Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) is used for the isolation to accurately measure very small or minute amounts of C-14.
 - The Calibration:** The ratio of C-14 to C-12 is then compared to a calibration curve that changes according to the atmospheric C-14 levels over time. This is done to convert the ratio into a calendar age.
 - The Age Calculation:** The age of the sample can be calculated using the calibration curve by locating the point on the curve that corresponds to the measured C-14 to C-12 ratio.

WORKING FLOWCHART

RADIOCARBON DATING AND IT'S INVOLVEMENT IN FORENSIC SCIENCE

The technique of radiocarbon dating in the work of forensic science mostly involves the use of specialized laboratory equipment and different techniques rather than the use of a single devices. The accelerator mass spectrometer (AMS) is the primary instrument used for radiocarbon dating techniques. AMS or Accelerator Mass Spectrometry, which is a powerful analytical technique used for the determination of the abundance of the isotopes present in a sample. The measurement of the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) of ions is the fundamental principle of AMS. •••Mass-to-charge ratios separate ions using a magnetic field. Detection and identification of specific isotope. Acceleration of ions to high energies.

- The exceptional precision of the measurement of trace amounts of isotopes. AMS in radiocarbon dating measures the carbon-14 (C-14) to carbon-12 (C-12) ratio to determine the sample's age.

The AMS is a primary instrument, and processes such as various chemical and laboratory techniques are also involved to ensure the accuracy of the measurements. The background subtraction, calibration against the known standards, and potential contamination correction. The use of AMS and radiocarbon dating helps in the determination of age of organic materials, the investigation of historical timelines, the estimation of time of death and more in forensic work.

Reliability:

- The rate of C-14 decay is well established and constant over time, so radiocarbon dating is highly reliable.
- The wide range of forensic scenarios can be covered as the method can date up to around 50,000 years old materials. As this is non-destructive to the samples used, multiple tests can be done if needed.

Relevance in Forensic Research:

- For establishing the time of death, helping to refute or confirm alibis, and determining the age of the human remain, radiocarbon dating can be crucial for forensic investigators.
- Radiocarbon dating can aid in the solving of cold cases and can provide valuable information where historical records are in less number. Forensic experts can build a timeline of events, aiding in the reconstruction of crimes by dating materials found at the crime scene.
- The potential leading to the identification of the cases involving unidentified remain, the insights on historical context can be provided with the help of radiocarbon dating.

Advancements in Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) for forensic science include:

- Calibration advancements. •Historical Records authentication. •Resolution of cold cases. •Better solving of cases is done with these advancements in this

techniques

RADIO CARBON DATING

COLLECTION OF SAMPLE

ISOTOPES OF CARBON

CONCLUSIONS

- From the poster, we can conclude that the application of radiocarbon dating has moved beyond its archeological roots to solve the modern mysteries, while history can also be illuminated together with this.
- The precision, adaptability, and potential to transform forensic science to bridge the gap between the past and the present, truth and mystery can be highlighted due to its long term relevance in applications.
- Recent advances in this technique have also played an important role in forensic science investigations.
- This poster lays the groundwork for a thorough examination and understanding the application of radiocarbon dating technique in the field of forensic science.

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We would like to express our sincere gratitude and appreciation to Miss. Pooja Rawat, for her able guidance and support in completing our poster. Last but not the least, we would like to acknowledge our faculty of Vivekananda Global University for giving us this opportunity.

The Effectiveness of Different Drug Treatment Program for Offender

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INTRODUCTION

- Substance abuse often leads to criminal behavior, posing a challenge for global criminal justice systems. To tackle this, diverse offender drug treatment programs aim to reduce reoffending and promote rehabilitation.
- Drug treatment programs for offenders vary, including residential rehab, outpatient counseling, medication-assisted treatment, and cognitive-behavioral therapy. Identifying the most effective approaches is vital for better outcomes in the criminal justice system.
- In the upcoming sections, we'll explore the various drug treatment programs, their objectives and methods, and assess their real-world effectiveness through empirical evidence.
- By doing so, we hope to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on how best to address the complex issue of substance abuse among offenders and promote their reintegration into society.
- Ultimately, the aim is to inform policy decisions and support the development of more effective, evidence-based interventions within the criminal justice system.
- The data and insights presented will contribute to an ongoing dialogue about how best to address the intersection of substance abuse and criminal behavior, with the ultimate goal of promoting safer communities and aiding the reintegration of offenders into society.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This research employed a retrospective, cross-sectional design to assess the effectiveness of different drug treatment programs for offenders.

THEORETICAL ASPECT

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Preventing and Treating Substance Abuse Among Offenders

- **Prevention**
 - Education and Awareness: Teaching about the dangers of drugs has been effective in stopping some offenders from using them.
 - Early Intervention: Identifying problems early and helping people cope can prevent drug abuse from getting worse.
 - Family and Community Support: When families and communities are involved, it can help prevent drug problems and support recovery.
 - Holistic Approaches: Addressing problems like poverty, mental health, and education can prevent people from turning to drugs.
- **Treatment**
 - Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT): This therapy helps people change the way they think and learn coping skills to avoid using drugs.
 - Medication-Assisted Treatment (MAT): For opioids and alcohol, medications can reduce cravings and withdrawal, supporting recovery.
- Rehabilitation and Reintegration: Programs that teach skills and provide education and job training are crucial for helping people build better lives.
- Continuum of Care: Support and therapy should continue after release to keep people from returning to drug use and crime.
- **Combining Prevention and Treatment:**
 - Early Help: Find those at risk early and give them the support they need, both for prevention and treatment.
 - Family and Community Involvement: Involve families and communities in both preventing drug problems and helping those in recovery.
 - Personalized Approaches: Understand that everyone is different and tailor programs to meet individual needs for the best results.

CONCLUSIONS

- Preventing and treating substance abuse among offenders is a complex challenge that requires a combination of strategies.
- Education and awareness programs, early intervention, family and community support, and holistic approaches are essential for preventing drug abuse in this population. Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT), Medication-Assisted Treatment (MAT), rehabilitation, and a continuum of care are vital elements of effective treatment.
- To achieve the best results, it's crucial to integrate prevention and treatment efforts.
- This means identifying issues early, involving families and communities, and offering personalized solutions based on individual needs.
- By combining these approaches, we can reduce substance abuse and improve the lives of offenders, promoting their successful reintegration into society while minimizing the risk of recidivism.
- Effective prevention and treatment strategies not only save lives but also reduce the societal and economic costs associated with substance abuse among offenders. A comprehensive, individualized approach that combines these efforts is essential for a healthier and safer society.

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Cognitive Behavioral Theory

Identification Of Pug Marks

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INTRODUCTION

- Pug marks are unique footprints left by large carnivores and can be used as an identification tool to distinguish between individual animals of the same species.
- Pug marks help forensic experts determine the species of animal responsible for a particular set of tracks, aiding in wildlife management and conservation efforts.
- By studying pug marks, researchers can gain insights into the behavior of animals, such as their hunting strategies, territorial boundaries, and movement patterns.
- Forensic experts use pug marks to create geographic profiles of animal populations, which can assist in wildlife monitoring and management.
- Pug marks are crucial in efforts to protect endangered species by monitoring their populations and understanding their habits and habitats.
- Analyzing pug marks can help identify areas of human-wildlife conflict, enabling authorities to take appropriate measures to minimize these conflicts.
- Pug marks play a role in forensic investigations of wildlife crimes, such as poaching and illegal animal trade.
- Wildlife agencies maintain databases of pug marks to assist in tracking and identifying individual animals over time.
- Scientists and researchers use pug marks to study animal populations, migratory patterns, and ecological impacts, contributing to a better understanding of ecosystems.
- Pug mark analysis is employed in legal proceedings to provide evidence of wildlife-related crimes and support convictions, helping enforce wildlife protection laws.

Forensic Application

Forensic Application

Species Identification

Individual Identification

Behaviour Analysis

Geographic Profiling

Conservation

Measuring the Pug Marks

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

There are three techniques to identify the pugmarks.

PIP – PIP is a pug impression pads. They are laid along routes where tiger and leopard are likely to move or where they are known to frequent. PIP is a patch of dusty earth created manually for getting good pug impressions. A PIP is 2m long the length of the track and covers the entire width. A PIP is large enough to allow the registration of 3 to 4 pugmark. The soil used for making the PIP should preferably be from the same surrounding area.

CASTING- casting is another method to trace the pugmark. In this plaster of Paris is used. First water and then add pop in the mug and stir it well and after that pour it on the pugmark encircled with the aluminum strip.

Form 'D'- Form 'D' is a technique in which we use a sheet to trace the pugmark. It is 25 CMS *20cm glass or plastic with 2cm broad wooden frame. For height adjustment, corner screws can be provided. Flat pebbles or sticks can also be used

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, pug marks are not merely imprints left by wildlife but are invaluable tools with a multi-faceted significance in the realms of wildlife conservation and forensic science. These distinctive footprints aid in the identification of species and, in some cases, individual animals, helping researchers and conservationists monitor and protect endangered or threatened species. Pug marks offer insights into animal behavior, which is crucial for developing effective conservation strategies that align with natural instincts. Moreover, pug marks play a pivotal role in human-wildlife conflict resolution by identifying the culprits, understanding their behavior, and establishing patterns of movement. Through the use of pug marks, authorities and communities can implement targeted solutions to mitigate conflicts and promote harmonious coexistence between humans and wildlife. From crime scene investigations to conservation efforts, pug marks are an indispensable resource, contributing to the protection of wildlife, the preservation of ecosystems, and the enforcement of wildlife protection laws. Their significance extends beyond the visible footprint, making them a vital component in the fascinating and essential fields of wildlife science and conservation.

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How to place the trace on pugmark

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON CHEMICAL WARFARE AGENT

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INTRODUCTION

Weapons of mass destruction have been utilized for a very long time. In this regard, humans have invented several forms of chemical warfare agents for use in a variety of contexts, including personal or political agendas, power struggles between countries, terrorism, and other forms of warfare that have been used since the beginning of the world wars. Numerous organizations utilized it since it was simple to obtain, could be used in small amounts to cause significant damage and large casualties, and was also difficult to detect. As per the time we were founding different types of warfare agents, which are more dangerous and brutal than the old ones, very little has been found on the treatment of the warfare agents; in many cases, there was no antidote or basic treatment present for chemical warfare. There are many types of agents present based on their target system (as a particular organ of the body) such as Nerve agent, Blood agent, Blister agent, Pulmonary agent, RIOT Control agent, Incendiary agents, Toxic Industrial chemicals or and Biological toxins, We will compare their lethal dose, route of administration, effects and treatment.

Mechanism of action of different warfare agent's

Ricin:-

- It which can easily be produced from the beans of "*Ricinus communis*".
- Active principle:- It consists of two chains, Chain A with the catalytically active N-glycosidase and lectin based (it has ability to inhibit the synthesis of proteins in cells leading to cell death because of its toxicity), Chain B which is supportive for cellular uptake

Sarin:-

- The strong organophosphorus (OP) nerve agent sarin (GB, O-isopropyl methylphosphonofluoridate) inhibits acetylcholinesterase (AChE) irreversibly. Acetylcholine (ACh) then accumulates in the central nervous system (CNS), causing seizures and, at high doses, centrally mediated respiratory arrest.

Hydrogen Cyanide:-

- It is a colorless, extremely poisonous.
- Cytochrome oxidase inhibition, which inhibits cells from using oxygen

Tear gas:-

- The compound 2-chlorobenzalmalononitrile is, a cyanocarbon, is the defining component of tear gas commonly referred to as CS gas.

Phosgene:-

- It is harmful through two separate processes: acylation and hydrolysis. When phosgene comes into contact with water in the respiratory tract, it hydrolyzes into hydrogen chloride and carbon dioxide, which is the first process.

Anthrax toxin:-

- The toxin components are assembled complexes that are endocytosed. The toxin's enzymatic components move into the target cell's cytoplasm in the endosome. Once in the cytosol, the toxin's enzymatic components impair cellular communication and cell motility as well as other immune cell functions.

COMPARISON

Detection Techniques:-

The sensitivity, specificity, speed, and mobility of advanced detection techniques for chemical warfare agents have substantially improved allowing precise and prompt identification of these dangerous compounds. Ion Mobility Spectrometry (IMS), Raman Spectroscopy, Fluorescence Spectroscopy, Electrochemical Sensors, Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA), Surface Plasmon Resonance (SPR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), Ion-Selective Electrodes (ISEs), and Infrared Spectroscopy are some of the most important advanced techniques. These technologies enable quick and accurate detection of chemical warfare agents, which is essential for efficient reaction and mitigation. They offer several methods of evaluating chemical substances and their interactions. Multiple approaches combined with downsizing developments further improve detection capabilities, making them suited for on-site investigation, particularly in difficult field situations.

Agent	Lethal dose\ Mode of administration	Sign and symptoms	Detection Technique\ Treatment
Ricin	Can be inhaled, ingested, or injected. As few as five to ten micrograms per kilogram can be lethal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty breathing • Fever • Vomiting • Abdominal pain • Inhalation- Respiratory distress • Injection- redness, itching, necrosis 	Testing of body fluids, tissue or environmental samples for detection Treatment- Medication to manage symptoms and respiratory support or ventilator assistance.
Sarin	It is lethal to 50 percent of exposed individuals at doses of 100 to 500 mg across the skin.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blurred vision • excessive sweating, Nausea • muscle twitching, confusion • Convulsion, Paralysis • loss of consciousness • Respiratory failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection- Testing of blood, urine, or body fluids and techniques like MS and GS. • Treatment- antidote like Atropine and pralidoxime chloride and providing oxygen and ventilation.
Hydrogen Cyanide	Concentration of 300 mg/m ³ in air will kill a human as consider as lethal dose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dizziness • Chest pain • Seizures • Cardiac arrest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection- Blood test for to measure cyanide levels and analysis of other body fluids • Treatment- administering antidotes as hydroxocobalamin, and Sodium thiosulfate for detoxification of cyanide.
Tear gas	It is extremely toxic, oral lethal dose ranges from 5 to 50 mg kg ⁻¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Burning sensation in eye, skin • Redness and swelling of eyes • chest tightness • eye, respiratory, and skin irritation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection - Can be detect by audio analysis, it emits an audio signature • Treatment- rinse your eyes with water until there is no longer any sign of it. Poisoning by riot control agents has no known cure. Standard burn care methods, such as the application of medicated bandages, are used to treat burn injuries to the skin.
Phosgene	It is colorless oxidant gas. lethal exposure is 500 ppm/min.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coughing • sore throat • Irritation in eye and respiratory tract • watery eyes • burning and itching in eyes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detection- using High Performance Liquid Chromatography detection can be done (air) • Treatment- It entails giving supportive medical treatment in a hospital setting and eliminating phosgene from the body as quickly as possible. There is no cure for phosgene.

Phosphorous weapons used by Israel in Palestine

Figure:- Phosphorus weapon used by Israel.

CONCLUSIONS

- The comparison of chemical warfare weapons demonstrates a wide range of dangerous compounds that are classed according to their effects and chemical characteristics.
- Nerve agents, like Sarin and VX, target the nervous system and can be lethal even in small doses.
- Blister agents, including Sulfur Mustard, cause severe skin, eye, and respiratory irritation and damage.
- Blood agents like Hydrogen Cyanide interfere with oxygen utilization in the body.
- Choking agents like Chlorine damage the respiratory system, causing difficulty in breathing.
- Riot control agents, like Pepper Spray, cause temporary irritation to the eyes, nose, and skin.
- It is essential for preparation and response to probable chemical warfare situations to comprehend the traits and effects of these agents. It emphasizes the significance of global efforts to forbid the development, stockpiling, and use of these destructive weapons, such as the Chemical Weapons Convention (CWC). To minimize possible harm and guard against the disastrous effects of chemical warfare agents on human lives and the environment, effective detection, monitoring, and reaction tactics are needed.

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Figure:- How agent effect inside the cell.

Lost in the Abyss: Study of Asphyxial Drowning

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INTRODUCTION

"Drowning" is a potentially life-threatening event that occurs when an individual's airway becomes submerged in water or another liquid, impeding the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide. Risk factors for drowning include alcohol use, drug use, epilepsy, minimal swim training or a complete lack of training, and, in the case of children, a lack of supervision.

The key aspects of drowning, including its epidemiology, risk factors, prevention strategies, and the physiological mechanisms involved in the drowning process.

- 90% of drownings take place in freshwater and 10% take place in seawater
- Alcohol is involved in approximately 50% of fatal drownings, and 35% of non-fatal drownings.
- drowning rate for African Americans above the age of 29 between 1999 and 2010 was significantly higher
- Breath-hold under voluntary control until the urge to breathe due to hypercapnia
- Cerebral anoxia stops breathing and aspiration
- Cerebral injury due to anoxia becomes irreversible

DIAGNOSIS AND METHODS

- The diagnostic of drowning is described in the literature as one of the most difficult in the field of forensic medicine (Piette & De letter, 2006).
- The main goal in this field is to differentiate a death by submersion from a immersion of a body.
- It is important to remind that the death by drowning is defined as a death due to submersion in a liquid and the mechanism in acute drowning is hypoxemia and irreversible cerebral anoxia.
- The external signs of drowning influence the process of decomposition that are peculiar to immersion. The body surface is usually pallid. Face becomes bloated and body gets discolored with the progress of decomposition and as a result identification becomes impossible.
- The internal signs of drowning depicts that the lungs due to squeezing out of blood show pale grey appearance owing to compression of the vessels in the interalveolar septa by the trapped air and water in the alveoli.
- There are some histological contributions too which shows how the process of drowning and the medium in which it takes place. In addition to the lungs, liver, cardiac muscle and kidneys may also be examined for signs of acute oxygen deficiency and asphyxiation.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

DISCUSSION.

- According to the National Crime Records Bureau, there were 36,362, drowning deaths reported in 2021 in India, with children being particularly vulnerable.
- Boys at higher risk of drowning than girls.
- Limited access to safe water increases more drowning.
- People who are unable to swim also are at risk of drowning.
- Modell (1968) reviewed the mechanism of drowning and suggested that about 10% of victims of drowning do not aspirate water but die of asphyxia due to laryngospasm
- It has also been seen that the rate of atypical drowning is more than typical drowning. In classical drowning cases, there might be more drowning signs which gradually decelerate the drowning process.
- Cobbett et al. reported concomitant diagnoses which probably led to the death of the person for 38.2% of their autopsy cases of drowning
- I. The latest WHO Global Health estimates indicate that almost 236,000 people lost their lives to drowning in 2019. Just over 50% of these deaths occur among those aged under 30 years and drowning is the sixth leading cause of death worldwide for children aged 5-14 years.
- II. Highest drowning rates occur among children aged 1-4 years, followed by children aged 5-9 years globally.

RESULTS

- Drowning is a leading cause of death for youngsters nowadays all over the world
- More children ages 1-4 die from drowning than any other cause of death.
- For children ages 5-14, drowning is the second leading cause of unintentional injury death after motor vehicle crashes.
- For every child under age 18 who dies from drowning, another 7 receive emergency department care for non-fatal drowning.
- Nearly 40% of drowning treated in emergency departments require hospitalization or transfer for further care (compared with 10% for all unintentional injuries).
- Drowning injuries can cause brain damage and other serious outcomes, including long-term disability.
- People who have got certain medical conditions such as autism and heart conditions may have a higher risk of drowning.
- Drowning in the bathtub is the most common for people who have been suffering with seizure disorders.
- Drowning can also lead to emotional and psychological stresses in the case of both the victim and the witness, mostly the cases which involve children.

Fig: "Officials attempting to reconstruct events of a case through dumping a crude dummy in the sewerage pipeline. The case pertains to death of a lady constable"

CONCLUSIONS

CONCLUSION

- Drowning is one of the leading causes of death of children, youngsters and adults around the world under the age of 25 years where the number of males are twice the number of females. One of the major cause of drowning is the flash floods or flood disasters that mostly occur during the rainy season. Another reason behind the cases of drowning is the lack of parental supervision. In many cases, we see that when both the parents are busy with their respective chores, they leave their child to play out and as a result lack of their attention leads to a hazardous incident. So, it is advised to all the parents not to leave their child all alone even if when they are too busy. Next, drowning cases are also associated with alcohol consumption of the adults. So during swimming or any other activity related to water the person is advised not to drink alcohol or inhale any thing which makes them inebriated. And lastly, if anybody happens to drown in the water then it does not mean that you can only save them by going in the water too, but by acting quickly, by calling for help, by throwing a floating object, by using a life-jacket.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Asphyxia leads to relaxation of the airway, which permits the lungs to take in water in many individuals. We acknowledge the devastating and often preventable loss of life due to drowning. Drowning is a tragic event that can affect individuals of all ages, backgrounds, and abilities. It is a reminder of the importance of water safety education and awareness. Our thoughts go out to the victims and their families who have been affected by this heartbreaking event. We also express our gratitude to the dedicated first responders, lifeguards, and organizations that work tirelessly to prevent drowning incidents and save lives. This acknowledgment emphasizes the seriousness of drowning, expresses sympathy for the victims and their families, and encourages a collective effort to prevent future incidents through education and awareness.

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FIG: SIGN OF DROWNING

FIG: DROWNING DEATH

Complexities Of Crime: Navigating The Interplay Of Mental Disorders

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INTRODUCTION

- Crime is a word that has been defined by several people over the years each similar but different to each other. A criminal, however, cannot simply be defined as someone who commits a crime or is somehow related to the crime. One such example is the law regarding underage offenders. In India, anyone younger than eight is not convicted and deemed a criminal and in England, children younger than 10 are held incapable of criminal intent. These ages vary throughout different cultures but there is a version of this law in almost every nation of the world.
- Another such example of this law is the not guilty by reason of insanity clause. When an offender is convicted, they are declared to have committed the crime while being sound of mind. Thus, if an offender is said to be not guilty due to insanity, they were not aware of the quality of the act they were committing due to specific mental disorders plaguing them. Such offenders are referred for therapeutic disposal on health grounds and not punitive disposal in response to criminal grounds.
- There are several mental disorders that cause a person's basic instincts of wrong and right to become skewed. In such cases, the offenders are processed different than normal and given increased access to medical and mental healthcare facilities.

MENTAL DISORDERS AND CRIME

- Mental disorders can be identified by a set of signs and symptoms that cause a significant clinical distress or impairment in an individual's functioning.
- Mental disorder and crime are interrelated to each other but are individual concepts. Due to research about the link between mental disorders and crime heavily relying on people such as psychiatric patients and prison inmates, people being at risk of committing violent and criminal acts. This selection bias has led to the overestimation of the link between mental health and criminal and violent acts when in fact, individuals facing criminological factors such as substance abuse, socio-economic challenges etc. are much more prone to committing criminal and violent acts.
- There have been findings that suggest that only a fraction of violent offenders and only a small percentage of societal violence and criminal behavior constitute individuals diagnosed with mental disorders. This suggests that while mental disorders might impact criminal behavior and offenders in some cases, it doesn't particularly have a direct link to crime (other than psychopathy).
- Despite this, stereotypes still persist that associate violent behavior and mental disorder due to the way it is portrayed by mass media. Mass media has portrayed every violent offender as somebody plagued by a mental disorder, implying that majorly violent crimes are usually committed by individuals having mental illnesses.

DISCUSSION

There are several mental disorders that have an accompanying risk of violence along with it.

- **Substance Abuse Disorder:**
Substance abuse disorder is by far the most violent even compared to comorbid major mental illnesses. Substance abuse disorders are usually accompanied by several distinct comorbid conditions such as personality disorders, most prominently antisocial disorders. Additionally, depressive disorders, anxiety disorders may also accompany it. Each of these disorders invariably compromises the impulse control and emotional regulations of the affected, but in varying degrees. The most extreme acts of violence, some subtypes of murder or suicide have been linked to the clinical configuration of depression, antisocial disorder and substance abuse.
- **Personality Disorder:**
Studies have presented a strong evidence of personality disorders representing a significant risk of violent behavior. Paranoid, narcissistic and passive-aggressive personality disorder symptoms are correlated to violent behavior. Notably, narcissistic injury plays a role in the prodigious rates of violence in individuals defined as psychopaths. Hare, who was arguably the founding father of contemporary study of psychopathy, described narcissism as central intrapersonal fact, that along with antisocial behavior formed psychopathy.
- **Schizophrenia Spectrum Disorder:**
It is acknowledged that people with schizophrenia are significantly more likely to be violent than the common person. But it is a much less known fact that societal violence when compared to schizophrenic violence is significantly less. It has also been found that with time, psychotic symptoms, exclusive of paranoia, might be associated with lower levels of violence over time as assessed in recidivism rates, especially in individuals.
- **Chronic Psychosis:**
Psychosis is a combination of symptoms resulting in an impaired relationship with reality. It can be a symptom of serious mental health disorders. People who are experiencing psychosis may have either hallucinations or delusions. Hallucinations are sensory experiences that occur within the absence of an actual stimulus. In other words, hallucinations cause individuals to see things that aren't actually there. Individuals experiencing psychosis may also face loss of motivation and social isolation. They may also cause people to hurt themselves or others.

CONCLUSIONS

Numerous studies have indicated a disproportionate representation of individuals with mental illnesses within the criminal justice system, fostering the misconception that certain manifestations of mental disorders are criminalized. This misconception arises from two primary factors. Firstly, symptoms of severe mental illnesses have been implicitly treated as criminal offenses, leading to the incarceration of individuals displaying psychiatric symptoms. Secondly, these symptoms have been demonstrated to be motivating factors or causes behind criminal behavior. Additionally, research suggests that individuals with mental illnesses face an elevated risk of engaging in violent offenses, which might also be recurrent. When examining the root causes of crime, perspectives diverge based on the expertise of the observer. Criminologists offer varied explanations rooted in psychology or sociology. In contrast, the general public often attributes criminal behavior to the offender's mental state, characterizing them as "not right in the head." This perception is partly influenced by media portrayals, with criminals, especially those involved in heinous crimes, frequently labeled as psychopaths or sociopaths. While there are mental disorders, such as schizophrenia, that may contribute to violent impulses, statistical data indicate that individuals with mental illnesses are less likely to be repeat offenders compared to those influenced by substances, residing in lower socio-economic conditions, or affected by other criminological factors. The nuanced relationship between mental disorders and criminal behavior, emphasizes that while mental illnesses do play a role, they are not the primary determinant compelling individuals with these disorders to commit crimes. Generalizing behavior solely based on mental illness is inherently complex and calls for a more nuanced understanding of the intricate interplay between mental health and criminality.

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SYMPTOM

MOOD

DIAGNOSIS

CHILDHOOD TRAUMA AND ITS MENTAL EFFECT

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INTRODUCTION

The term "child trauma" describes a terrifying, perilous, violent, or potentially fatal incident that affects children (0–18 years of age). This type of incident might also affect a person your child knows, and your child may be affected if they witness the other person's harm or injury or hear about it from others. Youngsters may feel very overwhelmed, upset, or helpless when these kinds of things happen. Anybody can have these kinds of experiences at any age and at any moment, but not all of them are painful. Rapid growth and development of the brain occur in children, particularly in the first three years. Early trauma can have an impact on a child's development. Additionally, it may hinder their capacity for strong attachment, particularly if the trauma they experience involves a carer. Trauma from the past can have a big impact on someone's present and future experiences. They could have trouble maintaining focus or curiosities, or they might become sidetracked by reactions to traumatic reminders. They could have deficiencies in their capacity for abstract thought and language development. Many kids who have undergone profound trauma have learning issues that might call for assistance in the classroom. Relationship skills and brain function can both be significantly impacted by adverse childhood experiences (ACES). Even though some studies have suggested that life changes like divorce, widowhood, or employment changes can affect how people behave, these impacts have only ever been weakly suggested by other research.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Strategies for Addressing Childhood Trauma While the effects of childhood trauma can be long-lasting, multiple strategies are available to those who've experienced trauma, allowing them to address their trauma, recover from it and live a healthy life. Mental health professionals, including psychiatric nurse practitioners, can work with their patients to identify the best recovery strategies. Counseling - One way to deal with childhood trauma is to speak with a counselor or therapist. Those who've gone through trauma often internalize blame and guilt, potentially leading to low self-esteem. A counselor can help patients allocate blame more judiciously, develop the skill sets required for self-compassion, and learn other skills to grapple with weighty or complicated emotion. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy - Following a traumatic episode, children sometimes develop negative behavioral or emotional responses as a way to cope with their trauma. Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) is an evidence-based approach to unlearning these negative responses, training the brain to deal with trauma, stress, and grief in a healthier, more productive way. Meditation - Mindfulness meditation may not be the best solution for everyone, but in some cases, it can provide an opportunity to increase present-moment awareness, as opposed to constantly dwelling on the past. Additionally, mindfulness meditation may increase self-compassion and also improve the individual's ability to self-regulate (that is, the ability to keep one's emotions in check). Medication - In some cases, a psychiatric nurse practitioner or other medical professional may recommend medications to help cope with some of the effects of childhood trauma. Antianxiety medications and antidepressants may both be viable options, depending on the patient's specific symptoms.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

(SAMHSA) estimates that two-thirds of all children report some kind of

- PTSD in children can lead to depression, suicidal behavior, substance use, and oppositional or defiant behaviors well into adulthood, which can affect their ability to succeed in school, and create and nurture important relationships.
- Offending behavior might have a complicated and diverse relationship with childhood trauma. It's crucial to highlight that not everyone who experiences trauma will go on to commit crimes, despite research suggesting that those who have suffered childhood trauma are more likely to engage in a variety of violating behaviors. Several factors can affect the link between childhood trauma and criminal behavior: Childhood trauma, which includes physical, sexual, and emotional abuse as well as neglect and exposure to violence, can have a significant psychological impact. Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, anxiety, and personality problems are among the conditions it may cause. These circumstances might make it more likely for someone to commit a crime.
- Disrupted Attachment: Adolescent trauma can sabotage secure attachments between children and their carers. This disruption can impair social and emotional growth, making it more difficult for people to build wholesome relationships and practice prosocial conduct. Social Environment: Growing up in unfavorable social conditions, such as poverty or areas with high crime rates, is frequently linked to childhood trauma. Due to the lack of possibilities and susceptibility to criminal influences, these circumstances may make engagement in crime more likely.
- Re-victimization: Some people who have undergone childhood trauma may be at risk of being victims again, making them more susceptible to other forms of victimization, such as criminal victimization. Early intervention and access to therapeutic treatments can help to lessen the impact of childhood trauma and lower the likelihood of criminal behavior. Relationships of care and support with kind adults can also operate as protective factors.
- Unpredictable emotions, flashbacks, relationship problems and physical symptoms like headaches or nausea are some of the ways that unresolved trauma can manifest, according to the American Psychological Association.
- Unhealed trauma can lead to a variety of mental health challenges in adulthood, including depression, anxiety, and addiction. By understanding the link between childhood wounds and mental health in adulthood, we can learn how to start the process of healing trauma and achieve a healthier, happier life.
- The understanding of such incidents is especially complex for a child, who lacks the brain capacity of adults. Children have a harder time with or lack of education, socialization, life experience than adults. They often fall into the pit of self-blame, unable to comprehend the causes and consequences of these distressing events.
- The understanding of such incidents is especially complex for a child, who lacks the brain capacity of adults. Children have a harder time with or lack of education, socialization, life experience than adults. They often fall into the pit of self-blame, unable to comprehend the causes and consequences of these distressing events.
- Childhood trauma physically damages the brain by triggering toxic stress. Strong, frequent, and prolonged, toxic stress rewires several parts of the brain, altering their activity and influence over emotions and the body.
- Trauma-induced changes to the brain can result in varying degrees of cognitive impairment and emotional dysregulation that can lead to a host of problems, including difficulty with attention and focus, learning disabilities, low self-esteem, impaired social skills, and sleep disturbances

Being introvert

Fear of other people

CONCLUSIONS

- Victims of childhood trauma have low self-esteem and struggle with sadness and anxiety. Some people try to avoid the effects of their traumatic events on their lives by denying their past of trauma, while others fabricate their identities and abuse alcohol and other drugs. Along with adequate and individualized therapy approaches, early interventions can lessen the effects of trauma.
- Research has repeatedly demonstrated that some traumatic situations are more likely to produce symptoms, cause more discomfort, and have longer-lasting posttraumatic consequences than others. Because of its consequences on child development and psycho-relational health, cumulative childhood interpersonal trauma, for example, is the type of traumatic event that is most strongly linked to later troubles.
- Interpersonal trauma in childhood is linked to a higher risk of mental health issues throughout adulthood, such as posttraumatic stress disorder, eating disorders, depression, anxiety, suicidality, and substance abuse. In the long run, these psychological issues may develop into chronic conditions that impair relational and professional performance, increase the risk of suicide, and reduce social engagement.
- It was discovered that traumatic experiences in childhood were linked to criminal behavior. The inclination to be violent was significantly correlated with childhood traumas, and childhood traumas had an impact on the tendency to be violent (11%).

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to extend our sincere and heartfelt gratitude towards THE DEPARTMENT OF FORENSIC SCIENCE and thereby giving us the opportunity to present this poster today in front of such eminent personalities. We are extremely indebted to Mr, Anshuman V. Ramani, our guide, for his constant guidance and support throughout the preparation of this poster, thereby helping us increase our knowledge on this poster.

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Trauma Affects

All Areas of a Child's Development

FORENSIC PSYCHOLOGY AND ITS IMPACT ON INSTANCES OF MILITARY RAPE

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INTRODUCTION

FORENSIC PSYCHOLOGY AND ITS IMPACT ON INSTANCES OF MILITARY RAPE:

- Forensic Psychology applied to law. Application of scientific knowledge help in answering legal questions arising in law enforcement is a forensic psychology.
- Military Rape is Sexual Assault or Rape occurs in the Armed Forces.
- It troubles in Physical & Psychological consequences for the victims.
- Forensic Psychology in military rape deal with awareness about sexual violence in armed force, depressed & anxious victims from assault cases & examines how the principles of psychology interact with the case of assault.
- It evaluates victims, witness, an alleged perpetrator & playing role of therapist.
- Military courts-martial offer a unique environment where the fields of psychology and law intersect.
- With an increasing number of cases involving sexual assault and intimate partner violence in the military, psychologists are playing an ever-expanding role in courts-martial.

- Forensic psychology aims to gain a deep understanding of the dynamics, causes, and consequences of sexual violence within the military.
- It also aim to provide emotional, psychological, and therapeutic support to survivors of military rape.
- Their goal is to help survivors cope with trauma, facilitate their recovery, and empower them to seek justice if they choose to do so.
- It work to assess the psychological profiles of individuals who commit sexual assault within the military.

METHODS:

1. Evidence Collection and Legal Proceedings: The aim is to assist law enforcement and legal professionals in collecting and preserving evidence related to military rape cases. This helps ensure that the legal process is well-informed and that perpetrators are held accountable for their actions.

2. Prevention and Education: Programs like developing and implementing prevention programs and educational initiatives within the military aim to reduce the incidence of military rape by promoting a culture of consent, respect, and intervention when necessary.

3. Policy and Reform:

- Forensic psychologists may also contribute to policy development and reform efforts within the military to address systemic issues related to sexual violence.
- Their expertise can lead to changes in military policies and procedures aimed at preventing and responding to rape more effectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

CASE STUDY: KASHMIR MASS RAPE

- The incident occurred on February 23, 1991, in the village of Kunan, located in the Indian-administered region of Kashmir.
- Women in the village, including Zooni and Zareena, shared harrowing experiences of sexual assault and violence by the soldiers.
- These women described how they were subjected to sexual violence, and their accounts are filled with pain and trauma.
- The people of Kunan and the neighboring village of Poshpora have accused the Indian army of orchestrating a mass rape of women and subjecting men to brutal torture during this incident. They have been seeking justice for these alleged atrocities for over 26 years.

- In recent years, a group of young Kashmiri women, along with Natasha Rathar, filed a petition to reopen the case in the state High Court. They believed that this significant case of mass rape, supported by substantial evidence, required a renewed investigation. After a challenging legal process, the Jammu and Kashmir High Court directed the state government to provide compensation to the victims, but the government later contested this decision in the Supreme Court of India, where the case remains pending.

The Indian Army has consistently denied the allegations, stating that the case has been independently investigated multiple times and closed due to conflicting statements.

- The truth of what transpired that night in Kunan and Poshpora remains elusive, and it is a deeply disturbing and unresolved chapter in the history of Kashmir. The case is significant not only for its historical implications but also for the new generation of Kashmiris who are determined to bring the truth to light despite the challenges and complexities of the legal process. The residents of Kunan and Poshpora continue to grapple with the painful memories of that night, even as the village and its inhabitants evolve with the passage of time

ANNUAL REPORTS

- The Department of Defence encourages greater reporting to promote more help-seeking by Service members and to hold alleged offenders appropriately accountable.
- In total, the Department received 8,942 reports of sexual assault involving Service members as victims and/or subjects in Fiscal Year 2022, an increase of 1 percent from the 8,866 received in Fiscal Year 2021. Of the 8,942, 5,941 were Unrestricted Reports of sexual assault and 3,001 remained Restricted at the end of the year. Of the 8,942 reports, 7,378 were from Service members reporting an incident that occurred to them during military service.
- This reflects a 1.6 percent increase from the 7,260 such reports received in 2021. The Military Departments reported case outcomes (dispositions) for 3,928 cases in Fiscal Year 2022. Of those 3,928 cases, military commanders had sufficient authority or jurisdiction to consider 3,188 cases for possible action against the accused.
- The evidence supported command action in 2,117 cases. Commanders were precluded from action or respected victims' desire to not further participate in the justice process in 1,031 cases. Forty of the 3,188 cases were determined to be unfounded.

Top army officer says women 'used by a nexus through a fake narrative.'

CONCLUSIONS

- The aim of forensic psychology in the context of military rape is to comprehensively address this complex issue by supporting survivors, assessing perpetrators, preventing future incidents, and contributing to the pursuit of justice.
- The ultimate goal is to create a safer and more accountable environment within the military while ensuring that survivors receive the care and support they need.
- The Fiscal Year 2022 Annual Report on Sexual Assault in the Military provides an update on Department of Defense efforts to counter sexual assault and sexual harassment in the military.
- The report includes sexual assault reporting information and military justice outcomes as required by Congress.
- This year, the report includes summaries of the steps taken to implement prevention and response initiatives and recommendations of the Independent Review Commission on Sexual Assault in the Military, as approved by the Secretary of Defense. The report covers Fiscal Year 2022.

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KUNAN POSHPORA: 30 years on, Survivors Await Justice

Recent Secretary of Defense Sexual Assault Prevention and Response Initiatives

MADANAPALLE DOUBLE MURDER CASE STUDY

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INTRODUCTION

- Two young, intelligent girls were discovered in blood pools in front and inside the puja room of their home.
- Lawyer claims that dumbbells were used by parents as Lord Shiva's damruks to murder their daughters.
- The brutal killing of two young girls in the Andhra Pradesh town of Madanapalle in the district of Chittoor by their biological parents.
- After enacting an act of worship at their place of residence on Sunday (24 January) night, Alekhya (27) and Sai Divya (22) were killed by their parents.
- Alekhya's body was discovered in a pool of blood inside puja room, while Sai Divya's body was discovered dead right in front of the puja room.
- Red saris draped both of the dead people's bodies. Their parents murdered them, then chopped piece of their hair and presented it to Lord Shiva. [3]
- The Women's Degree College in Madanapalle employed Purushottam Naidu, 55, an associated professor of chemistry with an MSc and PhD. He was also the vice-principal of the college.
- Padmaja (50), a gold medalist in mathematics and postgraduate. She spent 20 years at Master Mind IIT Talent School tutoring IIT students. [1]

HISTORY OF NAIDU FAMILY

- Padmaja was from Chittoor town, and Valleru Purushottam Naidu was from Kondraju Kalva in Thavanampalle mandal. Five years ago, they made Madanapalle their home town.
- Every single person in the Naidu family were highly educated. They had no money problems. They constantly urged their daughters to pursue their goals.
- The family, which had been residing in Prashant Nagar up until six months ago, moved to Siva Nagar on August 14, 2020 after constructing an opulent home there.
- They held a straightforward house-warming ceremony without any of their relatives because of the pandemic.
- They had been regularly engaging in pujas and rituals ever since the day they had moved into the property.
- The Naidu family took a few days off on January 23, 2021, for private matters. Their co workers claimed that the Naidu family intended to perform various rituals and that doing so would require a lot of time.
- Locals claimed that they had been carrying out rituals for over 4-5 days and that yells and screams occasionally came from the residence.

SHARED PSYCHOTIC DISORDER

- A rare disease known as shared psychotic disorder is characterised by the hallucination being shared by two or more people in a close connection. The inducer (primary), who suffers from psychotic disorders and delusions, exerts influence over one or more additional non-psychotic people (induced) based on their delusional beliefs.
- In this instance, Padmaja served as the host and shared the family's belief in rebirth. The children fully trusted their mother. As previously indicated, Sai Divya instructed her elder sister to kill the latter, hence she was gladly giving up her life in accordance with her mother's instructions.
- The terms "imposed psychosis," "simultaneous psychosis," "communicated psychosis," and "induced psychosis" refer to the four different types of shared psychotic disorders. [3]
- The original delusion(s) are typically shared by both the primary and secondary persons in a shared psychotic condition, which is typically chronic. The shared delusion(s) might take any form and can happen in a variety of situations. Persecutory and colossal delusions are the two most typical types of delusion.
- Every patient should receive a unique treatment plan. If a patient is receiving inadequate care, efforts should be made to promote greater adherence to the prescribed course of action. There have been claims that cutting ties with the primary greatly improves the situation. After admittance, the major partner's influence eventually fades away. It is important to keep in mind, though, that recent results indicate that separation may not always be sufficient or may even make the disease worse. The condition might be improved by administering medicine to both couples, either singly (antipsychotics or antidepressants) or in combination (mood stabilisers and antipsychotics and antidepressants and antipsychotics). Starting medicine denotes a serious ailment with a high likelihood of persistent symptoms. A potential other diagnosis necessitates close patient monitoring. [2]

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

ROLE OF POLICE

- The District Government Hospital received both bodies when the police sent them there to undergo autopsies.
- A case had been filed by the Madanapalle Taluq Police in accordance with IPC section 302.
- On January 26, the accused were brought before the Judicial Magistrate and put on remand. Padmaja and Purushottam Naidu were placed into separate cells at the Madanapalle Sub-Jail.
- The pair underwent a team of psychiatrists' (Dr Radhika, Dr Lakshmi Prasad and Dr Raja Rao) evaluation on January 27 at the request of jail superintendent Ramakrishna Yadav.
- The Magistrate granted the police approval to move the couple to Ruia Hospital in Tirupati on the advice of psychiatrists. [1]
- Both of them was admitted by the jail authorities to Visakhapatnam Government Hospital on the doctor's recommendation.
- On 29 March, the pair were brought back to the jail amid the surveillance of armed reserve police.

ROLE OF DOCTORS

- Bhaskar (the assistant who works in the post mortem ward at the government hospital in Madanapalle), claims that at the post-mortem, no food fragments were discovered in the stomachs of either of the two dead girls. Their tummies had dried up and were empty. Before being killed, it appeared that they had been fasting for at least three to four days, the attorney claimed.
- On February 3, the couple was transported with tight security to the Vizag Government Hospital.
- According to hospital authorities, the couple has received psychiatric medication and has completed a psychometric analysis test, as well as an abreaction treatment. [4]
- Doctors assessed the couple and came to the conclusion that everyone in the family had "Shared Psychotic Disorder".

STATEMENT OF PURUSHOTTAM NAIDU

- Purushottam Naidu claimed that both of his daughters had entered a total trance and had failed to effectively communicate with him. He claimed that Alekhya had been claiming to have mystical abilities, while Divya, the younger daughter, claimed that malevolent spirits were prowling the home.
- He claimed that his older daughter killed his younger daughter by hitting her with a trishul.
- Alekhya, who was dressed in crimson robes, claimed that shakti had gained control of her and stated that she needed to be slain since Satyuga would begin when Kalyuga ended. She also instructed them to do the rituals for her sister. [3]
- After doing naked pujas, all four members of the family were psychologically prepared to kill themselves one by one since they all felt they would be reborn in the Satyuga in a much purer form.
- Naidu claimed that he was supposed to ring the bell continually throughout the ritual, and that his wife struck their older daughter with a dumbbell after the puja.
- Despite the fact that the parents were also intended to die, the killing spree was stopped when Purushottam Naidu contacted one of his pals and admitted to killing both the parents' daughters after emerging from a spiritual trance. [4]

THE FAMILY PHOTO OF NAIDU FAMILY [5]

CONCLUSIONS

- A case was registered against them under IPC Section 302.
- The police were instructed to provide the parents with medical care in accordance with IPC Section 84.
- They continue to receive mental health care now. The couple reacted to treatment and showed regret for perpetrating the crime, according to hospital officials.
- Justice for the two daughters is still pending. The investigation is ongoing. Justice will be administered following the parents' full treatment, the court decided.
- Effective therapies for shared psychotic disorders are not well established due to their rarity. The shared psychotic disorder patient is typically treated by being isolated from other people. This lessens the effect on auxiliary individuals.

HIGHLIGHTING POINTS

- Dumbbells → Lord Shiva' Damruks
- Trident → Lord Shiva's Trishul
- From Prashant Nagar → Shifted to Siva Nagar

BREAKING NEWS

TWO SISTERS FOUND IN THE POOL OF BLOOD

PARENTS WHO USED DUMBBELLS TO KILL THE OWN DAUGHTERS

Well educated parents killed their daughters believing in reincarnation. They used dumbbells to represent Lord Shiva's Dumruk.

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THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CONSEQUENCES OF SEXUAL ASSAULT SURVIVORS

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INTRODUCTION

Rape has serious consequences, including psychological, physical, and reproductive costs. Fear and anxiety, posttraumatic stress disorder, depression, low self-esteem, social adjustment challenges, and sexual dysfunctions are among the topics addressed. According for many victims, seeking post-assault support becomes a "second rape," a secondary victimization of the initial trauma. In response to growing concerns about the community's response to rape, new treatments and programs aimed at improving services and preventing secondary victimization have evolved. Rape crisis centers, restorative justice programs, and sexual assault nurse examiner programs are investigated. Strategies for increasing the visibility and effect of psychologists and other associated professionals are also highlighted. The statistical procedure of multidimensional scaling was employed in the analysis of this data, which in turn produced a five-cluster model of serial rapist behavior.

THE ALARMING RISE OF RAPE

Rape is regarded as one of the most heinous crimes against the individual and his or her identity. The rising rate of crime against women in India has become a major issue for the government and its officials. It is critical to keep sexual violence against women under control. Women's status in Indian society has been steadily declining. Women in the pre-Vedic era gained equal rights and were treated similarly as males; the deterioration in women's standing in Indian society continues. The social and cultural structures of India have consistently subordinated women, and the legal system has traditionally regarded women as weak and passive, serving as a tool for women's subordination. The patriarchal worldview drives women to be naïve, feeling uncomfortable and susceptible to their male counterparts. [3] The goal of this study paper is to better understand demographic characteristics and their impact on sexual assault against women. Rape is considered the most severe form of sexual violence against women. A number of community outreach activities are being carried out by local authorities and administrative divisions to create public awareness about this heinous crime. The purpose of this research article is to discover the core reasons of such horrific acts, to provide a legal viewpoint in the Indian Criminal Justice System, and to enhance the mental health of rape survivors.

COUNSELLING SESSION OF A SEXUAL ASSAULT SURVIVORS

Phase 1: Assessment and education

Phase 2: Rapport and strengths

Phase 3: Cognitive intervention

Phase 4: Emotion focused

Phase 5: Trauma narrative

Implications and model tenets

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

RAPE TRAUMA

Rape is relatively seldom reported by girls and women globally due to the acute social, religious, and caste stigma or the fear of rejection by their family members or being subjected to violence and where premarital sex is banned or premarital sex can face prosecution before the laws. In India, rape is a notoriously under-reported crime. Because rape victims will face prosecution under current legislation, they must undergo protracted prosecution and inquiry. Even if there is adequate evidence to show a rape inside the court, they cannot obtain justice. [4] Recovery from sexual assault-related Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is not only defined by the absence of symptoms or the achievement of specified outcomes. Healing from this trauma does not imply that the survivor will forget the experience or will never feel any symptoms again. [1] Rather, successful recovery is subjective and measured by whether the survivor increases his or her involvement in the present, acquires skills and attitudes to regain control of his or her life, forgives himself or herself for guilt, shame, and other negative cognitions, and gains stress reduction skills for overall better functioning. [2] Many factors contribute to successful recovery, including the amount of support received, past self-concept, personal strength, and professional treatment provided by the medical and justice systems. PTSD is one of these. The psychology of each age group is different for each rape cases. Childhood sexual abuse sufferers were separated from nonvictims by a pattern of enhanced anxiety, heightened interpersonal sensitivity, greater anger problems, more paranoid ideation, and increased obsessive-compulsive symptoms. Many factors influence an individual's response to trauma, and psychological reactions differ widely amongst people. The 'meaning' that a victim assigns to the occurrence is likely to be crucial, as evidenced by the distinctions between stranger and acquaintance rape. It may be believed that the former would be significantly more traumatic, but research has revealed that rape victims experience similar degrees of sadness and greater difficulty when raped by their husband, that is, forced copulation between the partners. [5] Lack of mutual consent is present in all sexual assaults. The traditional triad of post-traumatic stress symptoms of haunting, intrusive recollections, numbing or restriction of sensations and focus, and lowered threshold of anxious arousal following severe anxiety, terror, and loss of control are all present. Anxiety, melancholy, phobic reactions to situations resembling sexual assault, sexual dysfunction, decreased social adjustment, and diminished capacity to enjoy life are long-term repercussions.

8 YEAR OLD GIRL GANGE RAPED [6]

CONCLUSIONS

CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM FOR RAPE CASE IN INDIA

Rape is a cognizable offence in India. There are so many provisions in different Acts for rape. Section 375, 376A, 376B, 376C and 376D of Indian Penal Code 1860. Section 53(1)[4], 164A [5], 327(2)6 of Code of Criminal Procedure. Section 114-A [3] of Indian Evidence Act. To raise awareness about the need of protecting girls children and ensuring that they have similar rights as boys. Give boys and females equal opportunities in society and respect girls/women. The study was carried out to examine the status of rape victims in today's criminal justice system in comparison to the previous one, as well as to identify any gaps in the new improvements. The paper gave opinions on India's criminal justice system. The report has recommended several policymakers to the government, NGOs, and social communities in order to reduce crime against women. Our constitution will include numerous safeguards to prevent and control crimes against women. As a result, through appealing programs, the media should play an essential role in raising legal and social awareness among young men and women. Society should also focus on changing its attitude toward young women, and they should be given more security and care. The government should also enforce harsh penalty, and the length of the judicial procedure should be decreased to discourage perpetrators from taking advantage of it.

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I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to Mr Anshuman V Ramani Professor, Vivekananda Global University, Jaipur and Ms Sahar Zehra Naqvi, Assistant Professor, Vivekananda Global University, Jaipur for invaluable guidance and support in creating the poster. Your expertise and dedication played a pivotal role in our success, and we are truly thankful for your mentorship. I would also like to extend our sincere thanks to Vivekananda Global University for providing us with this wonderful opportunity.

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मासूम सरप

बिचकर ले गया आरोपी, अरेस्ट

पता कि वह परिवार के जि इलाके में किराए पर ली में पति, दो बेटे और ति प्राइवेट जॉब करते हैं। करीब 5 बच्चे उनकी पांच र के बाहर खेल रही थी। उन्होंने पाया कि उनकी थी। वह बच्ची को खोजने

वह अपने दोस्तों के साथ खेल रही थी इसी दौरान अकल उसे खींचकर टॉइल में ले गए। वह चिल्लाने लगी तो अंक ने उसे कई थप्पड़ मारे। इस दौरान उ कह रोने लगी तो लोगों ने चीख-पुकार सुनकर दरवाजा तोड़ दिया और बा निकाला। महिला ने पुलिस कोल व वारदात की जानकारी दी, जो मासूम

On Death Row

गैंगरेप के बाद कार से कुचलकर हत्या रोहतक में निर्भया जैसी दरिंदगी

THE NEWS OF RAPE CASES ACROSS THE COUNTRY

THE IMPACT OF SEARCH ENGINES AND DATABASES IN FORENSIC STUDY

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INTRODUCTION

- Digital forensics is a technique of research used to find any suspicious or harmful activity that can be used as evidence in court.
- Database forensics is a branch of digital forensics that focuses on in-depth examination of a database's contents, logfiles, metadata, and data files.
- Identification, gathering, preservation, reconstruction, analysis, and reporting of database incidents are all part of database forensic investigation (DBFI).
- Database forensics, to put it simply, enables you to more thoroughly investigate breaches, discount a suspected intrusion, or confirm and precisely scope a breach to lessen its impact.

DATABASE FORENSIC TOOLS

- On database servers, a lot of sensitive information is stored. Therefore, a tool that can evaluate databases and the related metadata is highly sought after in forensic investigations.
- The SQL Log Analyzer, Exchange Log Analyzer, Database Scalpel, and db Investigator are some examples of database forensic tools.
- Relational database structures, which can handle simple transactions and are ideal for many commercial applications
 - Modern advanced database systems frequently require more complex functions and table joins.
- It is a useful method for building databases and one of the most popular ones currently in use.

SEARCH ENGINES IN FORENSIC STUDY

- A program that automatically searches a target network for references to specific IP addresses using the Google API
- A promising investigation tool is GooSweep.
- It can help network forensic investigators compile data on specific computers, including referral logs, guestbooks, spam blacklists, and server login instructions.
- GooSweep also offers insightful information on a suspect's online behaviors, such as surfing patterns and communications in online forums.

SEARCH ENGINE AND DATABASE EFFECTS ON FORENSIC RESEARCH

- Forensic investigators require access to search engines and databases. They assist us in quickly and readily finding the relevant data, which is essential in solving cases.
- The use of search engines in criminal investigations is extremely beneficial as it can reveal unknown or hidden information about people or places.
- Databases can be used to find people with links to specific businesses or industries. For instance, if we are aware of the identity of a suspect, we can search a database for their address to see whether it was connected to any previous crimes.
- With the combined use of search engines and databases, we can create a profile of the suspected person and circulate it among the department for investigative purposes.

TIMELINE OF CYBER FORENSICS

- Periodic table of cyber forensics
- Over the years, forensic research has grown significantly.
 - The portion of this study that is pertinent to forensic science is quite tiny.
 - Rarely does forensic science research progress past the proof-of-concept phases and into actual application.
 - If long-term issues in real life as well as fundamental forensic science concerns were addressed, research would be more beneficial.
 - Moving away from quantity and novelty and toward relevance and quality is the present issue.

IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL FORENSICS

- The process of using scientific methods and principles to examine electronically stored data and ascertain the series of events that lead to a certain occurrence is known as digital forensics.
- It is crucial for researchers in the digital era to be aware of the most recent advancements in this dynamic sector and to comprehend the potential for the future
- Significant technology breakthroughs that can help with a digital inquiry have occurred during the last ten years
- Numerous forensically based procedures, tools, and techniques have entered the sector.
- Innovative methods have been explored in digital forensics to gather and examine digital evidence from a variety of sources.
- We evaluate the research literature published since 2000 and divide field advancements into four main areas in this work.

CONCLUSION

- With the use of database forensics, you can more thoroughly look into Breaches, rule out a potential intrusion, or confirm and accurately scope a Breach to lessen its effects.
- As you can see, this science may be a potent tool in your toolbox for responding to breaches and can act as your organization's last line of protection.
- There are already more than 80 different commercial databases that are created in various languages. Each database platform, as well as the varied types and retention of artifacts dispersed within it, must be interacted with by investigators.
- With the use of database forensics, you can more thoroughly look into Breaches, rule out a potential intrusion, or validate and accurately scope a Breach to lessen its effects.
- This chapter's objective is not to turn you into a database.

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Cyber Attacks Statistics).

Fig.1. Major motivation of attacks (Source: Hackmageddon, (2018),

- After land, sea, and air, cyberspace is seen as a realm worth studying and researching.
- The sporadic rise in cybercrimes and cybercriminals is the main cause of this.
- The development of technology and the Internet has caused an increase in cybercrimes.
- By 2021, \$6 trillion in losses from cybercrime are expected to have been caused worldwide.
- However, it was the highest reported crime between 2016 and 2018.
- Cybercrime is the primary reason for assaults, accounting for 81.7% of all attack motivations, according to information security timelines and data (Fig.1).

Fig. 2. High level view of the proposed DLCF framework.

- This section offers a framework for integrating deep learning cognitive computing techniques into cyber forensics, often known as the DLCF framework, as a contribution to the discipline of cyber forensics.
- The DLCF framework's objective is to demonstrate the skills and talents that DL can contribute to the discipline of cyber forensics. This framework is presented using diagrams at a more general level in this section to follow.
- It uses a generic framework rather than going into great detail about them.

ECHOES OF PROGRESS: UNVEILING THE FUTURE OF VOICE RECOGNITION TECHNOLOGY

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INTRODUCTION

- Advancements in voice recognition technology have ushered in a new era of human-computer interaction, revolutionizing the way we communicate with our devices and systems. From basic speech recognition to sophisticated voice biometrics, these innovations have expanded the horizons of applications in various fields. This study provides an overview of the significant strides made in this dynamic field, highlighting the key features and potential implications of advanced voice recognition technology.
- In recent years, the convergence of artificial intelligence and deep learning has propelled voice recognition technology to unprecedented heights. Traditional systems have evolved from rule-based approaches to data-driven methods, allowing for more accurate and contextually aware speech understanding. Deep neural networks, with their ability to learn complex patterns in data, have become a cornerstone in achieving remarkable accuracy in speech recognition tasks.
- One of the most striking advances is the development of voice biometrics, which goes beyond mere speech recognition to authenticate individuals based on unique vocal characteristics. This has profound implications for security, authentication, and access control, finding applications in fields ranging from banking and finance to law enforcement and healthcare.

MATERIALS & METHODS

- High-Quality Microphones**
 - Sensitive microphones capable of capturing clear and accurate audio data are crucial for voice identification systems.
- Databases**
 - Extensive databases containing voice samples for training and testing the identification algorithms. These may include a diverse range of accents, languages, and emotional states.
- Computing Hardware**
 - High-performance computers or servers with powerful processors and ample memory are required for processing and analyzing voice data.
- Deep Learning Frameworks**
 - Advanced machine learning frameworks like TensorFlow or PyTorch are used to implement deep learning models for voice identification.
- Acoustic Models**
 - These models help in understanding the phonetic content and characteristics of speech, and are a crucial component of voice identification systems.
- Statistical Models**
 - These models may include Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), Hidden Markov Models (HMMs), or other statistical methods to analyze speech patterns.
- Feature Extraction Software**
 - Software tools that can extract relevant features from audio data, such as Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), spectral features, etc.
- Machine Learning Algorithms**
 - Various machine learning algorithms are used for tasks like classification, regression, clustering, etc., depending on the specific application within voice identification.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

- Preprocessing**
 - Noise reduction, filtering, and other preprocessing techniques to enhance the quality of the audio data.
- Feature Extraction**
 - Extracting relevant features from the audio signal, like MFCCs, to represent the speech signal in a form suitable for analysis.
- Training Data Preparation**
- Deep Learning Models**
 - Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), and variants like Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs) are employed to process audio data.
- Model Training**
 - Utilize large-scale computing resources to train the deep learning models on the prepared datasets. This involves optimizing parameters to achieve high accuracy.
- Testing and Evaluation**
- Post-Processing**
 - Techniques like speaker diarization, where multiple speakers are identified in an audio stream, can be used to refine results.
- Integration and Deployment**
 - Incorporate the voice identification system into the desired application, whether it's for authentication, virtual assistants, or other purposes.

Databases

- CommonVoice**
 - An open-source dataset provided by Mozilla, which consists of recordings of people reading sentences in multiple languages. It's used for training and validating speech recognition systems.
- Speaker Recognition Evaluation (SRE) datasets**
 - These datasets are used for speaker identification tasks in evaluations like NIST SRE. They include multiple recordings of speakers in various conditions.

Software

- Deep Learning Frameworks**:**
 - GoldWave**
 - It is a comprehensive digital audio editing software. While it's not primarily designed for voice recognition technology development, it can play a supporting role in certain aspects of the process. It can be used to preprocess audio data before it's fed into a voice recognition system. This may include tasks like noise reduction, filtering, and normalization to improve the quality of the input data. It can be used to visually inspect audio waveforms and spectrums. This visual information can help in the manual extraction of features, though automated tools are typically used for large-scale operations.
 - HashCalc**
 - It is a widely-used cryptographic hashing tool, primarily used for calculating and verifying hash values of files. It is not a software directly related to voice recognition systems, but it can still play a role in certain aspects of system security and data integrity. It can be used to generate and verify hash values for files related to a voice recognition system. This ensures that critical files (such as model weights, configuration files, etc.) have not been tampered with and can be used to generate and verify hashes for these weight files, providing a way to ensure their integrity during storage and transfer.

Result

With all new accomplishments in the last couple of years, and many that did not make it to our list due to shortage of space, there is still a lot more work to be done. Although incremental improvements are done everyday, in all branches of voice recognition since the channel and audio type mismatch seems to be biggest hurdle in reaching perfect results in voice recognition.

PROCESS OF VOICE RECOGNITION

CONCLUSIONS

- Speech recognition is evolving rapidly thanks to advances in deep learning, databases, and software tools. These systems have the potential to change the way we interact with technology; It enables many applications in areas such as authentication, security, usability and more.
- Key materials and techniques for speech recognition include quality microphones, comprehensive data, computer performance and interactive learning models, energy absorption, acoustic models, statistical models, software extraction software, and machine learning algorithms. Deep learning models play an important role in achieving state-of-the-art results in speech recognition, speaker identification and other tasks. These models are trained on large and diverse databases containing speech samples from different speakers. Repositories are important for training and evaluating speech recognition models. Commonly used libraries include VoxCeleb, CommonVoice, LibriSpeech, TIMIT, and SRE datasets. TensorFlow, PyTorch, Google Speech Recognition API, Microsoft Watson SDK, IBM Azure and other software tools Speech to Text and Mozilla DeepSpeech to improve and train language teaching skills is used. We expect speech recognition to be incorporated into many products and services in the coming years.

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VOICE RECOGNITION DATABASE

VOICE TO TEXT TRANSFORMATION